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EDITORIAL NOTE

Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) is the official Journal of the Faculty of Education, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The Journal publishes article of diverse fields of interest in education. Papers reporting original research and extended version of already established conference and journal articles are welcomed. Papers for publication are selected through peer review process to ensure originality, relevance and readability. ZIJE is published bi-annually June and December.

The aim and scope of the journal is to provide an academic medium and an important reference for the advancement and dissemination of information that supports high level learning, teaching and research in the fields of education.

This edition, Volume 3, Number 3, September, 2023 is poised to present research reports in the following fields of education: Educational Foundations, Science Education, Educational Psychology, Curriculum & Instructional Technology, Guidance & Counselling, Philosophy & History of Education, Sociology of Education, Entrepreneurship Education, Special and Inclusive Education, Physical & Health Education, Religious Education, Gender Studies, Peace & Security Education among others. The articles in this volume are academic and professional discourse written by reputable scholars in their areas of specialization.

The Board remain indebted to its editorial members for the ceaseless support given towards successful publication of the Journal. In the same vein, we acknowledge quite sincerely the assistance and support of our esteemed consulting editors for ensuring the credibility of this edition. Also worthy of appreciation are the authors and their immense contributions to this publication.

Associate Professor Bashir Suleiman

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CALL FOR ARTICLES

The Editorial Board of Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) calls for scholarly articles for review and possible publication in its next edition (Volume 4). ZIJE publishes articles that emphasize on research development and application within the field of Education. All manuscripts are reviewed by editorial review committee. Contributions must be original, not previously or simultaneously published elsewhere, and are critically reviewed before they are published. Papers, which must be written in English Language, should have good grammar and proper terminologies. Also note that prospective articles are subjected to plagiarism assessment to estimate the percentage of originality of the papers. Hence, plagiarism threshold of $\leq 20\%$ is recommended.

Editorial Guidelines

1. Manuscripts including references, appendices, tables and diagrams should be double-spaced and single coded on A4 paper with generous margins (at least 1”/2.5cm).
2. Title should be explicit and not more than 19 words.
3. Title page should be arranged as follows: Title, author(s) full name, affiliation, full addresses, email addresses and phone numbers.
4. Abstract should be single line and not more than 250 words.
5. For conceptual papers, the body should have appropriate headings where necessary.
6. For empirical papers, it should be presented in the following order: Introduction, Objectives of the study, Research Questions and/or Hypotheses, Methodology, Results, Discussion of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations.
7. Acknowledgement (if any).
8. Quotations of more than 40 words should be indented and typed single spacing with indication of the pages where the quotes were lifted.
9. In-text citations should follow the APA 7th edition format.
10. References should be in range with 7th edition of APA Style.
11. Each table and figure should be presented within the manuscripts, with a brief and self-explanatory title.
12. All text within the table should be clearly legible, and all graphics and legends should be easily distinguished when printed in black and white.
13. Tables should be in horizontal lines only, with only blank space to separate columns.
14. Tables and figures that may be included in the main text of the paper should be numbered separately, in the sequence that they are mentioned in the text.
15. Figures should be saved in a neutral data format such as JPEG, TIFF or EPS.

Submission of Manuscripts & Assessment Fee

Manuscripts should be submitted directly to the Editor-in-Chief or Publication Editor through the following e-mail address: zijefugusau@gmail.com. Articles can be submitted between the periods of January to April ending for June publication, while July to October ending for December publication. Assessment fee for manuscript is #5,000.00 only.

Dr. Abubakar Sadiq Haruna

Publication Editor

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Assessment of Parental Socio-Demographic Determinants on Sexual Abuse among Senior Secondary School Students in Benin Educational Zone, Edo State

*Aideyan, Daniel Osarenmwanta Ph.D.¹

Email: daniel.aideyan@uniben.edu

Odigie, Eunice¹

Email: euniceodigie22@gmail.com

¹Affiliation of First Author (Department of Health, Safety and Environmental Education, University of Benin)

Abstract

This study assessed parental socio-demographic determinants on sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo state. Three research questions and hypotheses were raised to guide the study. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design and the population of the study comprised all public and register private senior secondary schools in Benin educational zone. The multi-staged sampling technique was used to select 184 male students and 200 female students making a total of 384 respondents for the study. A Self-structured questionnaire titled “Sexual Abuse among Secondary School Students (SASSS)” was used for the collection of data. The research instrument was validated and reliability coefficient of 0.73 was obtained using the test-retest reliability method. Data obtained were analyzed using chi-square inferential statistics. Findings revealed that there is no significant relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. Similarly, the study established a significant relationship between parental socio-economic status and family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. The researchers concluded that parental socio-economic status and family size are socio-demographic determinants on the occurrence of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone. On the contrary, marital status is not a parental socio-demographic determinant on the occurrence of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone. The researchers recommended that government and non-governmental agencies should develop support programs for families from lower socio-economic backgrounds.

Keywords: Parental socio-demographic, determinants, socioeconomic status, sexual abuse, students.

Introduction

The sexual abuse of children has been categorized by different researchers across the world as representing a global human rights violation of children with severe immediate and long-term health and social consequences (Hillis, James, Amobi, & Kress, 2016). Despite being a global epidemic, there is considerable debate over what exactly constitutes the sexual abuse of children. The variation in definitions is due to sexual abuse being a complex issue (De Jong, et al., 2015; Samms & Cholewa, 2014) and the definitions of CSA differ between cultures and societies (Meinck, et al, 2015). Different cultures have their standards by which sexual behaviours towards children are considered and judged as acceptable or deplorable. For instance, in a typical African culture, love and affection for children may be expressed by their parents, relatives and friends through various forms of touch or practices that may be seen as sexually stimulating in another culture, particularly in the Western culture. Hence, it is crucial to employ culturally appropriate definitions when assessing child sexual abuse.

Sexual abuse of children is a grave and pervasive violation of human rights that continues to plague societies worldwide, transcending cultural, geographic, and socio-economic boundaries. It encompasses a range of acts, from sexual exploitation and molestation to trafficking and forced pornography, all of which have devastating and lasting effects on the physical, psychological, and emotional well-being of children. In Nigeria, like many other countries, child sexual abuse remains a significant and deeply concerning issue, demanding urgent attention and targeted interventions. In Nigeria, community-based surveys among in-school and out-of-school adolescents indicated high levels of CSA. In a study from Maiduguri, North-East Nigeria, a sexual assault rate of 77.7% was reported among female children’s workers with sexual assault being more likely in girls who were younger than twelve (12) years (Audu, et al., 2009). Also, Kunnuji and Essiet (2015) reported that about 14% and 35% of out of school adolescents in an urban slum in Lagos had been victims of rape and statutory rape, respectively. Olley (2008) and Manyike, et al. (2015) reported a child sexual abuse (CSA) prevalence of 55% and 40% among in-school

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adolescents in Southwest and South-east Nigeria, respectively. Other studies based on newspaper accounts indicate a high incidence of sexual abuse of children in different parts of Nigeria (Okonkwo & Naish, 2013; Akpoghome & Nwano, 2016).

Several socio-demographic factors are known to play a pivotal role in shaping the vulnerability of school children to child sexual abuse. Parental attributes, including marital status, family size and socioeconomic status may significantly influence a child's risk of falling victim to sexual abuse. Parental socioeconomic status has been cited as a determinant of sexual abuse of children. The socioeconomic status involves family income, education and occupational status. Specifically, on parental level of education predicting sexual abuse of children, Chime, Orji, Aneke and Nwoke (2021) revealed that the prevalence of CSA is higher among students whose parents achieved secondary school education and above than those with primary school education and below. In contrast, Abodunrin, et al. (2014) reported that children from parents with secondary and tertiary level of education were less likely to experience sexual abuse than the less educated ones. For example, lower levels of education in fathers may be correlated with increased risk of child sexual abuse in some populations or settings. This could be due to various reasons, such as lower education levels being associated with increased stress, financial difficulties, mental health issues, and other risk factors that may impact parenting behaviours and family dynamics (Brown & Williams, 2016).

On the relationship between maternal educational level and sexual abuse of children, Johnson and Stone (2014) suggest that a mother's level of education could potentially impact child sexual abuse risk factors in different ways. For example, higher education levels may be associated with increased awareness of child sexual abuse prevention strategies, better access to resources, and improved parenting skills, which may potentially reduce the risk of child sexual abuse. On the other hand, lower education levels may be associated with increased stress, limited access to resources, and other challenges, which may potentially increase the risk of sexual abuse of children. In explaining the higher prevalence rate of sexual abuse of children across higher educational level, Akinsulire (2017) stated that parents with higher educational qualifications tend to have better employment opportunities as they work outside the family setting, exposing their children to sexual abuse through lack of parental protection and supervision. On the relationship between parental employment status and the prevalence rate of sexual abuse of children, Abera et al. (2021) reported that adolescents whose fathers were self-employed or salaried were more up to five times more likely to be sexually abused and this may be attributed to the fact that such fathers had better employment opportunities and so were away from home (Akinsulire, 2017).

Furthermore, parents' income influences the incidence of abuse of children including child sexual abuse. Hurst (2021) illustrated that children from families seeking financial assistance were over two times more likely to suffer for child labour and sexually abused. In line with this, Okpukpara (2015) reported that the incident of child abuse including child sexual abuse was high among learners whose parents' income was N50,000 and below. It was to a low extent for learners whose parents' income was N51,000 and above. The finding was in consonance with that of Elgbeleye and Olasupol (2011) who found out that parents of low-income status showed significant high tendencies toward child labour practices (which is a predisposing factor for sexual abuse of children) than their high-income counterparts. In general, Sedlak, Mettenburg, Basena et al. (2010) report that children from families with low SES were twice as likely to experience sexual abuse and three times more likely to be endangered than children from families with higher SES. In a recent study, Lee, Coe and Ryff (2017) report a higher risk of severe and multiple types of sexual abuse for children experiencing poverty during childhood. However, Oshima, Jonson-Reid and Seay (2014) found no significant difference in the rate of sexual abuse of children from more affluent and poor families.

Additionally, family size has also been cited as a predictor of sexual abuse of children. The number of children in a family was shown to be significantly associated with sexual abuse of children (Schoedl et al., 2010). In investigating the prevalence of child sexual abuse among secondary school adolescents in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria Gabriel-Job, Alikor and Akani (2019) reported that the prevalence of sexual abuse of children increased significantly from 30.9% in those that came from families of four children or less to 43.9% in those from families of more than four children. Corroborating this finding, Farah (2010) also reported that children who were abused were found to come from families who had significantly more children. A possible explanation for this finding could be that every additional child to the family leads to an increase in financial burden as well as an increase in the likelihood of the children engaging in child labour to financially support their parents thus increasing their vulnerability to child sexual abuse. Also, there seems to be a relationship between family disruption and the prevalence of sexual abuse of children. This view is corroborated by previous studies on family disruption and history of CSA (Fomby & Cherlin 2007; Li & Wu, 2008) where the role of a stable family in preventing sexual abuse of children was highlighted. Disruptions of family structure either by death or divorce may reduce parental control during childhood and adolescence thereby making children more exposed to potential child sexual abuse perpetrators (Yahaya, 2012).

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Conclusively, in societies worldwide, including the African context, parents universally uphold the belief that children are the most treasured assets and the bearers of tomorrow's hope. This cherished philosophy underlines the imperative of nurturing a childhood marked by happiness and devoid of crises, uncertainties, and danger. Regrettably, despite the deeply rooted commitment by government and non-governmental agencies to nurturing and safeguarding children, Sexual abuse of school children still lingers as an acute social dilemma, and an egregious violation of human rights that continues to undermine the well-being of children across the world. In light of this disconcerting dissonance between the cherished philosophy of childhood and the persistently distressing prevalence of sexual abuse, it becomes imperative to comprehensively investigate the parental socio-demographic determinants that contribute to this grave issue particularly within the context of Benin educational zone of Edo State, Nigeria, as understanding how parental socio-demographic factors intersect with the occurrence of sexual abuse is essential for formulating effective and targeted interventions.

Objectives of the study

The objective of the study was to assess the parental socio-demographic determinants on sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. Specifically, the study investigated:

1. The relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.
2. The relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.
3. The relationship between parental socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State?
2. What is the relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State?
3. What is the relationship between socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.
2. There is no significant relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.
3. There is no significant relationship parental socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.

Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The descriptive research design accurately and systematically describes, observes or validates aspects of groups collected through quantifiable information without manipulation of the variables (Siedlecki, 2020). Based on Siedlecki (2020) description of the descriptive survey research design, the researcher was able to use this design to effectively provide an in-depth assessment of the socio-demographic determinants on sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. The population of the study comprised all the public and registered private senior secondary schools in the seven (7) local government areas that make up the Benin Educational Zone. The total population of public senior secondary school student is thirty-one thousand, seven hundred and twenty-five (31,725) while that of registered private senior secondary school is seventy-five thousand, five hundred and forty-seven (75,547). This gives a total population of one hundred and seven thousand, two hundred and seventy-one (107,271) senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone (Edo state Ministry of Education, 2022). Sample size of 384 respondents was selected using the Cochran's formulae. The sample was selected using multi-stage sampling technique. In the first stage, three (3) Local Government Areas was selected from the seven (7) Local Government Areas in Edo South senatorial district of Edo using simple random sampling technique of balloting by replacement. In the second stage, stratified random sampling technique was used to group the schools into rural school and urban school based on their location.

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In the third stage, Two (2) schools (one public urban school and one public rural school) were selected from each of the three Local Government Areas using simple random sampling technique of balloting by replacement. Lastly, simple random sampling technique of balloting by replacement was used to select 18 female respondents and 14 male respondents from each of the six selected schools. The same procedure was repeated to select sample from the registered private schools.

Table 1: Sample distribution

S/N	School Type	No. of schools selected	No. of school children selected	
			Male	Female
1.	Public Urban Schools	3	46	50
2.	Public Rural Schools	3	46	50
3.	Private Urban Schools	3	46	50
4.	Private Rural Schools	3	46	50
	Total	12	184	200
	Grand total			384

The research instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled “Sexual Abuse among Secondary School Students (SASSS)”. The instrument has two sections: sections A and B. Section A sought the socio-demographic information of the respondents, while Section B sought the parental socio-demographic information of respondents. However, items on parental socio-economic status were adapted from Gaur’s socio-economic classification (2013). The instrument was content validated, and a reliability index of 0.73 was obtained using the test-retest reliability method, thereafter subjecting the scores obtained from both administrations of the instrument to Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Socio-demographic variables were coded thus: marital status (married=1, separated =2, divorced=3 widowed=4); family size (1-2 children=2, 3-4 children =4, 5 children and above=6) and socio-economic status (positively worded question, yes=1point, no=0point; negatively worded question, yes= 0point, no=1point). Marital status was further measured as intact and disrupted family; family size was measured as small, moderate and large family size and socio-economic status was further measured as Upper, Middle and Lower Class.

The research instrument was administered by the researcher and three research assistants who were trained on the objectives of the research. The research instrument was administered after seeking due permission from the school principals. Also, the respondents were briefed on the purpose of the study alongside a general overview of child sexual abuse. The respondents were assured of utmost confidentiality regarding their responses and administered questionnaires were retrieved immediately upon completion after checking to ensure their level of completeness by respondents. This enabled the researcher to obtain a 100percent return rate. The collected data was coded and analyzed using frequency counts, simple percentages and Chi-square inferential statistics.

Ethical approval was obtained from the University of Benin Teach hospital Research and Ethic Committee and a formal permission to allow the selected schools to participate in the research was requested and granted through the Commissioner of Education and Principals of each of the selected schools. To maintain confidentiality of the respondents, respondents were asked not to indicate their names on the questionnaires.)

Results

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State?

Table 2: Descriptive statistics on the relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State (n=384)

S/N	Parental marital status	Sexual Abuse	
		Yes f (%)	No f (%)

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1.	Married	143 (37.24%)	84 (21.88%)
2.	Separated	56 (14.58%)	33 (8.59%)
3.	Divorced	15 (3.91%)	15 (3.91%)
4.	Widowed	26 (6.77%)	12 (3.12%)
	Total	240	144

(Researchers' fieldwork, 2023)

Table 2 reveals the descriptive statistics on the relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. It can be observed that 143(37.24%) respondents who had been sexually abused indicated that their parents were married. Also, 56(14.58%), 15(3.91%) and 26 (6.77%) respondents who had been sexually abused indicated that their parents were separated, divorced and widowed respectively. Therefore, it can be deduced that the parents of majority of the respondents who have experienced sexual abuse were married.

Research Question 2:

What is the relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State?

Table 3: Descriptive statistics on the relationship between relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State (n=384)

S/N	Family Size	Sexual Abuse	
		Yes f (%)	No f (%)
1.	1-2 children	95 (24.74%)	40 (10.42%)
2.	3-4 children	109 (28.39%)	92 (23.96%)
3.	4 children above	36 (9.38%)	12 (3.12%)
	Total	240	144

(Researchers' fieldwork, 2023)

Table 3 reveals the descriptive statistics on the relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. It can be observed that 95(24.74%) respondents who had been sexually abused indicated had a family size of 1-2 children. Also, 109 (28.39%) and 36(9.38%) respondents who had been sexually abused indicated that have a family size of 3-4 children and 4 children and above respectively. Therefore, it can be deduced that majority of the respondents who have experienced sexual abuse had a family size of 3-4 children.

Research Question 3:

What is the relationship between socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State?

Table 4: Descriptive statistics on the relationship between socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State (n=384)

S/N	Socio-economic status	Sexual Abuse	
		Yes f (%)	No f (%)
1.	Upper Class	30 (7.81%)	23(5.99%)
2.	Middle Class	142 (36.98%)	87 (22.66%)
3.	Lower Class	68 (17.71%)	34 (8.85%)
	Total	240	144

Source: Researchers' fieldwork

Table 4 reveals the descriptive statistics on the relationship between socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. It can be observed that 30(7.81%) respondents who had been sexually abused belong to the Upper Class while 142(36.98%) and 68(17.71%) respondents who have been sexually

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abused belong to Middle Class and Lower Class respectively. It can be deduced therefore, that majority of the respondents who have experienced sexual abuse are from the Middle Class.

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant relationship between parental marital status and the sexual abuse among school children in Edo South Senatorial District of Edo State

Table 5: Chi-square analysis on the relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State (n=384).

S/N	Marital status	Sexual Abuse		χ^2	df	Sig.
		Yes O(E)	No O(E)			
1.	Intact family	143(141.9)	84(85.1)	0.058	1	0.110
2.	Disrupted family	97(98.1)	60(58.9)			

1point=intact family, 2-9points=disrupted family; P>0.05

Table 5 shows the Chi-square analysis on the relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. The table indicates a calculated chi-square value of 0.058, degree of freedom 1 and level of significance of 0.110 which is greater than the set alpha level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo state is retained. The table clearly indicates no significant differences in the number of respondents (143) from intact family (a family where both parent are still married) who had experienced child sexual abuse and respondents (97) from disrupted family (a family where both parent are no longer together due to separation, divorce or death) who had also been sexually abused. The conclusion here therefore, is that there is no significant relationship between parental marital status and the occurrence of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.

Table 6 shows the Chi-square analysis on the relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.

Table 6: Chi-square analysis on the relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State (n=384).

S/N	Family size	Sexual Abuse		χ^2	df	Sig.
		Yes O(E)	No O(E)			
1.	Small family size	95(84.4)	40(50.6)	12.63	2	0.002
1.	Moderate family size	109(125.6)	92(75.4)			
2.	Large family size	36(30)	12(18)			

2points=small family size, 4points=moderate family size, 6points=large family size; P=<0.05

secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. The table indicates a calculated chi-square value of 12.63, degree of freedom 2 and level of significance of 0.002 which is lesser than the set alpha level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State is rejected. The table clearly shows a significant difference in the number of respondents (95) from small family size (a family of 1-2 children) who had experienced sexual abuse and respondents (145) from moderate and large family size (a family of 3-4 children and 4 children and above, respectively) who had also have been sexually abused. The conclusion here therefore, is that there is a significant relationship between family size and the occurrence of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.

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Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant relationship between parental socio-demographic socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State

Table 7: Chi-square analysis on the relationship between parental socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State (n=384)

S/N	Socio-economic status	Sexual Abuse		χ^2	df	Sig.
		Yes O(E)	No O(E)			
1.	Upper Class	30(17.44)	23(10.56)	32.32	2	0.001
2.	Middle Class	142(113.35)	87(68.65)			
3.	Lower Class	68(53.21)	34(32.1)			

15-23points=Upper Class, 5-14points=Middle Class, 0-4points=Lower Class; P<0.05

Table 7 shows the Chi-square analysis on the relationship between parental socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. The table indicates a calculated chi-square value of 32.32, degree of freedom 2 and level of significance of 0.001 which is lesser than the set alpha level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between parental socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State is rejected. The table clearly indicates a significant difference in the number of respondents from upper class (30), middle class (142) and lower class (68) that had experienced sexual abuse as against those who haven't. The conclusion here therefore, is that there is a significant relationship between parental socio-economic status and the occurrence of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State

Discussion of Findings

On parental marital status, findings revealed that there is no significant relationship between parental marital status and the occurrence of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. In line with this, this study revealed no significant differences in the number of respondents from intact family who had experienced child sexual abuse and respondents from disrupted family who had also been sexually abused. This view is contrary to findings from previous studies (Fomby & Cherlin 2007; Li & Wu, 2012) which indicated a significant relationship between family disruption and history of CSA. The researcher attributes this contrary finding to the fact that sexual abuse is a multifactorial phenomenon influenced by a variety of factors such as the respondents' individual and environmental characteristics. Hence, the respondents' individual and environmental characteristics may better predispose them to sexual than parental marital status.

Furthermore, findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between family size and the occurrence of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. In line with this, this study established a significant difference in the number of respondents that had experienced sexual abuse and those who did not based on their family size. Specifically, respondents from moderate and large family size experienced sexual abuse more than those from small family size. This finding is similar to the findings of Gabriel-Job, Alikor and Akani (2019) who reported that the prevalence of sexual abuse increased significantly from 30.9% in those that came from families of four children or less to 43.9% in those from families of more than four children. Family size being a predisposing factor may be attributed to the fact that large family families may face additional stressors related to financial, mental and emotional demands, which could impact family dynamics and increase the risk of sexual abuse. High levels of stress, lack of resources, and other challenges may affect parental capacity to effectively protect their children and create an environment that is conducive to healthy child development. Conclusively, a significant relationship between parental socio-economic status and sexual abuse was established by this study. This finding is similar to the findings of Sedlak et al. (2010) who report that children from families with low SES were twice as likely to experience sexual abuse and three times more likely to be endangered than children from families with higher SES. In contrast, Oshima, Jonson-Reid and Seay (2014) found no significant relationship between SES and child sexual abuse. The researcher noted that the high prevalence of sexual in respondents from low socio-economic status may be due to several factors including the lack of resources in schools and other institutions serving low income communities to identify, prevent and respond to cases of sexual abuse. Also, families living in poverty may often face high level of stress and may experience violence, substance abuse or other problems that can increase the risk of child sexual abuse.

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Conclusion

This study provides insights into the parental socio-demographic determinants on sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo state. Based on the findings of this study, the researchers concluded that marital status is not a parental socio-demographic determinant of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. However, family size and parental socio-economic status are parental socio-demographic determinants of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations were made:

1. There should be a prioritization of research into potential determinants of sexual abuse among school children such as family size and parental socio-economic status.
2. Government and non-governmental agencies should develop and implement community-based support systems that offer assistance and guidance to families with larger family sizes, helping them navigate the challenges that may contribute to child sexual abuse. Also, schools in collaboration with parents and caregivers should develop programs that provide parents with strategies for maintaining a safe and protective environment within larger families while emphasizing communication, supervision, and recognizing signs of abuse.
3. Government and non-governmental agencies should develop programs that aim to uplift families from lower socio-economic backgrounds, providing them with access to education, employment opportunities, and financial support. Also, the program should include an offer of educational workshops for parents from lower socio-economic backgrounds that focus on child protection, healthy parenting practices, and recognizing signs of abuse.

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Cloud Computing and its Application in Nigerian Libraries: Challenges and the Way Forward

Yakubu, Emmanuel John TRCN, CLN

Email: ejyakubu60@gmail.com

Tel: 08054169500

Federal University of Education, PMB 3045, Kano

Abstract

This paper is on cloud computing and the challenges to its application in libraries in Nigeria. The paper discussed the concept of cloud computing, the development and deployment of cloud computing, characteristics of cloud computing and types. The paper also discussed what to consider before implementing cloud computing, areas of application of cloud computing in libraries, and its benefits to libraries. Also, challenges to cloud computing application in libraries in Nigeria were discussed together with suggestions on how the identified challenges can be ameliorated. Some of the recommendations made are that: the nation's information and technology infrastructures and by extension, its Internet facilities should be improved upon from the present situation, solar energy should be explored as an alternative source of electricity power to replace the current unreliable power supply from the national electricity grid, among others.

Keywords: Application, Constraints, Cloud Computing, Libraries.

Introduction

The information environment in recent years has been changed by the convergence of ICTs such as computers, telecommunications, satellite broadcasting, and Internet technology. It is however the advent of the Internet that has so much impacted on the act of information dissemination in libraries and information centres around the world. The development of the Internet and other web enabled technologies on virtual platforms has helped to increase the opportunities for libraries and other similar organizations to use the services they provide for several purposes. Information flow and resource sharing has been also greatly enhanced by web technologies like 'cloud computing'. Cloud computing is the practice of using a network of remote servers hosted on the Internet to store, manage, and process data, rather than a local server or a personal computer. Library "users who have had the experience of using web 2.0 services like Wikipedia, blogs, and flickr etc; have already experienced cloud computing may be unknowingly" (Abidi and Abidi; 2012).

Today's "libraries have stepped up and are increasingly stepping into the realm of digital librarianship as well as platforms that extend IT's existing capabilities, and this extensively depends on using the cloud" (Movodza,2013).The use of cloud computing in education and other related areas of human endeavors is fast becoming very popular, and though cloud computing is a technology that has the potential of providing infrastructure and software solutions for the IT needs of libraries in Nigeria through the Internet, it is however only a few libraries that have adopted the technology (Seke,2015). Hence, the decision in this paper to consider cloud computing and the challenges of its application in libraries in Nigeria and proffer a way forward. This concept paper will provide an overview of cloud computing and its application in libraries in Nigeria. The paper also explored the various areas in the library's operations that cloud computing can be applied, the benefits of such application and the challenges associated with adopting cloud computing technology in Nigeria's libraries. The paper in conclusion also suggests ways the challenges identified can be minimized to enhance the use of the technology in libraries in Nigeria.

The Concept of Cloud Computing

The term "cloud computing" simply means "Internet computing". The Internet is metaphorically referred to as 'cloud' hence the term 'cloud computing' being used to denote computations carried out using the Internet. Users of cloud computing are able to access resources on data bases through the Internet from any location in the world and at any time they may need such resources without having to worry themselves about the problems associated with the maintenance or management of such resources (Wolf, 2010). Cloud computing combines the features of technologies like utility computing, unified computing, web 2.0, and the likes. The Garner Group (2009) defines cloud computing as "a style of computing in which massively scalable and elastic IT-enabled capabilities are delivered as service to external customers using Internet technologies". According to Kroski (2009) it "...means using web services for our computing needs which could include using software applications, storing data, accessing computing power, or using a platform to build applications". To the National Institute of Science and Technology (NIST,2012) cloud computing "...is a model for enabling convenient, on- demand network access to a shared pool

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of configurable computing resources (for ex, networks, servers, storage, applications and services) that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction”. On his part, Murky (2009), define cloud computing as “an emerging architecture by which data and applications dwell in cyberspace facilitating access to users through any web-connected device”. As Hoy (2012) further pointed out, “most cloud computing applications and infrastructures are built with the assumption that users will access them from the Internet, on multiple platforms and from any where in the world”. Cloud computing is nothing more than the collection of computing software and services that can be accessed via the Internet rather than residing on a desktop or internal server” (Stroh, Ache and Kumarl, 2009).

Figure 1: Shows a depiction of the Internet as a Cloud (Source: Yakubu, E.J; 2023)

Development and Deployment of Cloud Computing

How the term cloud computing originated is not clear, but the concept dates back to the 1960s, when John McCarthy first insinuated that “computation may someday be organized as a public utility” (wikipedia.org). It appears the term was derived from the practice of using drawings of stylized clouds to denote network in diagrams of computing and communication systems (Lewis, 2010). The cloud symbol was used to represent the Internet as early as 1994, but reference to cloud computing in the present sense was first made in 1996 in a Compaq internal document (Regalado,2001), and as computers became more popular, scientists and technologists explored ways to make large-scale computing power available to more users through time-sharing. What we know today as cloud computing is actually the result of the evolution and adoption of existing technologies and paradigms which allow users to take benefits from existing technologies without the need for deep knowledge about or expertise on any of them. The cloud aims to cut costs, and help the users focus on their core business instead of being impeded by IT obstacles (Hamdaqa, 2012).

Characteristics of Cloud Computing

The National Institute of Standards and Technology in Mell and Grance (2009) identifies five essential characteristics of cloud computing; these are:

1. **On demand self-service-** A consumer can unilaterally provision computing capabilities, such as server time and network storage, as needed automatically without requiring human interaction with each of the service provider.
2. **Broad network access-**capabilities are available over the network and accessed through standard mechanisms that promote use by heterogeneous thin and thick client platforms (e.g., mobile phones, tablets, laptops, and work stations).
3. **Resource pooling-** the provider’s computing resources are pooled to serve multiple consumers using multi-tenant model, with different physical and virtual resources dynamically assigned and reassigned according to consumer demands.

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4. **Rapid elasticity**- capabilities can be elastically provisioned and released, in some cases automatically to scale rapidly outward and inward commensurate with demand. To the consumer, the capabilities available for provisioning often appear unlimited and can be appropriated in any quantity at any time.
5. **Measured service**- cloud systems automatically control and optimize resource use by leveraging a metering capability at some level of abstraction appropriate to the type of service (e.g., storage, processing, bandwidth, and active user accounts). Resource usage can be monitored, controlled, and reported, providing transparency for both the provider and consumer of the utilized service.

Types of Cloud Computing and their Deployment in Libraries

Cloud computing is generally classified on the bases of services and usage.

Cloud Based on Services

- a. **Software as a service (SaaS)**- cloud providers install and operate application software in the cloud and users of cloud can access the software from cloud clients. The users are given access to application software and data bases online which they use without having to buy, install, run or maintain the software on their own servers. Since the cloud users do not manage the cloud infrastructure and platform on which the application is running, this then eliminates the need to install and run the application on the cloud user's own computers simplifying maintenance and support (Hamdaq, 2012). This service is used to provide email applications, free services, limitless storage, remote access from computers and devices that have Internet connection. Examples here include: Lib guides, salesforce.com, Google's Gmail and Apps, instant messaging from AOL, Yahoo and Google, also, VoIP from Vonage and Skype. These services (SaaS) are used in integrated library management and retrieval system for computing. The open-source software and open standards are also used for Internet based services towards next automated library system.
- b. **Infrastructure as a service (IaaS)**: This is the most basic cloud service model. In this service, a wide range of services, features and resources that can help in the building of a virtual infrastructure for computing are offered. Cloud providers offer these together with storages, networking and processing of data. They offer computers as physical or in most cases as virtual machines and other resources. The virtual machines are run as guests by a hypervisor, such as a Xen or XVM. Management of pools of hypervisors by the cloud operational support system leads to the ability to scale to support a large number of virtual machines (Amies, Sluiman, Tong and Liu, 2012). Vendors for IaaS are: Amazon.com for Elastic compute cloud (EC2) or simple storage service (S3), VMW, vCloud, IBM, Rack space, savvis, etc.
- c. **Platform as a service (PaaS)**: Here, cloud providers deliver a computing platform or application infrastructure which users require to build and run their web-based applications (soft wares and other tools) without managing the software and hardware. The user does not need to know programming language, database management systems and so on, to run the application, vendors of this service include: windows Azure, salesforce.com, ADP payroll processing, Google maps/ Google APP Engine etc.

What to Consider before Implementing Cloud Computing

When planning on applying cloud computing in the library, the following should be considered:

1. Who are the people that would be involved in the planning and preparation?
2. Deciding on compatibility of hardware and software to be used
3. Are software tools and other assistance available for the move?
4. What amount of data do you need to weed or covert to new format?
5. Who and how will the staff be trained once the new service is in place?
6. What new roles or tasks will IT cover?

Areas of Applying Cloud Computing in Libraries

As libraries try to make their services more accessible anywhere and at any time to users, they now deploy cloud computing services to achieve the goal. Cloud computing services and applications can be applied in libraries in the following areas:

1. **For file storage and preservation**- Using services such as Drop box, jungle Disk, Flickr, Google Doc, Sky Drive and the likes. Files can be stored, shared and accessed on the web from any place. Cloud based services like LOCKSS (Lots of copies keeps stuff safe), CLOCKSS (i.e. Controlled LOCKSS) and Portico tools are generally used to preserve digital documents in libraries.

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2. **For searching library Data base and for resource sharing-** The online computer library center catalogue (OCLC)'s Worldcat catalogue used for searching library data is presently available on the cloud. Through the OCLC Worldcat service, library services such as circulation, cataloguing, acquisition and so on, are provided on cloud via web share Management system that also facilitates the development of an open and collaborative platform which makes it easy for libraries to share their services, resources, ideas etc; with each other on the cloud.
3. **For setting up Digital libraries and repositories-** Every library needs a digital library through which it can make her resources and services accessible via the Internet, Duraspace has two software, namely Dspace and fedora commons. Fedora commons is the framework for digital repositories, while space is generally used for building digital libraries and repositories. Dura cloud which is closely related to Duraspace also provides open-source code needed to be installed on your libraries' machines. Duracloud provide storage and software you can use, and these you can subscribe to, if you want.
4. **For library Automation-** Polaris is a cloud-based library automation system which provides different types of cloud-based services for acquisition, cataloguing digital contents etc. The system uses a number of popular standards like, MARC 21, for bibliographic data, XML, Z39.50 for information retrieval, Unicode etc.
5. **For Hosting Library Websites-**Libraries may choose to host their websites on a third-party service provider's server instead of hosting them on their own servers. Website hosting was one of the earliest forms of cloud computing services provided. An example of a site hosting a library's servers which allows users to gain access from different locations on earth is Google sites.
6. **For scholarly content search-**The cloud-based platform that facilitates research and scholarly contents' sharing is Knimbus (Knowledge cloud). Knimbus is specifically designed and dedicated for knowledge discovery and collaboration among researchers and scholars. It enables them to discover and collaboratively share all kinds of knowledge.

Figure 2: shows the various areas of cloud computing application in libraries (Source: Yakubu, E.J, 2023)

Benefits of Adopting Cloud Computing in Libraries

Cloud computing has the following benefits when applied in libraries:

1. **Cost efficiency** –Using cloud computing helps the library to save costs in terms of extra charges on data storage, software updates, management and also reduces the cost of quality control.
2. **Low cost of maintenance-** Libraries does not have to pay any maintenance cost for hardware or software services provided to them by cloud providers. They only pay for resources used.
3. **Security-** Cloud services are made available to users 24/7 and as a result data centers go to great extent to ensure security and promote data integrity and confidentiality. Ordinarily, this will cost so much more if the library were to provide its own security.
4. **Provision of data back up and easy recovery-** A library that uses cloud services gets a safe back up for all her data and other documents. The recovery process for stored data in the cloud is very easy, fast and without much effort.

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5. **Unlimited storage capacity-** Cloud computing provides an unlimited amount of storage space for libraries. More data and documents can be stored in the cloud than on a library's machines, this eliminates the worry about the library running out of storage space on its machines or the need to upgrade such IT machines.
6. **Resiliency and redundancy-** In cloud computing, redundancy means that a duplicate copy of a document or data is available in the cloud, and a user who loses his or her data can always get a duplicate copy. The cloud is built on an architecture that is very robust and resilient hence providing resiliency and redundancy to its users. The resilience also includes disaster recovery services.
7. **Provide Easy Access to information and smaller learning curve-** the moment a user registers himself in the cloud, he gains access to information on the Internet from any part of the world. Cloud applications also provide smaller learning curves as people use them quietly.
8. **Users do not require any expertise-** The user does not need to master the application used in cloud computing to be able to use it. This means that anybody, with or without IT knowledge can use it (cloud computing).
9. **Quick deployment and ease of integration-** A cloud system can be deployed easily and kept running within a short period of time. A new user can be introduced directly to the system without their being required to wait for a period of time and this provide quick response to the end users.

Challenges Associated with the Adoption and Application of Cloud Computing in Libraries in Nigeria

In spite of the benefits that can be derived from applying cloud computing in libraries in Nigeria the following still remain issues that will need to be resolved:

1. **Internet bandwidth problem-** Deploying cloud computing require high bandwidth to enable usage. The Internet infrastructure in Nigeria is still relatively underdeveloped and there are no ways effective cloud computing services can be provided without high-capacity Internet bandwidth being available (Thomas, 2011; Suleiman, et al; 2017).
2. **Budget/funding constraints-** Money is required for subscription to cloud computing services and also to buy equipment required for setting up the service in libraries. The situation in most libraries in Nigeria is pathetic because they run their services on low budgets as a result of poor funding.
3. **Electricity/power supply issues-** Libraries need to provide Internet services 24/7 and without constant electricity/power supply this will not be possible and users' access to cloud services on the libraries' machines or on any other devices will be disrupted. Presently, electricity power supply in Nigeria is erratic and unstable (Suleiman, et al; 2017).
4. **Converting print documents to electronic ones-** Libraries' documents has to be in electronic formats for them to be made available on the cloud (Suleiman, et al; 2017). Most Libraries in Nigeria are yet to convert most of their documents like, theses and projects, and other documents to electronic formats, and this is a big issue.
5. **Lack of staff with technical knowledge and skills to provide I.T.** Support in the area of maintenance and management of the library's end of the cloud services (Suleiman, et al; 2017). This is a very important constraint in Nigeria.
6. **Security and privacy issues-** These are issues of major concern to libraries in Nigeria who want to use cloud computing services. The problem here involves unauthorized access to a library's data stored in the cloud. As different countries have different privacy requirements and standards, data stored on a cloud infrastructure hosted in a country where security and privacy laws are lax, can easily be compromised, thereby exposing such data to risk of a third party's unauthorized access (Thomas, 2011; Suleiman, et al; 2017). Nigeria at the moment lacks the capacity to provide cloud hosting infrastructures for her cloud users, all her cloud computing infrastructure needs are provided outside her shores by cloud companies she has no control over. The securities of the files are therefore in the hands of the company hosting them.

Conclusion

Cloud computing technology is fast becoming a necessity for libraries all over the world. As Lowry, Prudence, Karla and Stuart (2009) pointed out, "Libraries need to deliver services and resources to the virtual environments used by students, faculty and researchers or they risk alienating users". With cloud computing, libraries can meet all the information needs of different kinds of users, this is because with cloud computing, information is not stranded on individual machines, instead it is combined into one digital cloud and made available to users at the touch of a finger from many devices (Hamm, 2009). Nigeria's libraries too can key into this all-important technology (cloud computing) so as to reap from the benefits it provides in today's twenty first century information environment.

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Recommendations for the Effective Application of Cloud Computing in Libraries in Nigeria.

To ensure the effective application of cloud computing in Nigeria's libraries, the following are recommended:

1. The nation's information and technology infrastructures and by extension, its Internet facilities will need to be improved upon. Internet services providers need to step up in this area, when this is done, as this will facilitate the provision of high-capacity Internet bandwidth that will run 24/7 in the nation's libraries thereby enhancing their ability to provide cloud computing services to their users.
2. Currently, almost all libraries in Nigeria are faced with funding problems. There is the need therefore for governments and other stakeholders at all levels to increase their funding to the libraries under their control because without money it will not be possible for these libraries to acquire the facilities and other equipments needed for providing cloud services. On their part, the libraries can source for funds from philanthropic organizations and individuals (like the MacArthur foundation and so on), to enable them acquire the facilities for setting up Internet and cloud computing services in their libraries.
3. Electricity power from solar energy can be used to replace or supplement the electricity supplied from the national grid which is currently erratic and unstable. This is necessary because to provide 24/7 cloud computing services, a stable power supply source is required.
4. Libraries in the country that want to extend the full benefits of cloud computing to their patrons, will have to ensure that their information materials like projects, and other documents are converted to electronic formats for easy upload to the cloud where patrons and other users can easily access them online through their computers and other devices.
5. Libraries require staff with skills in desktop and server operating systems administration, programming, data base management systems and network designs as well as in other Internet technologies to be able to implement cloud computing services effectively in the libraries. Aside employing staff with these IT know-how, the libraries must make training and re-training of its staff a priority for them to be able to keep up with the constant changes taking place in the field of library and information science technology.
6. Security and privacy issues which are often a major concern for libraries that wants to use cloud computing need to be addressed. The library in selecting a cloud hosting service provider may need to take into cognizance, the safety of its data when uploading them to the cloud. As a way of advice, libraries should not upload data or documents whose safety and security they are not sure would be guaranteed on the clouds.

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Development of Multifunctional Mobile Teaching Aid for Basic and Secondary schools in Nigeria.

***Lawal, Sadiq Sius¹**

Email: Sadiq.lawal@futminna.edu.ng
Tel: 07064358815`

Adeyemi, Michael Bolaji¹

Email: mbadeyemi@gmail.com
Tel: 08054071923

Yakubu, Abdullahi²

Email: abdullahiyakub@fugusau.edu.ng
Tel: 07065699399

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, Federal University of Technology, Minna., Niger State Nigeria.

²Department of Science Education, Federal University of Gusau, Zamfara State Nigeria

Abstract

The inadequate supply of educational teaching aids and truly functional laboratories to aid teaching and learning in the basic, science, secondary and virtual schools across Nigeria and in fact globally due to high cost incurred in acquiring them has necessitated the invention of a multifunctional mobile teaching aid and intervention laboratory for schools. The invention relates to educational demonstrations, experimentations, display and instructional materials as home-grown, purpose-built game changer to positively disrupt the educational sector to enhance quality and effective Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education in Nigeria translating into reduced situation of mass failures in NECO, WAEC, NABTEB, IJMB, UTME, quality impactful teachers' delivery, students' participatory interests in studies, value for money and reduced capital flights from importation of apparatus. This innovation which has been adopted and deployed by the Kaduna and Niger state Governments with other Federal Ministries of Education, Science, Technology and Innovation provides multifunctional interfaces for variety of experiments on single equipment and its auxiliaries has made experimentation and teaching easier, more captivating its mobility around for appropriate purposes and it equally fits into existing conventional laboratories. The results obtained in basic science, physics, chemistry, biology and mathematics were conclusively effective and efficient using the innovation. The 170cm height of the equipment was experimentally obtained like it was being done in the conventional laboratory to measure the height of the ceiling using simple pendulum and the results of 165cm was gotten within +2.9% minimum experimental error with recommendation for height automation and collapsibility.

Keywords: Invention, Multifunctional, Mobile, teaching-aid, laboratory

Introduction

In Nigeria, the use of practical supports for theoretical teachings of science had always been through the conventional laboratories which contain auxiliaries like retort stands, clamps, beakers, burettes, ray boxes, pulley system and other experimental functionaries usually in small confinement that is not only conducive and convenient enough for effective participatory teaching and learning, but is also very expensive and expansive in space utilization (Lawal,2008). There have been several challenges facing the educational system of Nigeria; one of these challenges is the lack of proper equipment and teaching aids for the teachers to properly demonstrate the theoretically acquired knowledge for more understanding. These challenges were identified and finding lasting solutions propelled Lawal to build in his 2008 efforts to invent and patented (RP:NG/P/2014/398) science educational mobile intervention laboratory that is multifunctional mobile teaching aid that also serves as intervention laboratory for basic, science and secondary schools (Lawal,2016). It could equally be deployed virtually and through other information and technology means and social media platform especially in the case of any lockdown and shut down of schools. The overwhelming feedbacks from the teachers, schools and educational stakeholders especially Kaduna state government that has adopted the invention in her schools has been a strong endorsement of its utility and versatility as reported in leadership newspaper,2019, Engineering Forum News, 2019 and sunnews online,2021.To leverage on emerging technology culminating in further improvement, upgrade and automation from researchers and innovators on one hand and

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market interests from educational managers on the other hand, the need for the automation of the lifting mechanism of the equipment for appropriate height adjustment was carried out and reported by Alkali,2019, Inyang,2019, Paul,2019, Awoyemi, 2019 and Momoh,2021 with the original patent owner and inventor (Lawal,2016).

This paper therefore presents the potentials exploration of the multifunctional teaching aid which also serves as interventional laboratory to positively disrupt the educational improvement and standards in the country.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of this project was to develop a multifunctional mobile teaching aid and intervention laboratory for schools.

Research Question

How viable is

Methodology

Some major factors like cost, availability of raw materials and weight among others were put into consideration during the design of the project. Selection of the right materials during construction is a vital decision to make as it is a major factor that determines the success of project as the design engineer’s understanding of engineering materials and their properties is critical. The impact of production methods and heat treatment on the properties of materials must be understood by a construction engineer. The following are the key categories of engineering materials namely metals and their alloys, such as Iron, steel, copper, aluminum and Non-metals, such as glass, polymers, elastomers, ceramics etc. The parts and materials used in this work are presented in Table 1 below: -

Table 1 Parts and Materials used in the development of a multifunctional mobile teaching aids

PART NO	PART DESCRIPTION	QUANTITY REQUIRED	MATERIALS
1	Square pipe	418 feet, 1x1	Mild steel
2	Square pipe	18 feet, $\frac{3}{4} \times \frac{3}{4}$	Mild Steel
3	Rectangular pipe	118 feet, 2x1	Mild Steel
4	Laminated plywood	1 4ft by 8ft	MDF Wood
5	Hinges	2	Mild steel
6	Angle brackets	28	Mild steel
7	Rollers	4	Steel and plastic
8	Contact adhesive	1	Wood adhesive
9	Bolts and nuts	28M4,	Mild steel
10	Screws	$8 \frac{3}{4}$,	mild steel
11	Spur gears	2	Mild steel
12	Microcontrollers		
13	Edges tape		Plastic

Fabrication of Metal Frame

1. The pipes were marked out to the various lengths of the improved science educational mobile intervention laboratory metal frame using scribe, tape rule, and tri-square.
2. The marked-out lengths on the pipes were clamped on bench vice one after the other and were cut into the marked out dimensions using a hacksaw. Straightness of the hand during cutting was strictly ensured in order to obtain a straight cut-edge of the pipes.
3. The cut pipes were joined together in an orderly manner to obtain the exact shape of the designed metal frame of the work using the electric arc-welding machine at 120A, and E6013 electrode.
4. The angle brackets were welded to the metal frame on the right positions of the frame where the plywood is to be bolted to.
5. Four rollers, two with a stopper and two without stopper, were welded to the four legs of the frame.
6. All the welded joints on the metal frame were grinded to a fine surface using the hand-held grinding machine.

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7. Potty filler was applied to the grinded welded joints after been mixed with a hardener, and was scrubbed with a sandpaper to give it a fine-finished look.
8. The plywood was then marked out to the various dimensions using a tape rule and a pencil.
9. The marked-out dimensions on the plywood were cut out using the circular wood saw.
10. The 105cm by 100cm size board's edges was covered with edges tape, held firmly to the edges of the board using the wood adhesive.
11. The welded metal frame was sprayed with a white paint using a compressor spraying machine and left for a day to dry.
12. The cut plywood was attached to the metal frame using bolts, nuts, and a screwing machine.
13. 10mm holes were drilled on the 110cm by 100cm board with 1cm equidistance apart using a drill bit, and a hand-held drilling machine.
14. The perforated board was attached to the two arms of $\frac{3}{4}$ " pipes which protruded from the two sides of the table top using a U-shaped clamp.

Lifting Device Mechanism and Assembly

The lifting device made up of the components such as Scissor screw jack, Spur gears, 12v D.C motor, Transformer, Switch, Rectifier, Arduino, Keypad, LCD display and Microcontroller (Faraday, 2013, Rout *et al*, 2014 and Chaudhary *et al*, 2016) are required for the automation of the height adjustment as recommended by users. A jack is a mechanical lifting system that can be used to apply massive forces or raises large loads. For lifting heavy machinery, a mechanical jack used a screw loop. Hydraulic control is used by a hydraulic jack. 1st A car jack, floor jack, or garage jack is the most common type, which raises vehicles so that maintenance can be performed. Jacks are usually rated for a maximum lifting capacity (1.5 tons or more). A jack screw also known as a screw jack, is a jack that works by spinning a leadscrew. It is often used to lift moderately heavy weights, such as vehicles; to raise and lower the horizontal stabilizers of aircraft; and to provide flexible supports for heavy loads, such as house foundations (Rout *et al*, 2014).

Automation of Lifting Device

This automation of the lifting device could be handled by a device (microcontroller) used is an Arduino board which attached with wireless remote controls the upward and downward movement of the experimental board mounted on the lifting device. To lift the experimental board, the suited microcontroller (Bogdan, 2018).

Results

The invented multifunctional mobile teaching aid with multiple experimental set up on display are shown in Figures 2

Figure 2: The Invented and automated Multifunctional Teaching aid with the switch and remote control system.

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Experimentations

One of the experiments carried out was to determine the Height of the Equipment using the Simple Pendulum principle as shown schematically in Figure 3 below and pictorially in Figure 4.

Figure 3: Diagram of simple pendulum experiment to determine height of the equipment

Figure 4: Screenshot of the Simple Pendulum experimentation set up on the equipment

APPARATUS

1. Pendulum
2. Stop watch
3. Meter rule
4. String
5. Protruding bolt (rod)
6. Multifunctional Mobile teaching aid and Intervention laboratory

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Procedure:

The protruding bolt (rod) is attached inserted on the welded nut at the highest side of the experimental board the simple pendulum is then hung on the protruding rod and the height of the bob above the floor is adjusted for the various height starting with 20cm above the floor, the bob was set swinging through a small angle and the time for 20 oscillations was counted the experiment was repeated by adjusting the height above the floor for 30cm, 40cm, 50cm, 60cm.

The Table 2 below are the experimental readings from the multifunctional teaching aid and intervention laboratory.

Table 2 Values from the experimental readings

Height above floor (cm)	Time for 20 oscillation(s)			Period T(s)	T(S)
1 2 average					
20 48	49	48.5		2.42	5.88
30 46	46	46	2.3	5.29	
40 44	44	44	2.2	4.84	
50 42	42	42	2.1	4.41	
	60	40	40	40	2
					4.00

Theory and Calculations

From the simple pendulum equation for periodic time (T)

$$T = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{L}{g}}$$

But $L = H - h$ (1)

Where,

H = height of the experimental board

h = height of the bob above the floor

Therefore, $T = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{H-h}{g}}$ (Abbot,1989, Nelkon and Parker,1995) (2)

Expanding $T^2 = 4\pi^2 \frac{H-h}{g}$ (3)

$$\frac{gT^2}{4\pi^2} = H - h$$

When $T^2 = 0$,

$$H - h = 0$$

Which implies $h = H$ at $T^2 = 0$

Figure 5:

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Graph of period of oscillation against height of bob above floor
 Actual height of the experimental board is 170cm

From the graph in figure 5

When $T^2 = 0$, $h = 165\text{cm}$

This $H - h = 0$

$H = 165\text{cm}$

Error estimated = $(165 - 170)\text{cm} = -5\text{cm}$

% error = $\frac{\text{Difference in height}}{\text{Actual Height}} \times 100$

$\frac{-5}{170} \times 100 = 2.9\%$

(4)

This result shows another encouraging output of the multifunctional teaching aid and intervention with minimum experimental results and error of $165\text{cm} + 2.9\%$.

Screenshot from the Monograph of the equipment of some experimental set up and procedures for Physics, Chemistry and Biology are shown below:

Figure 6: Screenshot for the Monograph for the Experimental setup and procedures for Compound Pendulum, Moment Principle, Triangle of Forces and Hooke's Law in Physics

Figure 7: Screenshot from the Monograph of Experimental Setup and Procedures for Quantitative Analysis (Titration), Qualitative Analysis and Simple Distillation in Chemistry

Figure 8:

Figure 8: Screenshot from the Monograph of Experimental Setup and Procedures for Water holding Capacity of Soils, Osmosis in Bon-living System, Food Tests and Light Microscope in Biology

Figure 9: Screenshot from the Monograph of Experimental Setup and Procedures for Mathematical Shapes, Coordinates and Graph Plotting in Mathematics.

Conclusion

The multifunctional Mobile Teaching Aid and Intervention Laboratory invented and furthered automated was tested to perform some experiments in Physics, Biology, Chemistry, Mathematics and some basic technologies has shown its utility and versatility with promising status as a positive disruptive game changer in teaching, demonstrations and conduct of practical in science classes effectively for the improvement of the basic, science, secondary and technical educational standard in the country. The Simple pendulum experimental determination of the height of the equipment as 165cm against the actual height of 170cm with 2.9% minimum error is testament on the effectiveness of the multifunctional teaching aid and intervention laboratory.

Recommendation

Government at all levels, Educational Mangers and stakeholders and Non-governmental, local and international educational support organizations are urged to take advantage of this home-grown and purpose-built invention to enhance quality educational delivery, scientific and technological ripples so as to address effectively the often pervading dearth of equipment that is the usual narrative in our educational system.

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Effective E-learning Instruction in English Language Learning: The Role of Teachers and Students

Akintunde, Abraham Femi Ph.D.

Email: akinmatson@gmail.com

Tel.: +2348166813796

Department of Arts Education, Faculty of Education, University of Abuja

Abstract

The paper examines Effective E-learning Instruction in English Language Learning: The Role of Teachers and Students. This study reviews literature and gives a scholarly background to the study by reviewing some contributions made by various researchers and institutions on e-learning specification and its definitions. An important part of this paper also explores role of a teacher in e-learning and how to engage students actively in e-learning environment. The major conclusion of the study is that the utilization of computers will influence the way teachers teach and students learn. The paper then recommends that researchers and practitioners need to work more on how technology could be adequately explored, in order to facilitate and foster more successful communication in e-learning classroom.

Keywords: E-learning, ICT, Teacher, Classroom and Feedback.

Introduction

In the information management systems, human agents can be considered one of the most important factors that make system run more smoothly (Trinder, 2016). In this manner, role of teachers in the e-learning environments are very important. The questions "Does the importance of teacher decrease as the technology grows?" And "What is the role of teachers in e-learning systems?" are very important to answer to estimate the productivity of the systems (Salmon, 2013). When we think about the role of the teacher in the learning environment, it could be suggested that the importance of the teacher is growing (Badia., Garcia, & Meneses, 2017). The educators afford should be more intensive to adaptation of new learning environments should be an answer to this question. But there are some issues in order to adapt these new learning environments. These issues of adapting to the environment are related to understand the concept and the work process of these environments. For example, administrators of the institutions can understand some basic concepts of e-learning such as how it works and where and why to benefit from it. However, these decision makers will find themselves in the point of milestone to apply or not apply the concept in their institutions. More importantly, teachers also will be a point of a decision making when they need to teach any course in e-learning (or blended) (Akintunde & Akuta, 2022). Teaching is considered a very important profession as it works as a productive factory to provide the builders of a nation. It needs expertise for the justification of teaching because it is considered a tri-polar activity which involves three important stages: Input-activity- output (Trinder, 2016). The success of teaching is at the same time "a target achieved" for a learner and "success" for a teacher. Teaching English as a second language is always a difficult job as it requires knowledge, skill, innovations and dedication of the teacher. If an English teacher possesses such qualities, his efforts can become fruitful and he can achieve the objectives of his work. A teacher is a person who has learnt the teaching skills and possesses the ability to train the learners for a career. There are some teachers who are "born teachers "and they do not require too much training in teaching skill as compared to those who do not adopt teaching profession as their first choice. Both types of such teachers can gain something through training programmes but the former ones can get lot better out of teacher training programmes. There is no doubt that teacher is a tower of light who brightens the minds and produces future generation of the world (Salmon, 2013).

In the past, the traditional view about a good teacher was that a person who had rich knowledge of something. Such person was given respect and whatever he said was believed and obeyed. Now, the things have changed drastically. People have become critical and scientific minded. There is variety and vastness in every subject these days. This has given rise to the concept of specialization in pedagogy. A teacher of today has to learn different skills and knowledge of modern technology (Trinder, 2016). Teachers of English language play a pivotal role in the performance of the institution. As English teachers have to work under sensitive responsibilities, they need to know about their pedagogical objectives of the learners as well as the professional growth of themselves. They cannot gain any progress until they are aware of their multiple roles and responsibilities.

E-learning Specification and its Definitions

There is not just one way of defining e-learning, there is a number of different definitions and terms to describe the use of the technology in education: online learning, web-based learning, web-based training, e-learning. It is fundamentally defined as learning facilitated through Information and Communications Technologies (ICT), the implementation of which has recently played an important role in the field of language (Salmon, 2013). The American Society for Training and Development defines e-learning as the entire group of technology-based learning, covering a wide set of applications and processes that include computer-based learning, web-based learning, virtual classrooms and digital collaboration. It is delivered by electronic means including the internet, intranet, satellite broadcasting, audio, video, interactive television and CD ROM (Garrison & Anderson, 2013). On the contrary, Rosenberg (2008) claims that CD-ROMs and DVDs should not be classified as e-learning for their lack of networkability. Badia., Garcia, and Meneses (2017) defines e-learning as a multimedia support of an educational process with the modern Information and Communications Technologies usage. It is realised by means of a computer network and its basic task is to provide unlimited access to education without the normal constraints of classroom time and space. When carried out, the e-learning course functions as a support of the educational process. Salmon (2013) defines e-learning very simply, as an educational process with the use of Information and Communications Technology. This definition is too broad and does not reflect the basis of e-learning as a method through which an educational process is realised. In Pedagogical Dictionary (Badia., Garcia, & Meneses, 2017) e-learning is defined as the determination of different kinds of learning supported by computers, usually using modern technological means - particularly CD-ROM. Electronic learning is spread in the spheres of both distance education and corporate education. Garrison and Anderson (2013) view e-learning as learning that is facilitated online through network technologies. "E-learning is networked, online learning that takes place in a normal context and uses a range of multimedia technologies." They point out that the essential feature of e-learning extends beyond its access to information and builds on its interactive and communicative features. E-learning of the 21st century is seen as a new "ecology of learning". The authors characterise it as the technology transforming educational institutions, comprehension of teaching and learning and experience. They stress the uniqueness of e-learning as it consists in the control and responsibility for self-learning, in the art of critical thinking, in the managing of our own learning, constructing knowledge, and in the interaction, the result of which is various skills and knowledge. It supports both synchronous and asynchronous communication ranging from texts, through visuals to voice. The educational advantage is its capacity to support reflective text-based interaction, independent of time and distance. The authors speak about the so called value-add of e-learning that is created by an integrated social, cognitive and teaching environment (community of inquiry). The philosophical perspective of their comprehension reflects a constructivist view of teaching and learning. According to Fedyunina (2016), e-learning is a complex process the basis of which is a special pedagogical approach to learning. Methodology of effective e-learning should be based on the following criteria: engaging learners in the learning process, encouraging independent learning skills, developing learners' skills, and motivating learners. The scientist mentions that universities make investments in e-learning because they realise that it is borderless education, there is high demand from students, and a growing competition for students on the global education market. The potential of e-learning is seen in six key dimensions:

1. Connectivity - access to information,
2. Flexibility - learning any time, at any place,
3. Interactivity – assessment of learning can be immediate,
4. Collaboration - discussion tools supporting collaborative learning,
5. Extended opportunity - e-content reinforces and extends classroom-based learning,
6. Motivation - it can make learning fun.

E-learning is defined as learning facilitated and supported through the use of Information and Communications Technology; it occupies the central position in self-access (Akintunde & Akuta, 2022a). E-learning can be used as *supporting learning* for existing courses, *blended learning* as combination of traditional and electronic practice and *fully on-line learning* (Fedyunina, 2016).

Additionally, Fedyunina (2016) agrees that computers and other new technologies have become an important aspect of foreign language learning. He stresses that e-learning substantially contributes to increased affectivity of the educational process and defines e-learning as "using new multimedia technologies and the Internet to improve the quality of learning" (Fedyunina, 2016). Hronova (2011) defines e-learning in a broader sense. He views it as a new and modern concept of education and as a means by which we can educate ourselves outside of the traditional classroom setting. Nevima (2012) states that "e-learning can be characterised as electronic education which uses Information and Communications Technologies in order to increase education quality and efficiency". He points out that nowadays students can have easier access to e-

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learning through utilizing the opportunity to connect the Internet with a mobile phone. He sees e-learning as an efficient form of education because students do not lose continuity in subject-matter in case they are ill for a long time.

Another definition of e-learning refers to "learning that takes place using technology, such as the Internet, CD-ROMs and portable devices like mobile phones or MP3players" (Dudeney & Hockly, 2017). Dudeney and Hockly (2017) mention the following terms associated with e-learning that are often used interchangeably and can be confusing: **online learning** is learning that takes place via the Internet, and is understood here as a facet of e-learning. The next term is **open learning** that is connected with the degree of learners' independence and is comprehended as one aspect of distance learning. The last term is **blended learning**, which is a mixture of face-to-face and online learning (Akintunde & Angulu, 2021). These words are all associated with e-learning in the sense of online teaching and learning.

As we could see, the literature offers a number of definitions, multiple terms and concepts, which reflect authors' cultural, educational and institutional backgrounds. Some definitions focus on technological aspects, some more on the educational process of learning. But the focus of the means of these technologies is on students' preparation for an acquisition of the foreign language which actually helps to avoid the state of uncertainty, restraint experienced by people in a native -speaking environment (Vasbieva & Kalugina, 2016).

Role of a Teacher in E-learning

The role of a teacher depends on what the teacher wants his/her students to achieve; the teacher should be able to switch between various roles and be aware of how to carry them out (Nevima 2012)). The role of teachers changed in the history of language teaching with the change of teaching methods. As Hronova (2011) mentions some methods depend on the teacher as a source of knowledge, others see his/her role as a consultant, guide, counsellor etc. Similarly, Nevima (2012) describes different roles of teachers in relation to different teaching methods. She exemplifies the role of a teacher as a source of knowledge and a controller in Grammar-Translation Method; the role of a prompter, guide and organizer in the Direct Method; the role of a native-speaker in Audio-Lingual Method; the role of a facilitator, organizer, guide, researcher, assessor and manager in Communicative Language Teaching; and the role of a counsellor and psychologist for example in Suggestopedia. Actions of teachers reflect their attitudes and abilities and teachers present role-models which students can follow in their future use of the language. The roles stated in the CEFR include a manager (classroom management skills), a researcher (ability to engage in action research), the ability to reflect on experience, ability to handle testing, assessment and evaluation, ability to develop students' aesthetic appreciation of literature, ability to deal with individualisation within classes containing diverse learner types, ability to teach sociocultural background information (CEFR, n.d. p. 144)

In learning the language in the classroom or outside the classroom, the role a teacher plays may vary in doing one activity to another activity. When a teacher has been good in making this change, automatically s/he effectiveness as a language teacher will increase. All roles played by a teacher in language learning aim to facilitate student development so that it needs to be applied appropriately. In some of the activities teachers do in the classroom, a teacher may act as a facilitator, and many other teacher roles according to Izadinia (2015) in e-learning classroom are described below:

Teacher as Controller: In this case, the teacher is the one who served as the controller, and when the teacher acts as a controller, they are responsible in the class and also responsible for all activities that occur in the e-learning language classroom. In this case, the teacher plays a role, tells the students who need to be informed, organizes the exercises, reads loud and the other role is to give an example or show how to do something with good quality to the students (Akintunde & Angulu, 2015). Teachers who usually only perceive their work as a transfer of knowledge are usually very comfortable with the role of controller. Many students can remember teachers in their past who only gave instructions and who have inspired their students with the knowledge and charisma they have. However, not all teachers have the ability to inspire students. There are certain times for the teacher to perform his role as a controller, such as when making announcements, while restoring circumstances, while giving explanations, or when a teacher is leading question and answer in the classroom (Hronova 2011).

Teacher as Organizer: Acting as an organizer in e-learning language classroom is one of the most important roles, in which case, the teacher must organize the students as well as the very diverse activities in language learning. Usually, activities in this field are to provide information to students, telling them how to do things, varying their study groups either in pairs or groups and finally ending something and typed something that ends or finishes (Akintunde & Akuta, 2022b). This role is very important to be played by a teacher when in a timely manner. For example, when students do not understand what they should be doing, they may not benefit from the ongoing activities or from the teacher's role as an organizer. The main thing teachers pay attention to in organizing something is to get students involved and ready in all the activities they organize. Or in other words, can be said when something new will be done, teacher should make sure that the activity is interesting. In this case, a

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teacher must be creative in informing the activities that he will engage the students. Meaning that,, teachers should be able to attract student’s attention so that they can be enthusiastic in doing these new activities. When students are ready for activities, this is where teacher will guide them in doing their activities with instructions either directly or indirectly. It is also possible to conduct a demonstration against students in terms of testing their level of understanding in doing something (Vasbieva & Kalugina, 2016).

Teacher as an Assessor: One of the things students expect from their teachers is an indication that they are right or wrong when they speak the language they are learning. In this case, teachers act as assessors. This means that as a teacher, he has to offer feedback to students as they speak and correct their mistakes in using the language and assess them in a variety of ways. Students also need to know how and for what they are assessed. Teacher has to tell the students what s/he is looking for and how far they have succeeded so that they can compare their abilities from what teachers have told them. For example, when a teacher wants to judge something, he can say ‘Okay now we are going to practice the conversation in pairs, so, choose each pair, and make a conversation with the topic of travel. What I value from this conversation is the correct speech and grammar’ from the notice, students will know to which areas they should concentrate. Also, teachers need to know the problem of honesty in assessing. Students can also know whether teachers are fair in judgment or not (Wright, 2017).

Teacher as Prompter: In this case, the teacher has a role as a whisperer. For example, in an activity or in a presentation, students are silent and do not remember what to say or they ran out of vocabulary when going to say something. This is where the teacher's role as a prompter can be applied. For example, in the case above, whether the teacher let them until they remember or can find the right words typed would say something. Or the teacher gives a clue, so, they can say it or even the teacher immediately tells the word they need. In this case, also, a teacher should be wise. For example, when writing, a teacher asks students the reason why they wrote it. After that, the students will give a reason but it is very difficult to get started. Teachers may provide words that can help him find answers to the teacher's questions.

Teacher as Participant: A tradition that often occurs during a discussion or a student's role play is the teacher as the organizer of the activities in the class. He can just interfere with the affairs or simply gives feedback to the students or even justifies the wrong when after the discussion is over. Basically, there are also certain times where teachers should not be teachers but participant. There are several reasons that support that teachers should sometimes act as participants. Teachers can enliven things from the inside instead of promoting or organizing from outside the group. When it goes well, students enjoy having the teacher with them, and for the teacher, participating is often more enjoyable than acting as a resource (Akintunde & Akuta, 2022a). This means that as a teacher who acts as a participant can create a lively atmosphere in the discussion rather than just as a source of information. Thus, when it succeeds students can enjoy their togetherness with the teacher, and for the teacher participation is an instant pleasure rather than a role as a source. Nevertheless, there remains the danger when a teacher acts as a participant, in which the teacher may be the master in the discussion. Therefore, the role of teachers as participant is a role that is included in the category difficult to do, meaning to avoid it he must have a strong ability and high sensitive (Baran, Correia, & Thompson, 2011).

Teacher as a Resource: In some cases, teachers do not need to apply the previously described roles. For example, when students are writing, or when they are involved in the presentation preparation that will be presented in the classroom or control them. In that case, the role of the teacher or when the teacher tries to control them, or try to encourage them, they will likely not welcome the teacher. In that case, the students need teacher as a source. Because of the possibility of students asking how to express something or ask the meaning of a word or phrase that they have not understood. Chances are they also want to know information from something in the middle of the discussion they are doing. For example, from where they will get information about something that has been assigned to them, from the book or from the web. In this case, teacher’s role as a source of information is needed. When a teacher acts as a source, he must have a sense of help as well as readiness in performing this role (Wright, 2017).

Teacher as a Tutor: When students are working on a longer project, such as writing or preparing for discussion or debate, this is where a teacher acts as a tutor, working with a private or a small group, pointing them one at a time. In such situations, teachers are merging their roles as prompter and resource, and acting as tutors. Being a tutor is a very difficult role to do in a class that has a large number of students because it indirectly must have an intimate relationship with students. However, when students are working in groups or in pairs, teacher can walk around and pause with some groups or partners and offer some guidance or direction in doing what he tells them to do. However, all the groups that are formed should feel teachers’ attention as tutors and otherwise the group that will be ignored will feel sad. Teachers have to play the role of a continuous tutor even though it is difficult because with a more specific context with students, they have the right opportunity to help and encourage so that the atmosphere in the class is awakened very well as a result.

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Teacher as an observer: In the process of carrying out observations, he should be careful, not be a nuisance by hanging all their questions by being close to them. This means that in practice, teachers should not interfere with what they are doing and should not give input to them. The teacher needs to bring a notebook and pen to assess students' performance either collectively or individually. Teachers here not only observe students to provide feedback. They should also pay close attention to the success of the teaching materials and the activities they deliberately carry on in the classroom (Baran, Correia, & Thompson, 2011).

Teacher as Performer: Having learned that different teachers' acting are also different, and that they have different behaviors. It depends on what they will do. Even though, the teacher tells the students which part to play, he should also be able to describe how they can play. Therefore, in an activity where students engage in a team game, it is appropriate that teacher acts full of energy, encouragingly, clearly, and fairly.

Example:

Activity	How the teacher should perform
Team game	Energetically, encouragingly, clearly, fairly
Role-play	Clearly, encouragingly, retiringly, supportively
Teacher and reading Aloud	Commandingly, dramatically, interestingly
Whole-Class Listening	Efficiently, clearly and supportively.

Teacher as a Teaching Aid: Regardless of the roles teachers adopt in the classroom and how these roles are applied, teachers are also aids. In particular, teachers are actually very useful, using clowns or body movements, as language models, and as a provider of understandable input. According to Brown (2012), the effective role of teachers in the classroom is as a facilitator, manager, director, conductor or teacher as a source. Baran, Correia, and Thompson, (2011) state that teachers' roles are: First, at the presentation stage the teacher acts as a model, by setting the situation and modeling the new structure that students must repeat over and over again. Secondly, teachers seemed to be like a conductor of an orchestra show that directs a musician in a harmonious sound. Third, teachers are required to be talented manipulators by using questions, orders, and other clues to provoke appropriate sentences from students (Scott, 2013).

How to Engage Students Actively in E-learning Environment?

The issue of making students to have a role actively in their learning and participate covers how to engage students into their learning progress. Encouraging students' learning without limit suggests putting students into the center of their learning. As the e-learning suggest a way of self-regulated activities. The active learning strategies may be very helpful because the students are responsible into their learning and they get involved into the teaching rather than just receiving simple lectures such as tutorials or presentations. Active learning strategies and how to put students in action are discussed below:

A student-centered approach is more likely a teaching methodology and instructional activities involving students in doing things and thinking about what they are doing. The learner-centered instruction attempts to engage students in activities that support knowledge constructions through media use, but which are not designed to control learning. The learners use media to investigate and to think. This type of learning activity leads to what can be described as active learning (Scott, 2013). Some of the strategies promoting active learning in language e-learning classroom are as follows:

1. Students are involved in more than listening.
2. Less emphasis is placed on transmitting information and more on developing students' skills.
3. Students are engaged in activities (e.g., reading, discussing, and writing).
4. Greater emphasis is placed on students' exploration of their own attitudes and values.

Also, the key principles of active learning suggested by Wright (2017) are as follows:

1. Purposive: the task is seen by the learner as relevant to his/her concerns;
2. Reflective: the learner reflects on the meaning of what is being learnt;
3. Negotiated: the teacher and learner negotiate the goals and methods of learning;
4. Critical: the learner appreciates different ways of interpreting learning;
5. Complex: the learning tasks reflect real life complexity;
6. Situation-driven: the learning tasks arise out of the needs of the situation;
7. Engaged: the learning activities reflect real life tasks.

Feedbacks

Feedbacks are one of the most valuable tools in the e-learning systems because they allow teachers monitoring and improving the performance of the students in several ways. In designing of information systems, feedback also has an important role where it helps teachers to understand whether the targeted receiver (or the learner) fully got the message (Hronova 2011). According to Brown (2012) the targeted recipient should receive the message and encode it fully in order to act in the communication. On the other hand, the sender also has to be sure the message has been sent correctly by observing the recipient's interpretation which also returned to the sender (Hronova, 2011). Also, in the communication, the message sender should act as the recipient as a result of this respond of the receiver; which is called feedback. Therefore, feedback has a potential for measuring or detecting the communication errors. Practically, those communication errors help us to provide guidance to the students if we can catch them. To find errors, the action or the objective must be known exactly. These errors help us to monitor whether there is a gap between what should be happening. On the other hand, it is a difficult process to find communication errors without getting any feedback from the students. Also, there is a great chance to learn from those communication failures because it helps learners to see their conditions and understanding about the concept. In real life situations, those failures should be used as an opportunity that goes through success. Fedyunina (2016) describes failures as opportunities with these words: "Usually, failure or success is almost entirely in the eye of the beholder... Failure is very often a misperception about the difference between what exists and goes unnoticed (such as growth and learning when we fall short of reaching a goal) and what is realized later (longer term success)". Most of the times students can make so many mistakes when they are new to the concepts and trying to discover that concept by themselves. In that case, the best thing that can be done is to show them quickly what the mistakes are and let them to have enough time and guidance to improve their performance in those parts that they had problems. In general, if a teacher gives students a space to work on their ideas, the chance to experience their mistakes teachers should give them the chance to fail. There are several learning activities that can be used that let the students to work on their ideas and have a chance of failure. In those activities the main roles of the teachers are to monitor students, catch their mistakes, let them know their mistakes and give them guidance to correct their mistakes. Discussions boards with brain storming sessions, cooperative learning, worked examples, class projects -research and in class activities in active learning are the cases where the instructor can provide a good way to let their students to have some mistakes freely and provide guidance to improve them using performance related feedbacks. In those cases, the feedback can be given immediately before waiting until the figuring that the students have some problems or they don't get the ideas in the lesson. Also, to have those immediate feedbacks, the teachers should monitor students' activity by observing or asking some questions on issues that demand clarifications.

In discussion forms, students can generate ideas freely and talk about those ideas. These discussions should start with a brain storming session where all the students can present their ideas freely. Then, they can discuss those ideas and evaluate each other's ideas. In that case, they can have further discovery in certain ideas also. The teacher also can lead those discussions to make student to generate a final goal or idea about the topic and also guide them to gain further understanding about the ideas. Similarly, in discussions, the students can also have some activities in groups where they provide feedback for one another about their work. The teacher can also monitor the groups' works by monitoring their activities regularly. If the teacher wants s/he can also have an inference to those groups' activities to correct something and give feedback and guidance (Trinder, 2016).

Active learning in the class is also a good way to provide students to engage their own learning where teacher can also have performance related feedback such as class projects and research. In active learning students are required to take action in the class by actively participating. For example, they can participate in lectures by taking notes, posing questions, involving role playing or games. In those performances the teacher or the learning system can monitor the activities and can provide feedback. Other activities where students can have feedbacks are tests, inquiry, guided inquiry and scaffolding. In those activities, however the teacher cannot monitor the whole ongoing progress to give immediate constructive feedbacks. They can just give formative feedbacks according to end results of the students. For example, in mastery learning tests provide some results for students to have a corrective instruction and give them chance to retest; but it is so hard to detect the exact nature of the problem such as a misunderstanding of a student in a solution part of the problem which leads to wrong results in the test (Scott, 2013).

Also, it is sometimes difficult to find good feedbacks. Especially, when the students develop a certain skill and developed it overtime. Sometimes teachers think that the learners are good enough to find their own mistakes; if they get experienced in their learning. So, in that case, to have a good help seeking and self-monitoring ability will be very helpful to those students. Before seeking any help, the learners should be aware they need help because they have a problem in their

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performances. According to Baran, Correia, and Thompson (2011) to detect a mistake or a problem, the learner has to have an understanding of the standard, compare his current level of performance according to these standards, and plan - get correct actions to fill the gap. This type of a learning also considered as a self-regulated leaning where students compare their performance against a standard (Izadinia 2015). According to the several studies frequent self-evaluation produced positive results regardless of the type of goal adopted (Izadinia 2015).

Usage of e- learning systems can be very useful for those self-regulated students. In such a learning environment it is possible to have some feedback and support students learning process. In e- learning environment, self-regulated learners also can monitor their performance within, observing their actions in the system also following the feedbacks provided by the system which are called The Intelligent Tutoring System, Computer Assisted Instruction, Computer Based Instruction, Web Based System etcetera. In such an e-learning environment, students can get immediate feedbacks according to their performance within several computers managed activities such as drill /practice, problem solving, games, simulations, tutorials and online lectures. In those activities students can engage several cooperative learning opportunities to have peer feedback such as in online discussions with instant messaging or forums, online games, Wikis and online simulations. Also, the computers can give the opportunity to follow classical class activities in a local network or a web environment where a feedback mechanism can be provided by the teacher, by the system itself or mixed. These activities are virtual classes, online collaborative projects and e-portfolios.

Conclusion

E-learning has undergone great development in recent years and it is now considered to be a serious teaching method used in a number of educational institutions. In the current technology-driven environment, demand is high for new tools and learner-centered learning approaches. The utilization of computers will influence the way how teachers teach and students learn, and the teachers should make use of the Internet in ways that match the pedagogical goals.

Recommendations

Teachers have the least involvement in affective aspects of e-learning, it is then necessary to gear teacher training in the direction of facilitating positive instructor-learner relationships and building a helpful virtual classroom atmosphere. To fulfill this goal, teachers need new skills that are obviously different from those in traditional instruction. Also, researchers and practitioners need to work more on how technology could be made full use of in order to facilitate and foster more successful communication in e-learning classroom. Greater efforts are needed to supervise, monitor and track students' learning on e-learning in different ways. This is probably much more crucial than in face-to-face learning contexts.

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Effective Teaching and Learning of Economics at Secondary School Level in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State: Issues and Prospects

***Ibrahim, Mansur¹**

Email: miruwandoruwa@fugusau.edu.ng

Tel: 07038929443

Kanoma, Umar Manir¹

Email: umarkanomam@yahoo.com

Tel: 07068436428

Muhammad, Isah Muhti¹

Email: muhammadisahmuhti@gmail.com

Tel: 07031635767.

Department of Science Education, Federal University, Gusau

Abstract

One of the foundational subjects in secondary education is economics education. In order to solve personal and societal issues, the teaching and learning of economics becomes essential to any nation that aspires to great in its economic base. The paper x-rays the issues and prospects of teaching economics in Zamfara state public secondary schools, Researchers used secondary data for this being a qualitative type research. Print and online publications were used to gather the secondary data which was further translated using reviewed related literatures. The issues face in effective teaching and learning of economics in Gusau educational zone, Zamfara state were identified as; insecurity, large class size, poor supervision, inadequate infrastructure, a lack of an active association for economics teachers, inadequate teaching and learning materials, low motivation of staff and students, negative attitudes of students towards the studying economics. The following prospects were identified to address these issues: increasing funding for the economics program, recruiting qualified economics teachers, providing instructional materials, providing infrastructure facilities for both economics teachers and students, establishment of effective program and policies for economics teachers' capacity development. The following suggestion were identified: Government should provide adequate security to protect the secondary schools in Gusau local government area and the state in general, the state government should employ more professional Economics teachers, to provide more infrastructural facilities for both Economics teachers and students, to ensure effective motivation of Economics teachers i.e. increasing their salary, economics teachers should form Economics Teachers' association, there should be effective supervision of the Economics teachers in all the public secondary schools across the state.

Keywords: Economics, teachers, teaching and learning, Secondary school, students.

Introduction

Education is a fundamental issue in any given society that is a key to social, economic, and political stability. Education is a crucial part of economic progress. Eyibe (2016) asserts that education is a cultural process. "Education has been adjudged an instrument for societal development and advancement of human knowledge for harmonious relationship and interactions with his environment," according to Onebunne, J. et al. (2020, 85). It is both a developmental and a cultural process. It is a cultural process since it involves the transmission and modification of cultural norms among students and adults who are exposed to education. The second reason it is a behavioral process is that it involves both adults and schoolchildren who are gaining from education. Thirdly, the progression from a lower to a greater degree of educational achievement makes it a developmental process. Therefore, it is a method for fostering an individual's growth so that he can function effectively and efficiently in the society of today and make positive contributions to its development. Education can also be thought of as a systematic process for an individual's personal and societal growth on all levels—physically, mentally, spiritually, and socially. The unemployment problems facing the country can be addressed through equipping the young people with skills that can lead to self-employment, the curriculum therefore should equip the learners with skills and more so entrepreneurial skills and this therefore indicate the importance of economic education in the school curriculum.

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Instructional materials and teaching equipment hinder students' performance in economics in Zamfara state. Therefore, Economics teachers in the state should make use of appropriate teaching aid in teaching economics. They should also teach students in a well conducive environment for effective learning and performance. With teaching equipment's students begin to develop the necessary skills in reasoning, attitudinal and practical skills to solve practical problems. Moreover, teachers should make them available while teaching economics to students. Teachers and students should learn how to motivate themselves. Teachers should motivate their students since motivation refers to the process by which behavior is mobilized and sustained in the interest of meeting individual needs in achieving organizational objectives. Teachers should use various motivation strategies like reinforcement, feedback and so on, various teaching methodology in teaching economics for effective performance. A motivated student cannot forget what is being taught in the classroom because it was meaningful and clear to him. Therefore, students need to be motivated in the classroom. Moreover, teachers and students should show positive interest in the teaching and learning of economics to enhance effective performance in the subject.

After graduating from a higher education institution, a person becomes certified as an Economics teacher if they have acquired the necessary skills, knowledge, and abilities to teach economics at educational institutions. Degree Finders (2020) defines an economics instructor as someone who disseminates knowledge about money, business, macroeconomics, microeconomics, technology, and personal finance. Lesson plans are developed, lectures are given, exams are given, student work is evaluated, and assistance is given to students as required. Either public or private secondary schools, colleges, or universities regularly employ economics teachers. The ability to teach in several social studies topics is a requirement in many schools for economics teachers. The person must register with the Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) in order to be accepted as a qualified Economics instructor in Nigeria. The second requirement is that the person read. B.sc (ed) According to Asikhai (2010), secondary education is meant to be the cornerstone and foundation for obtaining higher knowledge in university institutions. It is both an investment and a tool that enables a nation to progress economically, socially, politically, technologically, scientifically, and culturally more quickly. The fact that today's secondary schools fall short of the expectations placed on them by their performance in external tests is regrettable. There have been public outcries over the persistently poor performance of secondary school students in public examinations. Nwokocho and Amadike (2015), submitted that one indicator for testing the educational process of a nation is the academic performance of students in schools. The performance of students in Economics for some years now have been reported by different researchers and even national dailies as below average in public examinations, Punch newspaper (September 27, 2008). Gbadamosi, and Jegede, (2015) also observed that many students largely record poor performance in the subject. For instance, the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) results in Economics between 2000 and 2012 revealed that, less than 50% of the students that sat for the examination obtained the required credit pass except 2006 and 2012. Udekaigbo, Onionwu and Mbionwu (2009) observed that the teaching and learning of Economics programme in majorities of Nigerian Public Secondary Schools have been seriously frustrated in recent time.

This issue is ascribed to the difficulty of converting some economic notions and theories into visual, usable realities. The usage of instructional resources is allegedly lacking by teachers, and as a result, children are performing poorly academically, particularly on external exams. The teachers of economics have been blamed for the students' dismal performance on external tests. According to research, many Economics teachers in Nigeria's public secondary schools are struggling with a variety of issues that are affecting how well they function at their particular schools. The purpose of this study is to analyze the issues faced by Economics teachers and students in the public secondary schools in gusau local government area of Zamfara State.

Economics as a Secondary School Subject in Zamfara State.

Nigerian students took economics for the first time in 1967 as a topic in the West African School Certificate Exam. Since earning a school certificate required two years of study, economics may have been included to the secondary school curriculum in Nigeria significantly later than the majority of other secondary school subjects—in 1966—than most others. However, before becoming a secondary school subject, economics was a subject that private applicants may take in the General Certificate Examination. The fundamental issues with modern society's economy were acknowledged. Since 1967, when the West African School Certificate Examination included economics as a subject of study, both the number of institutions that offer it and the number of test-takers has grown dramatically. An illustration, In Nigeria, the West African School Certificate Examination included economics for the first time in 1967. Since obtaining a diploma For instance, it was 0.07% of the total number of applicants who took the exam in 1967, climbed to 12.56% in 1969, 17.16% in 1970, and reached 76.95% by 1976, exactly 10 years after it began (Noun, 2006). According to Gbemisola (2016), sustained research and significant innovations

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lead to ongoing changes in the Nigerian educational system. The 6-3-3-4 curriculum's multipurpose curriculum (NERC) is designed to meet a student's demands on an intellectual, social, material, and spiritual level, therefore catering to the "whole man" notion; that is, to provide for the intellectual, social, material and spiritual needs of a student through its multi-purpose curriculum (NERC, 2000; FME, 1989). With this mind, the secondary school curriculum is divided into three parts namely: (i) Core subjects or vacation subjects (ii) pre-vocational subjects and (iii) Elective subjects or non-vocational subjects. The core subjects such as Mathematics, English language, one Nigeria language among: Yoruba, Hausa and others like Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Agricultural Science, and Economics are basic intended to give students opportunity to offer Arts or Science subjects in higher education of learning in zamfara state and beyond.

The objectives of teaching Economics at senior secondary school:

1. **Allocation of resources:** To develop among students of zamfara state a favorable attitude towards conservation and wise use of the natural and available resources, and avoid misuse of the resources and wastage.
2. **Profit maximization:** To teach zamfara state students on how individual and corporate business owners can increase their profit margin using Economics principles to guide their business.
3. **Provision of basic tools:** To familiarize students in the state with the basic terminologies and elementary ideas of economics and acquire skills in interpreting simple statistical tools for analyzing economic issues and individuals in the state and government in general.
4. **Solutions to Economic problems:** To enable students to acquire knowledge for the practical solution of the economic problems of the society, such as zamfara state, Nigeria, developing countries and the world at large.
5. **Participation in government:** To foster and urge among students of zamfara state for effective participation in the task of economic reconstruction for the development of the state and country in at large.
6. **Consumption pattern:** To exposes the students to the various patterns of consuming commodities available in different localities in zamfara state.

Issues on teaching and learning of Economics in Zamfara state Public Secondary School

The successful teaching of Economics in Nigeria's public secondary schools is hampered by a number of issues. Teaching huge classes is one of these issues, along with bad staff development programs, poor supervision, inadequate infrastructure, a lack of an association for economics teachers, poor instructional materials, low motivation, and insecurity.

Teaching and learning of Economics in the face of Insecurity in Zamfara State

The menace of insecurity, armed banditry, human displacement and cattle rustling had virtually posed serious security challenges to Zamfara state and Nigeria at large. This, made scholars (Egwu, 2015 and Momale, 2015) to view it as criminal enterprises with the consequence for socio- economic, political, cultural and psychological spheres of (affected) society. As such made both teachers and students to be absent from schools and making their lives difficult. Insecurity is the first issue that zamfara state government needs to tackle in public secondary schools. Zamfara State has been struggling with insecurity issues since 2015. The militants and bandits have assaulted public secondary schools. About 10 public secondary schools were attacked between December 2020 and June 2021; during these attacks, instructors and students were slain, while some were taken hostage by the bandits for ulterior motives. Numerous teachers have died. The performance of teachers, particularly economists, is being hampered by these insecurity issues. The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) claims that since the insurgency began in Nigeria's northeast in 2009, Boko Haram has killed 2,300 instructors there, according to the Cable (2019).The first issue is security.

Inadequate Instructional Materials in Public secondary schools

Inadequate Economics instructional materials is another major problem facing the Economics teachers in majorities of the public secondary schools in Zamfara state. Things that help teaching and learning process to be more effective and efficient. Richardson, R. (2010), submitted that that economic teaching need concrete objects when teaching, for example if a topic like money is to be taught, the teacher needs to show the students the currency, both notes and coins and their demonstration, in order to retain the topic in their memory. Furthermore, a set goal may not be reached by the teacher if he fails to choose and correctly use appropriate resources in teaching, because there are some students who learn better when they see and touch and others learn more when they combine all the senses of learning, sight, touch, and even tasting and smelling. Mark, (2017) observed that despite the fact that instructional materials are essential tools that can make learning practical and

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knowledgeable, they are not readily available in the state secondary schools leading to low level in academic performance of learners in government examination.

Inadequate economics textbooks in public secondary school libraries

Unprofessionally published text books: Akpochato (2015) rightly of pointed out that non- availability of required economics text books, journals and magazine hamper the effective teaching and learning of economics at the secondary and tertiary level of education in Nigeria. He reiterated that text books that would aid effective discussion of economics concept are not in appreciable quantity. Teachers in economics are challenged to write and publish current materials to stem the gross inadequate of material in the area.

Low Motivation of teachers and students

Economics teachers are poorly motivated. The allowances and treatment given teachers in other subjects like mathematics, English language and sciences subject teachers are not given to the Economics teachers. Gbemisola (2016) observed in his study that on the part of Economics teachers' motivation, that 88.9% of the respondent agreed with the Economics teachers' lack of motivation. Motivation in terms of provision of a conducive staff room or office, teaching aids, skill acquisition and re- training on the; part of government and school authority have hindered their performance, which also indirectly affects the teaching and learning of economics in the zamfara state public schools.

Lack of adequately qualified Economics Teachers Association

Lack of Economics Teachers' Association is another problem facing the Economics teachers in Zamfara state Secondary schools. There is no any formal association in charge of professional development for Economics teachers even though the few once coming up are not strong enough to meet up the various challenges facing the Economics teachers. Noun (2015) submitted that all secondary school subjects which are regarded as established and important have associations for example; there are associations for subjects like English language, History, Geography and Sciences. Even the teachers of French in Nigeria are known to have only a few secondary school students yet they have an association.

Poor supervision

Many economics teachers are facing the problems of effective supervision due to shortage of professional Economics supervisors in the various Ministries and Agencies of government saddled with the responsibilities of supervising Economics instruction in the secondary schools are inadequate. Many Economics teachers are not constantly been supervised and even when supervised, non -economics supervisors are used for the supervision which is not encouraging due to different in teaching methodologies and approaches

Negative Attitudes of Students towards the Studying Economics

Economics teachers are also facing the problem of attracting students to study Economics in their various schools now. Economics is an elective programme in the Nigerian secondary schools. Students have many options. This make the students to avoid Economics even when chosen demonstrates some negative attitudes that is not encouraging the Economics teachers. Many students see Economics as voluminous and bore to read and study. They have negative mentality about the concept of the subject

Prospects in effective teaching and learning of economics in Zamfara state public secondary schools

1. The state government should collaborate with the federal government to provide adequate security to allow students go to school and study with peace.
2. The state government should provide more infrastructural facilities in all the Zamfara state public secondary schools.
3. It is important for the state ministry of education to encourage both students and teachers to study and teach economics by providing them with resources like high-quality textbooks and other study aids for the local government of Gusau and the state as a whole.
4. The state and federal governments should guarantee enough salary for teachers, fast and consistent payment of salaries, advancement, and better working conditions. The Zamfara state government ought to make sure that the state teachers are at least content with their pay, the minimum wage, and other perks related to their employment as instructors. Giving teachers scholarships to help them learn more about the subject would also produce positive results and should be done.

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5. Economics teachers in the state should form an association where issues concerning Economics programme can be discussed and ways of developing the programme suggested.
6. State ministry of Education should make sure that the economics education programme be supervised by the respective institutions in charge of Economics supervision.

Conclusion

Economics teachers are professionals employed to teach economics in Nigerian public Secondary Schools. It has been discovered that many economics are facing with challenges while implementing the economics programme their various schools. The paper identified teaching of large classes, poor supervision, inadequate infrastructural facilities, lack of Economics Teachers' Association, inadequate instructional materials, poor motivation and insecurity were identified as problems facing Economics teachers teaching in Zamfara state public secondary schools. In order to address these problems, the authors suggested that government should increase in the funding of Economics programme, employ more professional Economics teachers, provide more infrastructural facilities for both Economics teachers and students, motivate the Economics teachers, Economics teachers should form Economics Teachers' Association and effective supervision of the Economics teachers should be ensured in all public secondary school across the state.

Recommendations

1. Government should provide adequate security to protect the secondary schools in Gusau local government area and the state in general.
2. The state government should employ more professional Economics teachers.
3. To provide more Economics instructional materials for effective teaching and learning in the state.
4. To provide more infrastructural facilities for both Economics teachers and students.
5. To ensure effective motivation of Economics teachers i.e. increasing their salary.
6. Economics teachers should form Economics Teachers' Association.
7. There should be effective supervision of the Economics teachers in all the public secondary schools across the state.

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Effects of Jig-Saw (III) Cooperative Learning strategy on Achievement and Retention in Algebra among Senior Secondary School Students in Zaria

Bello, Abdullahi

Email: abdullahibello@fugsau.edu.ng

Tel: 08036631032

Department of Science Education, Federal University Gusau

Abstract

This study investigated the effects of Enrich Jig-saw (III) Cooperative Strategy on achievement and retention in Algebra among Secondary School Students in Zaria, Kaduna State. The population of the study consists of 1,061 (644 Males and 471 Females) Senior Secondary class II (SSII) Students in government secondary schools during the 2020/2021 academic session in Zaria, Kaduna State. A sample of 70 students (59 males and 11 females) were randomly selected using two intact classes. Quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pretest, post -test and post post-test design was employed. The two groups were pretested to determine their equivalence; the experimental group was exposed to Algebra using Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Strategy while the control group were taught same concept using lecture method. An Algebra Performance Test (APT) was used to collect data with reliability co-efficient of 0.78 achieved using Cronbach alpha reliability test. The null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 significant level using t-test inferential statistics. The results showed that the experimental group exposed to Enrich Jig-saw (III) Cooperative Learning Strategy achieved significantly higher results and retained better when taught the same concepts than their counterparts exposed to lecture method. It was recommended that Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Learning Strategy should be employed as a teaching strategy by Mathematics teachers in teaching Algebra in senior secondary schools in Zaria and Kaduna Sate as a whole.

Keyword: Jigsaw III Cooperative Learning Strategy, Algebra, Achievement, Retention.

Introduction

Mathematics in general is linked with the development of any nation in the world, mathematics as a discipline opens and shuts doors for men and women than any other content area we have got. Whether it is in science, engineering, or technology, it is tremendously important that a person be well armed with mathematics if they are to have options in their lives (Thompson,2003). Mathematics is intimately involved in every moment of everyone's life. Right from human existence on this earth, it has been a faithful companion. The role played by mathematics in the day-to-day activities of human endeavors is suggestive of the fact that mathematics is needed by all, not only for scientific and technological development, but for all forms of development. Mathematics is one of the core subjects to be offered to all students up to the tertiary levels of education (Salau, 2005). This compulsory nature of mathematics carries with it the assumption that the knowledge of the subject is essential for all members of society.

A variety of teaching strategies have been advocated for use in science and mathematics classrooms ranging from teacher-centered approach to more students-centered ones. One of such methods according to Oloruko-oba, (2001) is cooperative learning. Cooperative learning is a strategy in which students create, analyze, and apply concepts. Here, students learn lifelong concepts that will be useful both inside and outside the school. They work as a team, combining their knowledge and social skills. Students are often placed in heterogeneous groups and asked to accomplish a common goal. Each team member is assigned part of the content to be learnt and is not only responsible for their learning, but the other group members' learning as well. Students work until each group member successfully understands all concepts and then the assignment is completed (Timayi, Bolaji, & Kajuru, 2015). There are several models of Cooperative Learning Strategies one of which is Jig-saw Cooperative Learning model.

Jigsaw is a cooperative learning strategy that was developed by Elliot Aronson and his colleagues in 1978. The jigsaw technique was created with the goals of reducing conflict, enhancing positive educational outcomes and to help students realize they are essential components of a whole and encourages cooperation in a learning environment. There are currently six types of Jigsaw cooperative learning strategies available for teachers to use in the classroom. Algebra is that branch of mathematics that deals with the study of rules of operations and things, which can be constructed from them including terms, polynomials, equations and algebraic structure (Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia 2010). Hence, good skills and competencies in Algebra is a great asset to any secondary school student because it is a tool for developing critical and logical thinking that can facilitate

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the learning of other branches of mathematics and even other science subjects. Oluremi and Ajao (2012) reported that secondary school students tend to fear and hate Algebraic concepts to the extent that they avoid Algebraic questions in both internal and external examinations. This consequently affects students' academic achievement in mathematics negatively.

Academic achievement refers to student's success in meeting short- or long-term goals in education. Sani (2007) defines academic achievement as an accomplishment or proficiency of performance in each skill or body of knowledge. Adediwura and Tayo (2007), viewed academic performance as the knowledge attained or skills developed in school subject designed by test and examination scores, or marks assigned by the subject teachers. According to Nwagbo (2013), academic achievement can be defined as performance of students in schools. Academic achievement could be getting a high grade or a high-Grade Point Average (GPA).

Retention is the act of keeping something in one's memory or the ability to remember or recollect a body of knowledge after passing through instruction. In other words, retention refers to what is learned minus what has been forgotten (Mang and Mankilik, 2001). Retention is the ability of a learner to recall, remember and recollect a body of Knowledge after passing through instruction. For students' retention, Omar, (2012) observed that students' experience is a significant factor in retention and that the strategies of improving retention rate can be adopted by the teacher.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate effects of Enrich Jig-saw (III) Cooperative Strategy on achievement and retention in Algebra among senior secondary schools in Zaria, Kaduna State. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine the effects of Enrich Jig-saw (III) Cooperative Learning Strategy (EJ3CLS) on Students' Academic Achievement in Algebra in Senior Secondary Schools.
2. Determine the retention ability of students taught Algebra using EJ3CLS with those taught using Lecture Method.

Research Questions

The study sought answers to the following research questions.

1. Is there any difference in mean achievement scores of Senior Secondary School students taught Algebra using Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Strategy and those taught using Lecture Method?
2. Is there any difference in retention ability of students taught Algebra using EJ3CLS and those taught using Lecture Method?

Null hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of students taught Algebra using EJ3CLS and those taught using Lecture Method.
2. There is no significant difference between mean retention ability of students taught Algebra using EJ3CLS and those taught using Lecture Method.

Methodology

The design for this study is a quasi-experimental research design. The experimental group (EG) was exposed Algebra concepts using EJ3CLS while control group (CG) was exposed to Algebra concepts using lecture method. The sample selected was pre-tested to ensure that the two groups are not significantly different. A post- test was administered to determine the difference in students' academic achievement among the groups. A post-post-test was equally administered to both experimental and control group to ascertain difference in students' retention ability in Algebraic concepts. The population of this study comprised of all government secondary schools' senior class (SS II) students offering mathematics in Zaria, Kaduna Sate. There are eleven government secondary schools in Zaria metropolis with a total of 1061 SS II students. 644 students were males while 417 students were females. Two schools were randomly selected, that is G.S.S. Jama'a and G.S.S. Kaura and used as sample with an enrolment of 70 students were subjected to pretest as the sample of the study. The two sample schools were assigned as experimental group consisting of 36 students and the other school as control group (CG) having 34 students. In both experimental and control groups, 59 students were male, and 11 students were female. An instrument called Algebra Performance Test (APT) was used to collect data. The APT was constructed by the researcher. It was made up of 30 multiple choice items on algebra. Concept. The instrument was used for both posttest and post-posttest. The APT was validated by Senior Lecturers in Science Education Department Federal University, Gusau. This was to determine the appropriateness of the test item, language used and content validity. The APT was pilot tested at GSS Gyalesu. The results were used to determine the reliability co-efficient which was found to be 0.78 using Cronbach alpha reliability test.

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Results

Research Question 1

Is there any difference in mean achievement scores of Senior Secondary School students taught Algebra using Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Strategy and those taught using Lecture Method?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of mean scores of pre-tests and post-test scores

Group	N	Mean	STD	Mean Diff.
Pre- Test	36	67.9	8.63	24.7
Post-Test	34	43.2	3.95	

Source: field work (2023)

Table 1 above showed that there is difference in the mean scores of pre-test and post-test scores of students taught algebra using Enrich Jigsaw (III) cooperative strategy. From the table, pre-test group has a mean score of 67.9 with standard deviation of 8.63 as against post-test group with a mean score of 43.2 and standard deviation of 3.95

Research Question 2

Is there any difference in retention ability of students taught Algebra using Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative strategy and those taught using Lecture Method?

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of mean scores of post-tests and post post-test scores

Group	N	Mean	STD	Mean Diff.
Post-Test	36	78.5	7.93	32.7
Post Post-Test	34	45.8	3.43	

Source: field work (2023)

Table 2 above showed that there is difference in retention ability of students taught algebra using Enrich Jigsaw (III) cooperative strategy. From the table, post-test scores have a mean score of 78.5 with a standard deviation of 7.93 against post post-test scores with a mean score of 45.8 and standard deviation of 3.43

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of students taught Algebra using Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Strategy and those taught using Lecture Method.

Table 3: t-test Analysis of mean Scores of Experimental and Control Group

Group	N	Post-test scores	SD	SE	t-cal	t-crit	Df	p-value
Experimental	34	50.76	17.70	3.04	4.59	2.01	68	0.001
Control	36	46.17	17.22	2.87				

Source: field work (2023)

From Table 3, the p-value of 0.001 is less than the critical p-value of 0.05 with df = 68. This means that there is a significant difference between mean scores of experimental group and control group in favor of the experimental group. Thus, hypothesis one is rejected. This implies that the experimental group taught Algebra concepts using Enriched Jig-saw Cooperative Strategy performed significantly higher than those exposed to lecture teaching method.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significance difference in mean retention ability of students taught Algebra using EJ3CLS and those taught using Lecture Method.

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Table 4: t-test Analysis of Post-Posttest Mean Scores of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Post Post-test	SD	SE	t-cal	t-crit	Df	p-value
Exp.	34	51.06	20.91	3.59	4.75	2.01	68	0.001
Control	36	46.31	17.84	2.89				

Source: field work (2023)

From Table 4, p – value of 0.001 less is than the critical P -value of 0.05 with $df = 68$. This means that there is a significant difference between the post post-test means score of the experimental and control groups in favor of the experimental group. Thus, hypothesis two is rejected. This implies that the experimental group taught Algebra concepts using Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Learning Strategy retained the learned concepts better than the control group taught same concepts using lecture method. So, the null hypothesis which says there is no significant difference is therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The results obtained from the analysis of data, in Table 3 shows that students in the experimental group (EG) taught Algebra using Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Learning Strategy (EJ3CLS) achieved significantly higher than their counterparts in the control group (CG) taught same concepts using lecture method. The significant difference in the academic achievement in favor of the experimental group suggests a greater strength and effectiveness of EJ3CLS over the lecture method. This finding is in conformity with those of Naomi (2013), & Timay, etal (2015) which showed that Enrich Jigsaw Cooperative Learning Strategy is superior and more effective in improving students’ academic performance than the traditional lecture method.

The post-post test results Table 4 showed that the experimental group exposed to Algebra concepts using EJ3CLS had significantly higher retentive ability than those exposed to lecture method. Therefore, the statistically significant difference between the two mean scores suggests that the EJ3CLS is more effective in enhancing students’ retention ability. The results agrees with the earlier findings of Jansoon; Somsook and Coll, (2008); Zakari & Iksan, (2007) and Timayi, etal (2015) each of them reported that Jigsaw Cooperative Learning Strategy on the academic achievement and retention of student in science and Mathematics and revealed that EJ3CLS enhances the retention ability of students.

Conclusion

This study confirmed the superiority of Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Learning Strategy (EJ3CLS) over the lecture method in the teaching of Algebra. Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative strategy (EJ3CLS) improves achievement and retention during teaching and learning of algebra concept.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Kaduna State Ministry of Education Science and Technology should organize training programs for mathematics teachers in a form of seminars, workshops, and conferences on how to effectively use Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Learning Strategy in the teaching of Algebra concepts in Senior Secondary Schools.
2. Algebra should be given more teaching time by mathematics teachers because of its abstract nature for students to understand its concepts better.

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Efficacy of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Skills on Competency Level among Secondary School Computer Teachers in Zamfara State

Tafa, Taofik O.¹

Email: taofiktafa@gmail.com

Tel: +2348036044015

Adeyemo, Sarafa O.¹

Email: adeyemoso2003@yahoo.com

Tel: +2348036351533

Abubakar, Barikisu O.²

Email: omenekeba@gmail.com

Tel: +2348051997650

Isah, Khadijat O.²

Email: ozavisa338@gmail.com

¹Department of Computer Science, Federal College of Education (Technical) Gusau

²Department of Computer Science, Federal College of Education Okene

Abstract

This study examined efficacy of ICT skills on competency levels of computer teachers in Zamfara state. The study is descriptive research of a survey type. A structured questionnaire tagged “ICT needs and competence level among secondary school computer teachers in Zamfara State” was used to generate data for the study. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha and the Alpha value was found to be 0.73. Draft questionnaire was presented to experts and specialists in ICT for face validation. The target population for the study was computer studies teachers in Zamfara State during the 2021/2022 academic session. A sample size of fifty (29 males and 21 females) computer studies teachers were randomly selected from public and private schools in Zamfara state, representing about 10% of the entire computer teachers in the state. The research questions were analyzed using frequency count and percentage and hypotheses tested using t-test statistical and analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that computer studies teachers in Zamfara state are aware they need to be ICT literate to effectively teach their computer studies. Findings also revealed that the teachers have higher competence level in the use of ICT for instructional purposes. The study therefore concluded that the teachers who are the final instrument in curriculum implementations have the desired competency in the utilization of ICT for instructional purposes. Therefore, appropriate integration of ICT in education, especially at the lower level, should not be neglected so as to bring about effective and efficient educational system. Alternative power supply should also be made available for ICT facilities in schools.

Keyword: Competency, computer studies, ICT, teacher

Introduction

Globalization and the incorporation of information and communication technology (ICT) in all spheres of life have created a society which is motivated by knowledge and driven by technology. In recognition of the potentials of ICT, Zurich (2013) cited in Hilty and Aebischer (2015) observed that ICT made teachers’ work more sustainable: saving energy and materials resources by creating more value from less physical input, increasing quality of life forever more people without compromising the future generation ability to meet their needs. ICT is the range of technologies that are applied in the process of collecting, storing, editing, retrieving, and transfer of information in various forms (Olakulehin, 2007 as cited in Danner & Pessu, 2013). The potentials and role of ICT as a tool for contributing to development is limitless and well established. Bolaji and Adeoye (2022) referred to ICT as empowering tool that encourages and stimulates changes and development in 21st century. ICT is used within the school setting as tool for school administration and management, presentation of classroom work, teaching and learning interesting tasks, teaching and learning intellectual, thinking and problem-solving skills, stimulating

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creativity and resourcefulness, communication tools by teachers and students. ICT is therefore unavoidable tool in all human endeavors, especially in the area of education (Bolaji & Jimoh, 2023).

The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2013) stated that ICT can contribute to universal access to education, equity in education, the delivery of quality learning and teaching, teachers' professional development, efficient management, governance and administration. Mustapha and Oladimeji (2021) asserted that the purposes of teaching in education process is considered vital especially when we consider teaching and learning process as the acquisition of knowledge and skills by individuals to enable him become worthwhile member of the society. While Jegede (2008) cited in Oyeronke and Fagbohun (2013) opined that ICT is now recognized as an crucial ingredient for producing 21st century learning environment, Lau and Sim (2008) cited in Oyeronke and Fagbohun (2013) reported that despite the benefits of the use of ICT for educational purpose, studies showed that in many cases, the learning potential of ICT is deprived as many teachers are still not fully ICT literate. Modern developments in innovative technologies have provided new possibilities to teaching professions, but at the same time have placed more demands on teachers to learn how to use these new technologies in their teaching (Sayfullayeya et al., 2021).

Competency is the capability to apply or use a set of related knowledge, skills, and abilities required to successfully perform critical work functions or tasks in a defined work setting. Competency serve as the basis for skill standards that specify the level of knowledge, skills, and abilities required for success in the workplace as well as potential measurement criteria for assessing competency attainment (Wagenaar, 2014). Competency is a set of attributes covering knowledge, skills and attitudes for enabling one to effectively perform the activities of a given occupation or function to the standards expected in employment (Adeoluwa & Ogunmodede, 2018). Balogun and Yusuf (2019) asserted that teachers' competence is of concern when new subjects or media are integrated into the school system. This is because teachers' capability and competence will form the root of their ability to implement the innovation in schools. The idea of competence with regard to the use of ICT in education is broader than the technical skills needed to use ICT. The type of ICT competence needed by teachers is a collection of knowledge, skills and attitudes that are inseparably bound up with the framework and pedagogy. Competency ethics, as opined by UNESCO (2013) are often closely tied to local ethics for students, so that expected student outcome in a particular field of study implies a set of competencies with ICT that their teachers should possess, and as such needs to be entrenched in teacher practices. Thus, this study examines efficacy of ICT skills on competency levels of computer teachers in Zamfara state.

Despite the strength of the rapid spread of technology around the world in recent time, there is a decline in the academic performance in computer studies in the country. This poor performance has been recorded for some years by the examining bodies of Junior Secondary Certificate Examination (JSCCE), school promotion examinations and the qualifying examinations conducted by the State Ministry of Education. This poor performance has been ascribed to non-availability of ICT resources and teachers' lack of the necessary digital competence to utilize ICT in instruction delivery (Olelewe & Okwor, 2017). It has also been recorded in the past according to Collins and Halverson (2018), that pupils acquire skills in computer technology which makes them fit into the society properly and the reverse is now the case as students on completion of the course cannot carry out simple daily maintenance on technological appliances. Several complains have been attributed to this among which is schools' lack of organization of workshops for teachers on the utilization of ICT in instructional delivery of content, teachers' enrolling for professional development programmes in which their employers gave no approval resulting to low input as expected and parents' little or no effort to support or address the utilization of ICTs in instructions during Parents Teachers Association (PTA) meeting. Hence, the essence of the study is to examine ICT needs and competence level of Computer Studies teachers in Zamfara State.

Objectives of the study

The purpose of this study is to find out efficacy of ICT skills on competency levels of computer teachers in Zamfara state. Specifically, the study:

4. ascertain the needed ICT skills required of computer studies teachers for effective teaching enhancement in Zamfara state.
5. determine the level of ICT use by computer studies teachers in Zamfara state.
6. examine the level of ICT competence of computer studies teachers in Zamfara state.
7. determine the challenges of using ICT to teach computer studies in Zamfara state.

Research Questions

3. What are the needed ICT skills required of computer studies teachers in Zamfara state?
4. What is the level of ICT utilization by computer studies teachers in Zamfara state?
5. What is the level of competence of computer studies teachers in the use of ICT in Zamfara state?

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6. What are the challenges of using ICT in teaching computer studies in Zamfara state?

Hypotheses

Based on the research questions, the following hypotheses were tested.

- H01:** There is no significant difference between male and female computer studies teachers’ competence in the use of ICT in Zamfara state.
- H02:** There is no significance difference in the use of ICT by computer studies teachers based on qualification in Zamfara state.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The method was used to allow the researchers to have a vivid description of the topic for the purpose of making generalization. The population for this study comprised of all computer studies teachers in Zamfara state. A sample size of fifty (29 males and 21 females) computer studies teachers were randomly selected from public and private schools in Zamfara state, representing about 10% of the entire computer teachers in the state. A structured questionnaire tagged “ICT needs and competence level of computer studies teachers in Zamfara State” was used to gather data on the study. The instrument consists of two sections. Section ‘A’ requested the respondents’ demographic information like gender, qualification and school proprietorship. The section ‘B’ contains the items developed under each research questions raised in the study. This section contains close ended questions which restricts the respondents to respond on four-point Likert scale which consists of *Strongly Agree (SA)*, *Agree (A)*, *Disagree (D)* and *Strongly Disagree (SD)*. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha and the Alpha value was found to be 0.73, indicating high reliability of the instrument for the study. Draft questionnaire was presented to experts and specialists in ICT for face validation and observations and comments were factored into improving the content. Data Collected for the study was analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency counts and Percentage while t-test statistical tool was used to test the research hypothesis 1 and ANOVA for research hypothesis 2 at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of respondents based on gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	29	58.0
Female	21	42.0
Total	50	100.0

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents based on gender. The table indicates that 29 respondents representing (58%) were male teachers while 21 of the respondents representing (42%) were female teachers. This shows that both male and female teachers were fairly represented.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents based on qualification

Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage (%)
PGDE	7	14.0
B.Ed.	12	24.0
B.Sc.	15	30.0
HND	6	12.0
NCE	10	20.0
Total	50	100.0

Table 2 revealed that 7 of the respondents were PGDE holders constituting 14.0%. Respondents with B.Ed. were 12 which represent 24.0%, 15 of the respondents representing (30%) have BSc degree, 6 of the respondents representing (12.0%) were HND holders. The remaining 10 (20%) have NCE.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents based on school proprietorship

Proprietorship	Frequency	Percentage %
Public	31	62.0
Private	19	38.0
Total	50	100.0

Table 3 shows that 62% of the respondents were from public schools while 38% were from private schools.

Research Question 1

What are the needed ICT skills required of computer studies teachers?

Table 4: Analysis of the results on the needed ICT skills required of computer studies teachers

S/N	Item	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	I need to be literate in using ICT to search and select appropriate information resource for teaching	18 (36.0)	24 (48.0)	6 (12.0)	2 (4.0)
2	I need to be ICT literate to prepare and organized my lesson notes effectively using appropriate computer application	16(32.0)	27 (54.0)	4 (8.0)	3 (6.0)
3.	I need to be ICT literate to keep and organize my students' record effectively using appropriate computer application	20 (40.00)	26 (52.0)	3 (6.0)	1 (2.0)
4.	I need to be ICT literate to customize the presentation of information needed for teaching	17 (34.0)	20(40.0)	10 (20.0)	3 (6.0)
5	I need to be ICT literate to appropriately cite information sources	13 (26.0)	20 (40.0)	12 (24.0)	5 (10.0)

Based on the results in Table 4, responses to the statements (items 1 – 5) shows that majority of the respondents agreed that they need to be ICT literate to search and select resources appropriate for teaching, prepare and organize lesson notes effectively, keep and organize students' record effectively, customize needed presentation for teaching and appropriately cite information sources. It is seen that more respondents believed that ICT literacy is needed to provide better teaching experiences.

Research Question 2

What is the level of ICT utilization in teaching of computer studies?

Table 5: Frequency distribution and percentage on level of utilization of ICT by computer studies teachers

S/N	Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1.	I use ICT for finding and accessing information and educational materials and for preparing lessons	8(16.0)	22 (44.0)	15 (30.0)	5 (10.0)
2.	I use ICT for teaching computer skills	10 (20.0)	21 (42.0)	9 (18.0)	10 (20.0)
3.	I use ICT for making presentation	15 (30.0)	17 (34.0)	13 (26.0)	5 (10.0)
4.	I use ICT for communicating with students	14 (28.0)	15(30.0)	14 (28.0)	7 (14.0)
5.	I use ICT for communicating with other teachers	21 (42.0)	23 (46.0)	5 (10.0)	1 (2.0)

The results in Table 5 indicated that the level of utilization of ICT by Computer Studies teachers. As reflected in the table, majority of the teachers used ICT to find information and relevant education material and prepare lessons, teach computer skills, make presentation as well as communicates with students and colleagues (items 1, 2, 3 and 5 are above 60 percent).

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Over 50 percent of the teachers used ICT to communicate with students. These findings indicate that most computer studies teachers use ICT for getting resources, teaching and communication with students and fellow teachers.

Research Question 3

What is the level of competence in computer studies teachers’ use of ICT?

Table 6: Analysis of the results on the ICT competency level of computer studies teachers

S/N	Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	I am capable of connecting the computer system and its peripherals and booting it	18 (36.0)	32 (64.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
2	I have adequate keyboard skills	5 (10.0)	20 (40.0)	19 (38.0)	6(12.0)
3	I can use Microsoft Office Suite Application i.e. MS Word, MS Excel, MS PowerPoint, MS Excel etc.	14 (28.0)	30 (60.0)	3 (6.0)	3 (6.0)
4	I can set up a printer and print documents	12 (26.0)	31 (62.00)	5 (10.0)	2 (4.0)
5	I can use Internet and Email Services.	20 (40.0)	28 (56.0)	2 (4.0)	0 (0.0)

The results in Table 6 are on ICT competencies of computer studies teachers. Result showed that the respondents indicated competency in connecting computer and its peripheral, booting the computer, adequate keyboard skills, use of Microsoft office suite packages, setting up of printer and use of internet and electronic mail, items 1,3,4, and 5 (above 50 percent). However, for item 2, only 50 percent agreed to have adequate keyboard skills.

Research Question 4

What are the challenges of using ICT to teach Computer Studies?

Table 5: Frequency distribution and percentage on the challenges facing the Use of ICT to teach computer studies

S/N	Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1.	I have problem of technical support in using ICT to teach computer studies	17 (34.0)	14 (28.0)	10 (20.0)	9 (18.0)
2.	I have problem of time in using ICT to teach computer studies in school	22 (21.0)	20 (20.0)	5 (32.0)	3 (27.0)
3.	I have limited knowledge on how to integrate ICT in teaching computer studies	9 (18.0)	13 (26.0)	20 (40.0)	8 (16.0)
4.	I have problem of non-availability of adequate computer systems for teaching of computer studies	9(18.0)	29 (58.0)	9 (18.0)	3 (6.0)
5	I have the Problem of electricity to use ICT to teach computer studies	32 (64.0)	18 (26.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)

The results in Table 7 are on challenges faced in using ICT to teach. Most teachers also agreed that they have problems of technical support, appropriate use of time and non-availability of adequate computer systems. Majority however disagreed that on the challenges of knowledge of integration of ICT into teaching of computer studies. This result also shows that the major prevalent problem is electricity which is a national problem, as all the respondents agreed to this (100 percent agreed).

Research Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between male and female computer studies teachers’ competence in the use of ICT.

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Table 8: Analysis on male and female computer studies teachers' competence in the use of ICT

Gender	N	X	SD	T	DF	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remark
Male	29	2.3220	1.04123				
Female	21	2.3171	1.03535	.023	98	.981	Accepted

Table 8 shows the result of the hypothesis using t-test. It is deduced that there is significant difference between male and female computer studies teachers use of ICT. This is reflected in the result $t(98) = 0.023, p = 0.981 > 0.05$. The p-value (.981) is greater than the significance level of 0.05 which indicates that there is no significant difference between male and female computer studies teachers' competence in the use of ICT. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significance difference in the use of ICT by computer studies teachers based on qualification.

Table 6: ANOVA analysis on use of ICT by computer studies teachers based on qualification

	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Between Groups	1497.830	5	299.566	1.716	.138	
Within Groups	16405.160	94	174.523			Accepted
Total	17902.990	99				

Table 9 shows the results of the hypothesis test using ANOVA. The results indicate that $F(5, 94) = 1.716, P = 0.138 > 5\%$ alpha level of significance. The hypothesis which states that there is no significance difference in the use of ICT by computer studies teachers based on qualification is accepted since the hypothesis result is greater than 0.05.

Discussion of Findings

The research was aimed at finding out the ICT needs and competence level of computer studies teachers in Zamfara state. The findings of this research revealed that computer studies teachers are competent in the use of ICT for teaching. This is against the report of Kirschner and Selinger (2003) as cited in Adeoluwa and Ogunmodede (2018) that the vast majority of teachers do not know how to use the computers to promote educational efficiency, and they are not adequately trained to use modern information media. It also confirms the assertion that teachers have developed competence in the use of ICT. The findings indicated some challenges faced in the effective utilization of ICT for teaching computer studies. These barriers as attested to by the teachers included lack of technical support, shortage of computers and other ICT tools in schools. The findings also show that the major prevalent problem is electricity which is a national problem.

Conclusion

This study has discovered that computer studies teachers in Zamfara state are aware they need to be ICT literate to effectively teach their subjects. These findings are in accordance with that of Balogun and Yusuf (2019) which disclosed that teachers are competent in the use of ICT for teaching purposes. Also, computer studies teachers in Zamfara state have higher competence level in the use of ICT for instructional purposes. It can therefore be deduced that the teachers who are the final instrument in curriculum implementations have the desired competency in the utilization of ICT for instructional purposes. Thus, the appropriate integration of ICT in education, especially at the lower level, should not be neglected so as to bring about effective and efficient educational system.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The government (at all levels; federal, state and local) should provide adequate ICT facilities in schools. Through this, the problem of insufficient computers and facilities will be minimized.
2. The government should provide frequent professional development programmes for teachers to update themselves of emerging technology
3. The government and curriculum developers should make available, suitable educational software by seeking the assistance of software developers, and this software should be affordable or be free for school use.
4. The teachers' salary should be made attractive to encourage ICT competent teachers to apply for teaching job.

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5. Alternative power supply be made available for ICT facilities in schools.

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Exploring YouTube Application in a Language Learning Environment for Quality Learning Access in Nigeria

Akintunde, Abraham Femi, Ph.D.

Email: akinmatson@gmail.com

Tel: +2348166813796

Department of Arts Education, Faculty of Education, University of Abuja

Abstract

This paper examines Exploring YouTube Application in a Language Learning Environment for Quality Learning access in Nigeria. It explains the concept of YouTube application and other ICT tools in English as Second Language Learning classrooms and explains quality criteria for using YouTube application as an educational tool. This paper reviews literature and gives a scholarly background to the study by reviewing some contributions made by various researchers and institutions on YouTube, students' motivation and learning styles, particularly the types of videos in YouTube and language learning resources on YouTube application. The paper discusses the limitations of YouTube application and benefits of its adoption and implementation and discusses YouTube application and video sharing. The major conclusion of the study is that using YouTube application videos as one and readily available source of authentic material will encourage the students to interact actively in class and further develop their language skills as they are eager to gain deeper understanding of the subject matter. The paper then recommends that YouTube videos can be used in an ELT classroom by teachers for various teaching such as vocabulary, accents, pronunciations, voice modulation and what not.

Keywords: YouTube, Internet, Information and Communication Technology, video and Google

Introduction

The arrival of digital technologies such as the internet has resulted in a new generation of individually literate called the Net Generation (Nguyen & Tri, 2014). Due to the emergence of this technical literacy people, their learning style is differing from the previous generations. Thus, this led to an integrated approach and a paradigm shift in teaching which have witnessed an adoption of a new method of teaching using YouTube videos in the classroom. This approach has brought new insights to pedagogy in higher institution and it is believed that the use of YouTube as a teaching tool could have an effect on the level of student engagement. The use of YouTube and other Web 2.0 technologies in education has been proposed as a tool to engage new generation students (Duffy, 2018; Roodt & Peier, 2013).

In February of 2005, Steve Chen, Chad Hurley, and Jawed Karim founded YouTube with the domain name <http://www.YouTube.com>. The site was created as a forum for people to create and share short video clips online. Soon, the website has gained the popularity and many people subscribe to it. The popularity of the website has drawn the attention of Google Company leaders. They have realized the potential role that YouTube will play in the people's life in terms of education, health, politics and economy. So, the company acquired the website in 2006. In the current design of the YouTube website, there are several categories where people can find what they are interested in such as education, music, news and sports. YouTube is a very attractive social medium that contributes to the global education (Duffy, 2018). It is being increasingly used by educators to teach the English language (Terantino, 2011). It "offers fast and fun access to language and culture-based videos and instruction from all over the globe" (Terantino, 2011, p. 11). In other words, YouTube is making new demands on learning that are changing the learning ecology (Chhabra, 2012). Every year, YouTube official website <http://www.YouTube.com> shares astonishing statistics about the use of the YouTube worldwide.

According to the press link "<http://www.YouTube.com/t/press-statistics>", YouTube is localized in 43 countries and across 60 languages; YouTube had more than 1 trillion views or around 140 views for every person on the Earth. 100 million people take a social action on YouTube (likes, shares, comments, etcetera) every week. These statistics show the influence of YouTube on sharing information and knowledge with other people. Due to the popularity of the website, its free-of-charge availability and easiness of use, many language teachers have started to use the website to teach different languages by uploading language learning videos. Language learners around the world like these videos, and some of these videos have reached millions of views. For example, the video titled. "Learning English–Lesson One (Introduction)" has more than 8 million views so far. YouTube has become an important tool in many universities and colleges around the world. According to Web Analytics Association (2006), MySpace, Facebook and YouTube are the top three favorable websites for university students. Therefore, the emergence of digital technologies such as internet and the worldwide web has made the use of YouTube in

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classroom a possibility. Today, the new technology has provided a lot of opportunities to enhance the quality of teaching and learning such as the use of internet and YouTube videos. Many Nigerian university students use these technologies to help them do their assignments and other language learning tasks (Akintunde & Akuta, 2022). This technology also helped them to learn the English language as well as enhance their proficiency level. YouTube is featured as something very authentic and able to help the students because it has been reported that the lack of English language proficiency has often been mentioned as one of the major factors contributing to graduate unemployment (Duffy, 2018). How students learn and gain information from YouTube in learning the English language is very important because it will help the educators to identify the students' preference, interest and types of material that they use to enhance learning. Therefore, by using a variety of instructional methods and learning activities in the classroom or via online education can help enrich the learning environment of the students (Rinji & Akintunde, 2019).

Since the use of YouTube videos to learn English language is still a new idea, how it can be used in facilitating language learning in class effectively is still unclear. Snelson (2011) states that a study on the perception of the usage of YouTube in ESL classroom for undergraduate students is a relatively new field of study and not much literature has been published regarding the subject especially in the Nigerian context. Despite the importance of using YouTube in engaging students in the classroom, little research has been conducted to investigate the perceptions of Nigeria undergraduate in using YouTube in ESL classroom.

Concept of YouTube

YouTube (<http://www.YouTube.com>) is a Web 2.0 site that is primarily based around video sharing, commenting, and viewing. On this website, users can post self-created videos, create appropriate tags related to the video's content (taxonomy), write a title and description for the video's content, comment on his or her own or other users' videos, create or join other users' video channels on various topics of interest, search for videos based on titles or keywords, create video responses to others' videos, etc. According to Terantino (2011), YouTube is considered to be a Web 2.0 site and not merely a collection of information because members of the website share their work and participate in peer feedback through asynchronous interaction with other users.

YouTube and other ICT Tools in English as Second Language in Nigeria

Research into the use of YouTube in the classroom is a relatively new area of study. However, the use of YouTube and other ICT tools in language learning has become a popular discussion all over the world. Several scholars from different countries suggested that using ICT in the classroom is becoming more prevalent in coming years (Klimova & Poulouva; 2014, Nguyen & Tri, 2014). In Nigeria, the trend of using ICT, especially YouTube, enables students to learn actively and interactively in classrooms and is acknowledged and considered as one of the most significant changes in ESL classroom (Akintunde & Angulu, 2015). The youth today use technology like the internet more than any other methods as a medium of communication and socialization (Maisamari & Akintunde, 2019). Therefore, due to this reality, educators bring in YouTube into the classroom to suit with the students' preferences and interest thus will make learning more interesting (Nguyen & Tri, 2014).

Criteria for Using YouTube as an Educational Tool in Nigeria

Among the key factors for YouTube's success are the following:

Accessibility: one can use it everywhere, anytime, and free of charge. It is user-friendly allowing an easy upload of videos that one can subscribe to on different channels. YouTube is authentic and offers rich multicultural content that provides a unique insight into the target culture. The easy connection with other social media enables cooperation, for instance sharing videos and communicating when rating and commenting on videos. It is available on multiple devices including mobile which make it a perfect medium for education. Media agreement, meaning the use of media our students interact with on a daily basis. It is an important factor when choosing educational resources (Roodt & Peier, 2013). On the downside, nowadays, YouTube is very ad-based and there is a lot of inappropriate content. The availability of videos might change and some videos that are copyright protected are unrightfully uploaded on YouTube.

YouTube, Students' Motivation and Learning among Nigerian Students

The use of YouTube has given positive impacts to the students' motivation. As stated by Brunner (2013), videos can have a strong effect on their minds and senses. He also suggested that the use of video clips need to be inserted in multimedia

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presentation to improve learning in higher educational institutions. These included using videos to grab students' attention, improve students' concentration, generate interests in the lesson, improve attitudes towards content, draw on students' imagination and make learning fun and meaningful. Chhabra (2012) also claimed that YouTube videos are not only able to attract the students' attention, but can cater for different learning styles namely: verbal, visual, musical, and emotional intelligences. Watching videos also allows the brain to react actively to both side of the brain which helps to increase and enhance students' understanding (Chhabra, 2012). Students' motivation to learn is much relies on their learning styles. According to Romanelli, Bird and Ryan (2009) have proposed that the definition of 'learning styles' is characterise by cognitive, effective and psychosocial behaviors that serve as relatively stable indicators of how learners perceive, interact with and respond to the learning environment. Many scholars have introduced different models of learning styles. Walter Burke Barbe which proposed three learning modalities known as VAK a) visual, b) auditory and kinesthetic learning and this model is a mixture of preferences, strengths and personality which is a mixture in each individual. This model was later refined by Fleming and Mills (1992) by introducing Neil Fleming's VARK model. Neil Fleming's VARK model which has been expanded upon earlier notions of sensory modalities such as the VAK model of Barbe and colleagues and the representational systems (VAKOG) in neurolinguistic programming. The four sensory modals in Fleming's model are; 1) Visual learning, 2) Auditory learning, 3) Read/write learning and 4) Kinesthetic learning.

Fleming and Mills (1992) claimed that visual learners have a preference of seeing visual aids that represented ideas using methods other than words, such as graphs, chart, diagrams, symbols and others. Auditory learners learn better through lectures, discussions and using tapes whereas tactile or kinesthetic learners prefer to learn via experience such as moving, touching example through science projects and experiments. The selection of YouTube among students is very much influenced by their learning styles preferences and interest. Klimova and Poulouva (2014) suggested several specific examples on how YouTube could be integrated and embedded into teaching and learning in ESL classroom. Some of the activities suggested are asking the students to create a video as a part of an assessment, record a video of a guest presenter and upload it on YouTube and use the comments functionality as a platform for discussion. Besides that, they also suggested that the students can search for videos that are related to questions posted at the end of lectures and educators can show students the real-world examples of material and theory covered in class as well as ask students to post video vignettes (Klimova & Poulouva, 2014). Another research was conducted by Roodt and De Villiers (2011) which was a study on using YouTube as a tool to support collaborative learning. The study was conducted on a first year of IS course at the University of Pretoria. The course included a group project in which students used YouTube to create a video on how businesses can use Web 2.0 technologies amongst other tasks. It was reported that from a sample of 185 students, it was found that YouTube was perceived as an innovative learning technology by the majority of the students (Roodt & De Villiers, 2011). Tan and Pearce (2012) agreed that the use of YouTube videos helped students to explain key ideas in a sociology course. They used these videos in an introductory sociology course at the Foundation Centre at Durham University. Tan and Pearce (2012) used these videos to illustrate important topics by giving explanation and discussion in the class and in smaller group environments. Tan and Pearce (2012) further explained that the use of YouTube videos helped students and was seen as an effective way to support their learning.

Types of Videos in YouTube

There are two types of videos that one will use when trying to learn a foreign language through YouTube. The first kind of video is the kind created by language teachers who explain a certain grammar point or give some type of lesson in the language. This is probably the best kind of video if one is just beginning. Often, one can get access to a variety of videos where people whose profession is to teach the language will sit down and teach someone a grammar point or two. This is an excellent way to learn and one can find these videos by searching on YouTube for "learn Spanish" for instance, if one is interested in learning Spanish (Roodt & Peier, 2013). The second kind of video is the kind that is created by native speakers of the language one is trying to learn. One can find video blogs and other types of entertainment videos. This is probably best if one is an intermediate or advanced level. Usually, these types of videos are fun to watch, so, it shouldn't feel too much like "studying" or "doing work". What one should do is watch these videos and use them to discover new words that one doesn't know or sentence structures and grammar that someone isn't aware of before (Duffy, 2018).

Language Learning Resources on YouTube

The abundance of online materials and resources on YouTube is overwhelming. Among the producers of these materials are media corporations, universities, schools, or major language product providers as well as individuals. They create everything

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from very professional over semi-professional to rather silly products that can be really attractive and helpful for students or just a waste of time. A thorough research for interesting and demanding language related videos is time consuming but definitely a good investment for future lesson preparation. In 2012, YouTube has launched different channels for educational purposes to facilitate the implementation of videos in education creating a safer environment for students without inappropriate contents or distracting videos <http://www.YouTube.com/education>

Limitations of YouTube

Educationalists mentioned two points about using YouTube in education. The first one is that YouTube addresses visual and auditory learners as they can watch and listen. As Zimmerman (2010) states, "I can imagine using a YouTube video and students following directions for movement, incorporating the bodily/kinesthetic intelligence, and so" (p. 189). In searching the YouTube website, one can find different teachers using YouTube for kinesthetic intelligence. For example, Professor Acton, a researcher spends years incorporating the bodily intelligence to improve students' pronunciation, uses YouTube to help students to improve their pronunciation in their preparation for TOEFL (for instance, *TOEFL iBTSpeaking Warm-up* at TOEFL® TV - The Official TOEFL Channel on YouTube. This video receives more positive reactions from language YouTube learners (Snelson, 2011). Another point is the control of the comments and the viewers of the YouTube. People think that YouTube has less privacy. However, many features of YouTube give instructors control over who will watch their videos and what comments appear under their videos too. Tracking the YouTube statistics shows that this website grows significantly in the cyberspace. In addition, the website shows concern about the problems that teachers have about using the YouTube in their classrooms (Snelson, 2011). For example, the instructors in the United States complain about the access of the website in their schools. Some US schools have blocked the YouTube website because students might use it for non-educational purposes. Therefore, YouTube has launched a new version of the portal called 'YouTube for Schools' to make the website available in every school in the United States (Roodt & Peier, 2013).

Benefits of YouTube to Nigerian Students

YouTube is a powerful personal branding tool that allows one to use one's images and links to one's site. The benefits according to Terantino (2011) are enumerated below:

1. People love to watch videos. Video gives your readers/customers an opportunity to see what you have to offer. Approximately 65% of the population learns or responds to visual methods of information.
2. It's an effective form of free advertising. Your YouTube page is an opportunity for you to advertise to the entire world without spending a dime.
3. It's global. YouTube is available in 22 countries.
4. YouTube can help your website go viral. Viewers have the choice to share your video on Face book, Twitter, Stumble Upon, Digg, and more.
5. It allows for others to share your videos and embed your video on their site.
6. It increases your chances of showing up in search engine search results because Google owns YouTube and they work together.
7. Your video may be displayed as a suggestion in other videos that are related to yours.
8. Is rated the 3rd most visited website according to Alexia.
9. It exceeds 2 billion views a day.
10. The average person spends approximately 15 minutes a day on YouTube.
11. Over 3 million people are connected and are sharing the videos to at least one major social networking site (Duffy, 2018).
12. You can comment on videos through your YouTube channel, which will increase the traffic to your channel. Subscribe and comment on videos that are related to your niche.
13. People can subscribe to you and they will be notified every time you upload a video.

The English Language Teaching process has been energized with the emergence of new Internet technologies and now the Web tools. Also, using videos for language teaching has been one of the most effective ways to achieve success in the classroom. The ELT classes have been using the videos for teaching English language skills since many years now. The organizations like BBC and CNN have even made billions of dollars selling the video content for teaching purposes. Money

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and Time - are two things which have been creating so many hurdles in accessing the authentic video content in the past time (Stoks, 2013). But for last three and a half years, YouTube, a video content sharing website has been making the difference to it. At YouTube, anyone can post / access video content. YouTube now contains enormous amount of video content, some of which is highly exploitable in the classroom.

The English Language Teaching process has been energized with the emergence of new Internet technologies and now the Web tools (Akintunde & Akuta, 2022). Also, using videos for language teaching has been one of the most effective ways to achieve success in the classroom. Some of them are: (a). Autos & Vehicles (b). Comedy (c). Education (d). Entertainment (e). Film and Animation (f). Gaming (g). How to and Style (h). Music (i). News and Politics (j). Nonprofits and

Activism (k). People and Blogs (l). Pets and Animals (m). Science and Technology (n). Sports (o). Travel and Events. The real advantage of YouTube - at least from a language learning point of view - is that, it offers authentic examples of everyday English used by everyday people. Yes, this is the challenge as well. Students may enjoy watching these clips, but poor sound quality, pronunciation and slang can make these short videos even more difficult to understand. At the same time use of YouTube videos enables teachers to attach the students to the "real life" nature of these videos. By creating context for these short videos' students can be helped to explore a world of online English learning possibilities. YouTube videos can be used in an ELT classroom for various teaching vocabulary, accents, pronunciations, voice modulation and what not (Stoks, 2013).

YouTube and Video Sharing

Over the past year, YouTube has become enormously popular. What is common to most clips is that they are amateur videos which document occurrences from the lives of non-celebrities. As such, the clips provide a huge multimedia library of real language use by real people, a potentially rich resource for language learning or corpus collections (Tan & Pearce, 2012). The vast majority of clips are in English, and a number of ESL/EFL teachers have begun tapping into this source. While some provide sample lessons for students to view and discuss, others have uploaded videos of their own, with the specific goal of language learning in mind. Instructors of other languages, including Spanish, French, Japanese and Indonesian, have also found YouTube to be useful in language learning. One of the differences between YouTube and other social networking sites is that it does not feature community tagging (Roodt & Peier, 2013). Rather, the user posting the video supplies the tags. As is the case in most social networking sites, there are no prescribed, or even recommended, content tags. This makes searching for particular kinds of video clips or specific content very much a hit or miss enterprise (Roodt & De-Villiers, 2011). Searching on "Teaching English," for example, returns hundreds of results, most of them clips of teachers in action or class profiles, but the hit list also includes commercials that could be used in teaching English, as well as clips from commercial providers of language instruction (Tan & Pearce, 2012). As with all clips on YouTube, clips in this category vary greatly in video professionalism, length, audio quality, and interest level for folks other than those directly involved as camera operators or subjects (Roodt & De-Villiers, 2011).

Quite a few group projects from language classes are posted to YouTube as a method of sharing and publicizing. Some of the clips uploaded are just slideshows or videos shot with a static camera; others, however, are quite sophisticated in the use of lighting, captioning, camera angles, and transitions. Many come with a music soundtrack, often using commercially available songs, which for the time being some copyright holders (i.e. record companies) are allowing to be used in this way. The murky permission issues in the incorporation of copyrighted audio and video in uploaded clips to YouTube result in some clips being suddenly pulled from the site (Tan & Pearce, 2012). This makes problematic any reliance on the availability of particular clips for instructional purposes. Uploading video clips to YouTube is a quick and easy process and works in similar ways on other video sharing sites. Video clips can be in AVI, move, or mpg formats (MPEG4) and be a maximum of ten minutes long. At least one content tag is required, along with a specification of the language used in the clip, presently restricted to a choice among English, Spanish, French, Japanese, Chinese, or German. Clips can also be uploaded directly from a digital camera or a PDA, as long as they are connected to the Internet (Roodt & De-Villiers, 2011). Video can even be directly uploaded to YouTube from a Webcam. Once uploaded, the file is converted to the Flash video format used for all clips. The URL is displayed to the uploader, along with the HTML code to paste into a Web page in order to display the video on one's own page. The ease with which anyone is able to upload video clips to sites such as YouTube, along with the popularity of shooting videos on cell phones or digital cameras has enabled the video sharing frenzy the Nigeria is currently experiencing. What also has contributed to this development is the rapid growth in broadband Internet connections in Nigeria, as well as the increase in processor speeds in computers, making video editing and format conversion/compression significantly faster. This

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has been accompanied by the availability of inexpensive yet powerful video editing tools such as movie for the Macintosh or Jump cut, Videoegg, or Eyespot for Windows (Tan & Pearce, 2012). These products have specific tools for creating videos to be delivered in a Web browser. One of the most significant enabling technologies for the new video Internet age is the Flash video format, which is quickly becoming the format of choice for video on the Web, used by YouTube as well as by Google Video, MySpace, and many other sites.

Conclusion

The use of technology has become increasingly important in language teaching and learning. The successful use of technology, however, requires that language teachers have the necessary technical competence and pedagogical knowledge. The English Language Teaching process has been energized with the emergence of new Internet technologies and now the Web tools. Also, using videos for language teaching has been one of the most effective ways to achieve success in the classroom. The ELT classes have been using the videos for teaching English language skills since many years now. The real advantage of YouTube - at least from a language learning point of view - is that it offers authentic examples of everyday English used by everyday people. Nevertheless, acquiring 21st century skills through meaningful project-based teaching and learning scenarios requires effort and time. Consultations and the support of the student during the language learning process become more and more important. With the evolution of the Web, YouTube will provide a broader spectrum of functionality, for instance, using exact word and phrase search that will prove to be especially useful for language learning. The automatic creation of subtitles that is already available for some videos will improve over time and provide additional opportunities for meaningful language learning. The integration of assessment tools and tools for cooperation will improve the use of YouTube as an educational tool. The YouTube channels dedicated to education will hopefully grow in future and offer a protected environment for learning and community specific knowledge bases. As educators consider the use of YouTube video as important, thus, they must strongly consider what students' think and feel about these tools in their courses. Therefore, using YouTube videos as one and readily available source of authentic material will encourage the students to interact actively in class and further develop their language skills as they are eager to gain deeper understanding of the subject matter.

Recommendations

1. The use of YouTube videos enables teachers to attach the students to the "real life" nature of these videos. By creating context for these short videos, teachers can help students to explore a world of online English learning possibilities.
2. YouTube videos can be used in an ELT classroom by teachers for various teaching such as vocabulary, accents, pronunciations, voice modulation and what not.
3. YouTube has the potential to be a useful educational tool that offers endless opportunities for formal and informal student centered language learning approaches. For teachers to engage students in meaningful learning scenarios, learners must be enabled to connect previous knowledge to new information as well as incorporate higher and lower order thinking skills.

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Impact of Condition of Service on Job Performance in Post Basic Education Schools in Nassarawa Educational zone, Kano State

Muhammad, Auwal Alhaji

Email: auwalalhajimuhd@gmail.com

Tel: 08036717672

Department of Educational Foundations, Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education, Kumbotso, Kano State

Abstract

The study examined the 'Impact of condition of service on Job Performance in Post Basic Education Schools in Nassarawa Educational zone, Kano state.' The specific objective of the study was to examine the impact of remuneration, promotion and staff development on job performance in the post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone. The study employed the use of descriptive survey, while the sample of the study was 322 staff derived from the total population of 2,066 staff which is in compatibility with K.C. Morgan table of sample size determination. A random sampling technique was employed in selection of the sample size. A validated researcher designed Questionnaire with 30 items was used to collect the data for the study. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Of mean and standard deviation were used in answering the three (3) research questions. The findings revealed that Remuneration, Promotion and Staff Development affect teachers job performance, to a high extent in Post Basic Education Schools in Nassarawa Zonal Education Directorate, Kano State. Based on the findings, the study recommended that the government at all levels should provide Special Teachers Salary Scale, Effective Promotion and Regular Staff Development Programmes.

Keyword: Condition of Service, Job Performance, Remuneration, Promotion and staff Development.

Introduction:

Post Basic Education Schools are parts of the major educational institutions that are required by both 'Individuals and Nations' for educational growth and development. In the schools right there, the Teachers are the most needed Staff as they are in possession of the required professionalism, skills and competencies needed in effective teaching and learning activities. Hence, improvement in the quality of learning, depend to a great extent on the level of their job performance. Selemani-meke (2013) opined that poor condition of service and poor allowances received by the teachers have contributed to their lack of motivation to effectively implement their job satisfactorily at all levels. Thus, (Musa,2015) postulated that, teachers' absenteeism, job dissatisfaction, perceived neglect and excessive grievances have been identified as the most pressing and complex problems confronting the nation's teaching profession. Therefore, teachers supposed to be carefully trained, maintained and supported to enable them successfully deliver the required quality of education to the citizenry. As, the aspiration of any country to transform into educationally developed nation may only become a reality if there are competent and committed teachers who take on the responsibility of impacting the appropriate and needed attitude, skills and knowledge to its human resource (Adegbemile, 2012). This was supported by Eduese (1996) cited in Ige (2014) that teachers are the Pillars on which the architecture of the educational system rest on. According to Musa (2015), prompt payment of salaries not only assist people to attain their basic needs, but also instrumental in satisfying their higher-level need. In a nutshell, teachers' welfare is very low to guarantee efficient service delivery and attainment of the overall objectives of the education. It has been observed that the question of remuneration has much influence on staff motivation, job satisfaction, commitment, performance and productivity (Udeozor, 2004).

Similarly, promotion is believed to be one of the motivating factors amongst staff. According to Musa (2015) it is a positive way of rewarding people for their efforts and services. Sheafter et al. (2018) stated that promotion is pivotal for organizational personnel as it helps enhance individual employee performance. Similarly, Koo et al. (2020), argued that if employees perceive that there has been a dearth of promotion opportunities, they might be dissatisfied with their current jobs. But, if an employee receives a timely promotion to the next seniority post, then such employee will become more motivated and satisfied with the job role (Lup, 2018). Therefore, conclusively, Promotion is an essential part of employees' jobs career life as it will affect their attachment and engagement level at the workplace (Kostea, 2011). On the same vein, staff development has been recognized as an essential factor of motivating employees to put in their best in their respective places of work. To Khalid (2007) staff development is concern with the provision of learning, development and training opportunities for employees in an organization in order to improve their organizational performance. The teachers like any other employees

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equally need these trainings and all other opportunities that comes along with promotion. Thus, Aloma (2012) viewed staff development as a process designed to improve job understanding, promote job performance and establish future goals for career growth of workers like the teachers. It is therefore very clear that condition of service, particularly the lower-level needs such as remuneration, promotion and staff development play an essential role in motivating employees to be at their best at work. The extent to which any organization meet up with the needs of its staff, determine the level of their motivation and commitment as well as job performance (Enyi, 2004). Thus, management of human resources through the establishment and maintenance of good condition of service is of paramount importance for all organizations. Hence, nowadays many teachers run away from the educational sector to other sectors that seem to have a better condition of service. The poor pay of academics was confined by the report of the study group on Brain Drain in Nigerian Universities (1982-1993) carried out by the World Bank Project Implementation Unit of the National University Commission. According to Afolabi (2013), due to the poor condition of service and inadequate motivation for the teachers, their performance have fallen. And that many of them have decided to seek for better fortune elsewhere. Based on the above exposition, the study intends to examine the Impact of condition of Service on Staff Job Performance in Post Basic Education Schools in Nassarawa Educational zone, Kano State.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study was to examine the Impact of Condition of Service on Job Performance in Post Basic Education Schools in Nassarawa Educational zone, Kano. While, the specific objectives of the study are:

1. To examine the extent teachers' remuneration, affects their job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano State.
2. To examine the extent teachers' promotion, affects their job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano State.
3. To examine the extent staff development, affects teachers job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. To what extent does teachers' remuneration, affects their job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano state?
2. To what extent does teachers' promotion, affects their job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano state?
3. To what extent does staff development, affects teachers job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano state?

Methodology

Descriptive Survey research design was used in the study. The population of the study comprised all 2066 staff from 79 post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone N.Z.E.D (2021). Sample size of 322 staff was drawn from the study population. Random sampling technique was employed in the selection of the sample size. A self-designed questionnaire with 30 items was used for data collection. The questionnaire titled "Condition of Service and Staff Job Performance Questionnaire (CSSJPQ)". The questionnaire was structured in a modified four-point Likert rating scale. The validity of the instrument was established by experts in school of education from the department of Educational Administration and Planning. The reliability of the instrument was obtained using Cronbach's Alpha reliability test with a sample of 26 respondents. The reliability coefficient of the instrument is 0.787. The research instrument was administered by the researcher himself, with the help of one assistant in each of the "12" sampled post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone. Collected data was analyzed using descriptive statistics. In particular, frequency count, simple percentage and mean score were used in answering research questions. The analysis was conducted with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does teachers' remuneration, affects their job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano state?

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Table 1: Impact of Remuneration on Staff Job Performance

Statement	SA (%)	A (%)	DA (%)	SD (%)	M	Decision
Salary paid as at when due, enhances staff management in schools	259 (85%)	46 (15%)	---	---	3.84	Accepted
Regular payment of leave grant, enhances managing staff in schools	225 (74%)	75 (25%)	5 (2%)	---	3.71	Accepted
End of the year bonus encourages staff to work harder and enhances managing them in schools	189 (62%)	70 (23%)	33 (11%)	13 (4%)	3.42	Accepted
Payment of hazard allowance, encourages to take risk in their job and enhances managing the staff in schools	183 (60%)	82 (27%)	32 (10%)	8 (3%)	3.44	Accepted
Uncertainty of getting salary at the month end, make staff management in schools more difficult	221 (73%)	84 (27%)	---	---	3.72	Accepted
Provision of housing allowance to staff, enhances managing them in schools	209 (68%)	85 (28%)	8 (3%)	3 (1%)	3.63	Accepted
Payment of disturbance allowance to staff on transfer, make managing them easier in schools	223 (73%)	75 (25%)	4 (1%)	3 (1%)	3.69	Accepted
Leave grant payment to staff, encourages good attitude to work and improve managing staff in schools	205 (67%)	79 (26%)	15 (5%)	6 (2%)	3.58	Accepted
Payment of marking allowance after examinations, improve managing the staff within that period in schools	228 (75%)	71 (23%)	3 (1%)	3 (1%)	3.71	Accepted
Payment of overtime to staff, will enhances managing them within that period in schools	226 (74%)	71 (23%)	8 (3%)	---	3.71	Accepted

Descriptive statistics was used in examining the impact of remuneration on job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone. From the above table, computed responses shows that the respondents were of the view that Salary paid as at when due, (M= 3.84), regular payment of leave grant (M= 3.71), end of year bonus (M= 3.42), payment of hazard allowance M= 3.44), provision of housing allowance (M= 3.72), having certainty in salary payment (M= 3.63), leave grant payment (M= 3.69), payment of disturbance allowance (M= 3.58) marking allowance payment (M= 3.71) payment of overtime (M= 3.71) were all having an impact on staff performance and management in school. Based on the obtained result, it was evident that prompt remuneration to staff has a considerable impact on their performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone.

Research Question 2

To what extent does teachers' promotion affect their job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano State?

Table 2: Impact of Promotion on Staff Performance

Item	SA (%)	A (%)	DA (%)	SD (%)	M	Decision
Regular promotion of staff, ease managing them in schools	241 (79%)	64 (21%)	---	---	3.79	Accepted
Promotion of staff, enhances managing them in schools	225 (74%)	80 (26%)	---	---	3.73	Accepted
Payment of arrears, enhances managing staff in schools	243 (80%)	62 (20%)	---	---	3.79	Accepted
Refusing to promote staff who failed promotional examination, ease managing them in schools	183 (60%)	95 (31%)	14 (5%)	13 (4%)	3.46	Accepted
Verification of credentials before promoting staff encourages genuineness, and ease managing them in schools	219 (72%)	82 (27%)	4 (1%)	---	3.70	Accepted
Oral interview as a criterion for staff promotion, enhances managing them in schools	221 (73%)	84 (27%)	---	---	3.72	Accepted

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Annual Performance Appraisal Form as a criterion for staff promotion, enhances their management in schools	207 (68%)	91 (30%)	7 (2%)	---	3.65	Accepted
Promotion as a basic criterion, enhances management of staff in schools	218 (72%)	87 (28%)	---	---	3.71	Accepted
Writing examination as a criterion for staff promotion, enhances managing them in schools	222 (73%)	83 (27%)	---	---	3.72	Accepted
Increment of salary after promotion, enhances managing staff in schools	226 (74%)	79 (26%)	---	---	3.74	Accepted

Descriptive statistics was also used to examine the impact of promotion on staff performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone. From the table, computed responses shows that the respondents were of the view that regular promotion (M= 3.79), promotion of staff (M= 3.73), payment of arrears (M= 3.79), non-payment of staff who failed promotion examination (M= 3.46), verification of credentials (M= 3.70), deployment of oral interview for staff promotion (M= 3.72), annual performance appraisal (M= 3.65), deployment of promotion as basic criterion (M= 3.71), and writing of examination (M= 3.72) were all having a considerable impact on staff performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone.

Research Question 3

To what extent does staff development affect teachers job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano State?

Table 3: Impact of Staff Development on Job Performance

Item	SA (%)	A (%)	DA (%)	SD (%)	M	Decision
In-service training towards staff career development enhances their management in schools	219 (72%)	86 (28%)	---	---	3.71	Accepted
Giving orientation to newly recruited teachers improve their commitment, and enhances their management in schools	216 (71%)	89 (29%)	---	---	3.70	Accepted
Seminar helps staff acquire skills and improve their responsibilities, and enhance their management in schools	211 (69%)	94 (31%)	---	---	3.69	Accepted
Attending conferences stimulate teachers to give in their best, and enhances their management in schools	205 (67%)	98 (32%)	2 (1%)	---	3.66	Accepted
Acquisition of higher qualification by staff, promotes their management in schools	188 (62%)	117 (38%)	---	---	3.61	Accepted
Regular attendance of workshop by staff, enhances their management in schools	172 (56%)	133 (44%)	---	---	3.56	Accepted
Training of teachers on leadership and management, enhances their management in schools	195 (64%)	110 (36%)	---	---	3.63	Accepted
Staff training on area of specialization, help to enhance their management in schools	190 (62%)	115 (38%)	---	---	3.62	Accepted
Induction for new recruited teachers, enhances their management in schools	223 (73%)	82 (27%)	---	---	3.73	Accepted
Re-orientation of teachers in the school, enhances their management in schools	152 (50%)	153 (50%)	---	---	3.49	Accepted

Descriptive statistics was also used in examining the impact of staff development on job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone. From the table above, computed responses shows that the respondents were of the view that in-service teacher training (M= 3.71), orientation exercise (M= 3.70), seminars (M= 3.69), conference attendance (M= 3.66), acquisition of higher qualification (M= 3.61), workshop attendance (M= 3.56), leadership skills training (M= 3.63), training of area of specialization (M= 3.62), induction (M= 3.73) and reorientation (M= 3.49) were all having a considerable impact on job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa education zone of Kano state.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined the Impact of Condition of Service on Job Performance in Post Basic Education Schools in Nassarawa Educational zone, Kano State. The objectives of the study are to examine the impact of remuneration, promotion and staff development on job performance in schools. Findings of the study revealed that remuneration package has a significant impact on teachers' job performance in schools. This was based on the computed mean scores which were all above 2.0 level. Such, finding was in line with the work of Udeozor (2004) that remuneration has much influence on staff motivation, job satisfaction, commitment, performance and productivity. Thus, it becomes necessary for all categories of employers of teachers in both the public and private educational institutions to carefully handle all issues concerning staff remuneration with utmost greater rationality if teachers are to improve their job performance.

Similarly, the study revealed that promotion has significant impact on teachers' job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano state. This was based on the obtained mean scores which were all above 2.0 levels. The findings were in line with the work of Ige (2014) who postulated that teachers that spent more years than stipulated on a particular grade level without getting promotion usually feel discouraged and became frustrated with the teaching job resulting in poor discharge of responsibilities which negatively affect the set educational goals. Therefore, it is necessary and very clear that teachers' employers particularly at different levels of government should ensure that teachers have their promotion as at when due in order for the teachers to enhance their job performance.

The study equally found that staff development has significant impact on teachers' job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano state. This was also based on the obtained mean scores which were also above 2.0 levels. The result was in line with the work of Aloma (2012) that staff development prepares workers to improve job understanding, promote job performance and establish future goals for career growth of workers, including teachers. He pointed out that training is necessary for all categories of staff to improve their performance and prepare them for promotion.

Conclusion

Conclusion should be drawn from findings and discussed in prose. Don't itemize it. Based on the findings of the study, remuneration package has a significant impact on teachers' job performance in schools. This was based on the computed mean score which was above 2.0 level. Similarly, the study revealed that promotion has significant impact on teachers' job performance in post basic education schools. This was based on the obtained mean score which was also above 2.0 level. The study equally found that staff development has significant impact on teachers' job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone. This was also based on the obtained mean score which similarly was also above 2.0 level.

Recommendations

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations were given:

1. **Special Teachers Salary Scale:** The remuneration package for teachers should be reviewed to much similar higher lucrative packages like the Federal Inland Revenue Service, Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency, Nigerian Communication Commission, Energy Commission of Nigeria, Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation Customs Service, and Banking of industry etc. This will not only motivate teachers to be at their best but to also attract and retain the best brains in the teaching profession.
2. **Periodic Promotion:** There should be an efficient and periodic promotion that will allow Teachers to be having prompt promotion as at when due. This will motivate teachers like their counterpart workers to enhances their job performance in all level of educational institutions particularly in post basic education schools in Nassarawa Educational zone.
3. **Regular Staff Development Programme:** There is the need to regularly allow the teachers to attend workshops, seminars, conferences and refresher courses in order to become more updated on the contemporary skills concerning teaching and learning activities. Such acquired updated skills, will go a long way to motivate the teachers to improve their job performance.

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Impact of Doctor of Philosophy Degree Programme on Students' Experience: A case study of National Open University of Nigeria

Akpan, Louis Okon, Ph.D.

Email: airmailo@yahoo.com

Tel: +2349020342987

Department of Educational Foundations, National Open University of Nigeria

Abstract

In Nigeria, the acquisition of Ph.D. degree is the ultimate expectation of every upcoming scholar and researcher. National Universities Commission issued directive some years ago that every lecturer teaching in the university should be armed with PhD degree. In light of the above, persons without the degree enroll on the programme. However, recent narrative by Ph.D. supervisees on ugly experiences in the hands of the supervisors necessitated the study. In other words, the researcher sought to understand how doctoral students experience Ph.D. supervision in National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN). Two questions guided the study. Furthermore, phenomenological approach as used for the phenomenon under investigation. Interpretive paradigm was used as lens to understand participants' lived experience. Nine doctoral candidates formed the sample size. Moreover, semi structured interview was used to elicit information from the participants. After the researcher subjected the data to transcription and coding, the emerging themes were analysed it was further recommended that supervisees and supervisors should undergo periodic orientation on supervisory ethics using Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). Findings revealed that Ph.D. students experience unhealthy relationship with their supervisors, hence led to the delay in the completion of the programme. Based on the findings, it was further recommended that supervisees and supervisors should undergo periodic orientation on supervisory ethics

Keyword: Doctor of Philosophy Degree Program, students' experience, supervisor, supervisees, NOUN

Introduction

In Nigeria and all over the world, Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) is the highest degree awarded by university institutions to aspiring scholars and researchers. It is critical and vital to university community who are desirous of transferring knowledge from one generation to the next generation of scientists, technologists and researchers (Hemmati, & Mahdie, 2020). Be that as it may, the National Universities Commission (NUC) whose essence of its establishment is to regulate operationality of university education in Nigeria has emphasized that every lecturer irrespective of his or her specialization should have Ph.D. In fact, the former Executive Secretary of NUC reported that there were 35,000 lecturers in Nigeria, out of this figure 21,350 which represent sixty-one percent still did not have a doctoral degree. There was a directive by NUC to all Vice Chancellors in the country that any person who do not possess a doctoral degree should be relieved of his/her appointment. In light of the above, various universities has given lecturers and researchers who does not possess this degree an opportunity to go for the programme. However, there are some universities whose lecturers who could not acquire this degree at the expiration of the grace period, were forced to resign. For instance, it was reported on Punch Newspapers of 25th May, 2023 that the management of the University of Calabar sacked twelve lecturers in various departments that could not present Ph.D certificate at the expiration of the period. It is on basis of the above and others, which is not the focus of the study that prompted people to enroll for the programme.

At the National Open university of Nigeria (NOUN), many candidates have registered for doctoral programme in various departments. Many of the candidates have stated that though the Ph.D programme is rewarding (Van Rooij, Fokkens-Bruinsma & Jansen, 2021), it is tied to negative outcomes such as attrition and delay (Riva, Gracia & Limb, 2022) lower productivity and mental health problems such as worrying, anxiety, exhaustion and stress (Pyhältö, Stubb & Lonka 2009). In a similar vein, Woolderink, Putnik, van der Boom, and Klabbers (2015) Tikkanen, Pyhältö, Bujacz and Nieminen (2021) argued that PhD journey is fill with tensions and challenges due to a sense of isolation, lack of support, ambiguity about doctoral expectations, deficient understandings of academic life, difficulty in completing a dissertation and lack of adequate funding. The complexities experienced by most Ph.D candidates while on the programme generated curiosity to understand the impact of Ph.D students experience with their supervisors in NOUN

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The theory that underpins the study is known as attachment theory propounded by John Bowlby and Mary Ainsworthy. Attachment theory explains the relationships and bonds that exist between two or more individuals (Bowlby & Ainsworth, 2013). It was hypothesized that future security, well-being, and positive relationships in adulthood are often contingent on the secure mother–infant relationship and the internal working models experienced and produced during infancy and childhood. The theory emphasised that the earliest bonds formed by children with their caregivers have a tremendous impact that continues throughout life. In other words, children attach to carers instinctively, for the purpose of survival and, ultimately, genetic replication (Abrams et al., 2013). Having access to a secure figure (parents) decreases fear in children when they are presented with threatening situations. Not only having a decreased level of fear important for general mental stability, but it also implicates how children might react to threatening situations. The presence of a supportive attachment figure is especially important in a child's developmental years (Abrams et al., 2013).

Within education sector, school students perform excellently well when they relate with their teachers or supervisors. In fact, where a teacher establishes good bond with his or her student, there is a possibility that the said student do have confident on the teacher, hence he/she do perform well on the subject. A study conducted by Wang (2021) indicated that children with disorganised attachment may struggle with self-control behaviours, this would affect their involvement in classroom. In the same vein, Košir, Aslan and Lakshminarayanan (2023) held that children with ambivalent attachment have worse cognitive performance and pay less attention in school since their exploration is restricted. The above conversation explains the importance of the theory in the study, hence its adoption to tease out the experiences of PhD students in NOUN.

Supervision is a social interaction between two or more individuals who might have diverging views but same objectives (Zaheer & Munir, 2020). According to Wood and Louw (2018), supervision may be conceptualized as intensive, interpersonally focused one-to-one relationship between the supervisor and supervisee(s). The essence of supervision is to ensure that the intended objective(s) of both supervisor and supervisee is met with precision. O'donovan, Halford and Walters (2011) submitted that the ultimate goal of supervision is the creation of positive working relationship between the supervisor and the supervisee (student). Lee (2008); Howells et al. (2017) opined that establishment of relationship seems to be a key factor in the successful completion of a doctoral study and (Ali, Watson & Dhingra 2016) it enhances students' well-being and academic performance.

In developed countries such as Britain, USA, Russia, Canada, among others, Ali, Watson and Dhingra (2016) held that PhD supervisees are at liberty to choose their supervisors. Ali et al. (2016) went further to say that it is candidate's right to choose supervisor for his/her research work. Gruzdev, Terentev and Dzhafarova (2020) maintained that most PhD candidates who completed their dissertation are the ones who choose their supervisors by themselves. Furthermore, literature also indicated that this relationship is characterised by several distinct attributes, such as the candidate's guidance through the formal research process towards completion (Thani, Wessels & Visagie, 2023), feedback on submitted work, theoretical and methodological advice (Duke & Denicolo, 2017), scholarly mentoring, and emotional support (Manathunga, 2019). In another circumstance worth reviewing, is the issue of absenteeism of the supervisor. Bazrafkan, Shokrpour, Yousefi and Yamani (2016) held that 'ghost supervisor' is an invisible one which is not always seen or give feedback to the student without delay. From the above background, Almusaed (2018) asserted that students who experience this type of supervision usually have nightmare. However, there should always be a balance between constantly seeking advice of supervisor for every small problem and being left alone without any support at all (Halse & Malfroy, 2010). Although, PhD students who experienced this type of supervision may actually appear not satisfactory (Lee 2010). Furthermore, lack of sufficient supervision is usually one of the main obstacles and reasons for delayed in completion of PhD programme (Almusaed & Almssad, 2020).

Aside from ghost supervision, there exist myriad of literature in respect of poor mutual respect between supervisor and supervisee. Almusaed and Almssad, (2020) opined that most supervisors exhibit abusive words on their students, (Cantor, 2020) which led to students having negative feelings towards the programme. According to Cohen and Baruch (2022), most supervisors does not have patience to give listening hears to supervisees' views, hence these abused students minimise interactions with their abusive PhD supervisors. From all indications, abusive supervision has peculiar negative consequences on doctoral students such as low job satisfaction, attrition or severe psychological stress including depression (Pyhältö, Toom, Stubb & Lonka, 2012). Vähämäki, Saru and Palmunen (2021) argued that in abusive supervision students to perceive their supervisor more of a boss or leader, while they view themselves more of followers or protégés.

Objective of the study

The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of Ph.D degree programme on students' experience with specific emphasis on National Open University of Nigeria.

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Research Questions

In line with purpose of the study, the following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the impact of Ph.D. students experience on dissertation supervision?
2. In which area(s) do PhD supervisees need support from the university?

Methodology

The research methodology adopted for the study is qualitative research method. Similarly, the researcher deployed hermeneutic phenomenology as research design for the study. According to Ramsook (2018), the essence of using hermeneutic phenomenology in qualitative study is to understand the complexity of the lived experiences. In the same vein, Hermeneutic phenomenology focused on personalized lived experiences and interpretations of individuals' communication which involve verbal, non-verbal and written words (Nigar, 2020). However, in order to understand and make sense of the true-life story of doctoral candidates, the researcher employed interpretive paradigm. Alharahsheh and Pius (2020) submitted that interpretive approach is used in qualitative research so as to gain insights into participants' views. Similarly, Ugwu, Ekere and Onoh (2021) held that reality is interpreted through the meanings that people give to their lives, and this meaning can be discovered through language or dialogue.

In line with qualitative method adopted, the researcher used purposive sampling technique to select the sample size. Here, the choice of purposive technique is based on the researcher's ability to get in-depth information from few participants he has chosen before hands. Therefore, the researcher purposively selected nine doctorate candidates from nine faculties of NOUN to form sample size for the study. The reason the researcher decided to use small sample size is based on Boddy (2016); Lakens' (2022) assertion that small sample size facilitates researcher's close association with the participants, enhance validity of the information and ensure gathering of in-depth data for phenomenon under investigation.

In any research study, researcher should ensure that there is strict adherence to research ethics. Here, the researcher sought the permission from the Dean, Postgraduate School (PGS) to interview Ph.D candidates. Furthermore, he also developed consent form and gave them in which they signed indicating their willingness to participate in the study. For anonymity of the participants, researcher used pseudonym for their names. The instrument used for the gathering of information for the study was semi- structured interview schedule. The choice of semi-structured interview in the study is drawn from Belina's (2023) assertion who says that it allows for gathering of information from key participants who have personal experiences, attitudes, perceptions and beliefs related to the topic under investigation.

During the interview session, the researcher used both audio tape-recorder and field-note in the collection of information from the participants. It has been argued by Rutakumwa, Mugisha, Bernays, Kabunga, Tumwekwase, Mbonye and Seeley (2020) that the use of audio tape recorder and field-note during interview is important because it capture what transpired during the interview and also help interviewer to fill in the holes from the notes when he/she fall behind. After the interview, the researcher transcribed the data into textual material. Thereafter, the textual data is subjected to (Parameswaran, Ozawa-Kirk & Latendresse, 2020) open coding. The reason for subjecting the data to open coding is based on Saldaña (2016); Mohajan and Mohajan's (2022) position who stated that open coding enables the researcher to methodically and systematically analyse data and also enhance trustworthiness of the analysis. After the coding, there were emergence of themes which were subjected to analytical tool known as Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). According to Smith & Nizza (2022), IPA is use as analytical tool in order to uncover individual lived experience through a process of in-depth reflective inquiry.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the impact of Ph.D. students experience on dissertation supervision?

The themes that emerged from open coding in which the data was subjected to are unhealthy relationship, untimely provision of feedback and disrespect of supervisees. These are explained below.

Unhealthy relationship

Interview indicated that the type of relationship existing between supervisor and supervisee is unhealthy one. In fact, Joseph who is at the post-field stage of PhD journey was reluctant to narrate his experience in the hands of his supervisors. After the researcher's persuasion, he posited that he has gone through unpalatable experience with his supervisors. The researcher probed further the kind of 'unpalatable experience' he might have received in the hands of his supervisors. In his

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reply, Joseph declared: “I want to let you know that the relationship existing between one of my supervisors and I is horrible. I am always afraid of seeing him due to the poor relationship.” When the researcher interrogated on the cause of poor relationship between him and his supervisor, he responded: “The issue brought about the poor relationship is that I could not see him for over three months due to my commitment in my workplace. When I finally met him, he was angry. This generated bad blood.” Though Joy was on the opinion that she maintained relative stable relationship with her supervisor, however, she reiterated that it is the kind of relationship existing between cat and mouse. When the researcher probed further on the assertion of ‘cat and mouse relation’, “she explained: In fact, there is sour relationship existing between my supervisor and I. The reason for this bad relationship is based on the fact that he is not critical on my work. Moreover, his little inputs are confusing and inconsistent.

This position was corroborated by Oluwatuyi, who reported that his supervisor do not have patience to engage on scholar argument without resorting to shouting. He narrated how his supervisor directed him to use a particular theory in his work, when he complained about the complexity of the theory, the supervisor instructed him to go and read about it. Oluwatuyi concluded by saying that the method of his supervisor’s supervision is strange and unfriendly hence the existence of their unstable relationship.

Untimely provision of feedback

It was reported by Kola, Kemi and Gloria that due to their supervisors’ unsolicited delay in going through their research works and also providing feedback on time has cause them nightmare. Kemi was very blunt to state that she has already spent seven years doing Ph.D without hope of completion. When Kemi was interrogated to explain the cause of the delay, she responded:

I want to inform you that aside from financial involvement in her Ph.D programme which is demanding, the delay caused by my supervisor is unimaginable. I gave my supervisor chapter two of the dissertation to look at. It took him over four months to send the feedback to me.

Notwithstanding Kemi’s assertion, Kola reported that he was so happy when he finished his coursework in a record time of one year. He went further to state he was thinking that his dissertation would take him only five years to complete. He concluded by saying that the untimely delay in the hands of his supervisor is not only uncalled for, but very frustrating. He, therefore, queried; “why on earth supervisor should spent six months to go through a chapter? This is unacceptable and unfortunate,” he concluded. In a state of frustration, Gloria thundered; “I am considering abandoning from this programme if the situation continues. I would rather use the money to train my children instead of wasting my time and money seeking for the degree which is not visible.” Additionally, Oluwatuyi opined that what PhD students valued is feedback given in a non- judgmental and constructive way, not just emphasizing all that was not good. As long as feedback was constructive, it was evaluated positively by PhD students. However, he concluded that it is very dangerous where feedback is rarely given by the supervisor to the supervisee.

Disrespect of supervisee by supervisor

Ayoola, Mfon and Victor were unanimous in their narrative when they stated that undergoing Ph.D journey in this university in particular and Nigeria in general is very difficult, when one consider the way supervisees are treated by the supervisors. When the researcher asked how they are treated, Mfon replied:

The perception of most supervisors towards supervisees is unfortunate and unacceptable. Imagine my supervisor asking me to drop off his children in the school, am I his houseboy? This is disrespectful from any angle one look at it. If he is not supervising me, would he have asked me to do that?

Similarly, Ayoola and Victor explained that aside from running for errand, they are often treated as secondary school students at the slightest provocation. In fact, Victor continued by saying that any time he intends to see his supervisor, he is compelled to pray to God not to meet him in his bad mode, otherwise, the essence of meeting that day will be defeated, because he will visit his frustration on him. Victor emphasized that “ordinarily, the respect between supervisor and supervisee ought to be mutual and reciprocal, but in this university the situation is different. It is one sided.” Collaborating Victor’s assertion, Mfon opined that some supervisors look at themselves as ‘boss’ who should not be questioned irrespective of whether they are right or wrong. He, then, queried why he should not be accorded the respect he deserves as a matured person and Master degree holder who worked for so many years before he enrolled for doctoral degree. Going by Mfon’s words, he expressed:

Most supervisors in this university still believed that they are everything for the student. They maintain the traditional and primitive ‘boss and servant relationship’ which is very obvious within African societies. I do not expect this type of behaviour from people who professes knowledge.

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Research Question 2

In which area(s) do PhD supervisees need support from the university?

From the analysis, all the participants clearly acknowledged the involvement of supervisee in the choice of supervisor and need for funding for PhD candidate. These are explained below.

Involvement of supervisee in the choice of supervisor

Kemi, Joseph, Oluwatuyi and Joy were on the view that in Africa, and particularly Nigeria supervisees are do not have any input on the choice of supervisors for their Ph.D journey. They wonder why Postgraduate School of the university should be saddled with the responsibility of appointing supervisors for all Ph.D candidates. Kemi said that Ph.D candidates should not be sidelined on the choice of their supervisors, otherwise, it would amount to shaving one's hairs in his absence. In similarly circumstance, Joseph and Joy stated that in developed countries, such as Norway, Sweden, South Africa, among others, Ph.D applicants are always given the right to select their mentors for Ph.D study. In fact, Joy went further to report that in Europe and America, Ph.D applicants' ability to choose his/her supervisor is one of the criteria for the admission into the programme. Joy called for the involvement of Ph.D candidates in the choice of their supervisors. She further said that allowing Ph.D candidate to choose his/her supervisor will eliminate unnecessary friction that usually occur between supervisor and supervisee. In line with Joy's argument, Oluwatuyi held that he does not believe in the theory of magnetic law of Physics which says that "unlike poles attract." He said that the application of this theory on human being is not acceptable, because human being does react negatively to harmful or uncomfortable situation. However, Oluwatuyi proposed adoption of homophily theory between supervisor and supervisee. At this juncture, the researcher was compelled to probe further on the adoption of homophily theory between supervisor and supervisee, in response Oluwatuyi declared:

I am a proponent of homophily theory propounded by Robert Merton in 1954 who stated that individual can only associate with others who are similar to themselves. In other words, there is a popular adage which says that 'birds of the same feather flocks together.' From this analogy, it is pertinent for the supervisee to pick his/her supervisor whom he/she will be able to work with.

In addition to above assertion, Ayoola and Victor reported that the success of a supervisor and PhD student depends on what often is vaguely known as 'solid chemistry' existing between them. They went on to say the solid chemistry exist where supervisor and supervisee have had prior contact such as being a former student of the supervisor. Therefore, Victor reiterated that the involvement of the supervisee in the choice of his/her supervisor is paramount in the completion of Ph.D programme and should be integrated.

Need for securing fund for doctoral students

Mfon, Glory, Joseph and Joy were on the opinion that most supervisors in Nigeria rarely attract any grant to themselves for research purpose, not to mention for their Ph.D students. Mfon posited that few of them who received grant hardly incorporate their supervisees, therefore, subjecting supervisees to untold hardship of funding the project. However, Oluwatuyi deviated a bit from the position held by Mfon, when he narrated that in developed world, supervisors attract grants for their doctoral students during the period of the study. He posited that most Ph.D supervisees are sponsored by either the university or supervisor. Therefore, he wonders why the situation could not be replicated in Nigeria to safe most doctoral candidates the agony of funding their programme. In addition to Oluwatuyi's narrative, Joseph and Joy explained that sourcing for grant to prosecute PhD programme is very difficult in Nigeria especially when the applicant(s) is/are not academic staff of any university. TET fund is not ready to commit any fund to anyone is not member of academic staff of a particular university either in Nigeria or outside. The researcher was compelled to ask Joseph and Joy if they have applied for the grant from TET fund before and they were denied. In a quick response, Joy stated:

My experience with TET Fund is nothing to write home about. I have applied for the sponsorship of this Ph.D. programme one year before its commencement. I was denied on the grounds that I did not provide the admission letter from the university. When I finally got the admission from the university, I applied again till date I have not heard of anything from this government agency.

After Joy's narrative, Joseph queried; "is this antic adopted by TET Fund in denying them the sponsorship of PhD programme right? This is unacceptable and infringement in one's right to education." In light of the above, all the participants explained that Ph.D. programme is tasking and demand huge financial involvement, therefore, it is necessary for supervisors, university and TET Fund to source for funding for their supervisees and intended Ph.D. applicants.

Discussion of Findings

From the findings, it was discovered that Ph.D. students experience unhealthy relationship with their supervisors. From all indications, the researcher believed that this unhealthy relationship between supervisor and supervisee may be resulted from PhD candidate high expectations from the supervisor which the supervisor could not met. When the supervisee and supervisor have contrasting expectations, this will surely affect their relationship which in turn causes unnecessary delay in the completion of the programme. The findings have strong agreement with Gill and Burnard (2008) assertion who argued that a poor relationship existing between supervisor and supervisee is a recipe for disaster and often ends in demoralization and depression, (Van Rooij, Fokkens-Bruinsma & Jansen, 2021) and may even result to students' dissatisfaction which often led to failure in the completion of the programme.

Similarly, aside from poor relationship which exists between supervisors and supervisees, findings also revealed that doctoral students experience series of untimely delay in the provision of feedback from the supervisors. From the researcher's perspective, it can be argued that most supervisors involved themselves in other activities in the campus such as being a member of a particular committee which made unavailable most times. This situation affects most doctoral students in the area of provision of feedback. Cumulatively, an average doctoral student in Nigeria takes approximately between 7 and 17 years to complete their doctoral study, instead of sixteen semesters as stipulated by the university policy. Obviously, this delay often led to frustration and eventual abandonment of the programme by the students. The findings collaborated with Thani, Wessels and Visagie (2023) notion who reported that most doctoral students who feel frustrated as result of their supervisors' delayed in providing feedback on the submitted work usually abandoned Ph.D. programme.

Additionally, another finding has shown that most supervisors exhibited high degree of disrespect to their supervisees. In fact, it was discovered that most supervisees received all manners of disrespect from their supervisors. Ordinarily, respect is reciprocal, however, when the supervisees are always at the receiving end, it usual leads to unresolvable conflict which may result in non-completion of PhD study or opting out of the programme. From all indications, the above finding reinforces Madan's (2021) view who postulated that supervisor's abusive behaviour is linked to supervisee's frustration, stress and low self-esteem. Additionally, Ivan & Evgeniy & Zibeyda (2019) the largest share of PhD students who are dissatisfied with their supervisors was observed among those who disrespect their personality.

It was revealed that the area in which Ph.D. supervisees need support from the university is their involvement in the choice of supervisor. They actual frowned at the situation in which the Postgraduate School without consultation from the supervisees pick supervisors for them. From the researcher's perspective, it is argued that anyone who is not partaking in the choice of his/her friend, the friendship is as good as non-existence. The findings further confirmed the conclusion made by Le, Pham, Kim and Bui (2021) that Postgraduate School involvement in the selection of supervisors for PhD candidates that do not fit supervisees' expectations, however, it is an invitation to chaos between the supervisees and supervisors.

Securing funds for doctoral students was found to be the needed support that Ph.D. supervisees desire from the university and their supervisors. It has been acknowledged that Ph.D. programme is a capially intensive programme. In fact, doctoral students need money during the proposal, pre-field, field trip and post-field stages of their dissertation write up. Aside from the above, the money for stationaries and others necessary things needed by the students for the study cannot shoulder alone. Hence the supervisees called for the involvement of the university and supervisors in supporting the programme through the award of grant. The above finding was earlier canvassed by Belavy, Owen and Livingston (2020); Corsini, Pezzoni and Visentin (2022) who stated that there is a positive relationship between those whose Ph.D programme were funded and their high completion rate.

Conclusion

Before the commencement of PhD journey, all applicants have had high expectations about their supervisors especially in the context of mutual relationship, reciprocity of respect and completion period. However, the experiences of most PhD candidates in National Open University of Nigeria concerning the styles of supervision adopted by their supervisors were unfortunate and sad. The study explained unhealthy relationship and other unnecessary frictions between supervisees and supervisors which often resulted to the abandonment of programme.

Recommendations

Obviously, the motive for the study was to unpack the lived experiences of PhD students had with the supervisors in the cause of PhD supervision. Based on the findings, the researcher recommended as follows;

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Postgraduate School should involve doctoral candidates in the choice of their supervisors just like their counterparts in developed countries. It is unacceptable for anybody to choose a friend for another person because they would be able to work together. If the supervisee is involved in the choice of his/her supervisor, there is high possibility of a good working relationship.

In the developed countries, all supervisees and supervisors undergo periodic orientation on supervisory ethics. In fact, this measure keeps the parties involved on their responsibilities to each other. If this is replicated in NOUN particular and Nigeria in general, it is believed that the unnecessary delay in the completion of the programme will be eliminated.

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Impact of Social Network Application on Interest and Performance in Concept Quadratic Equation among Secondary Students in Yenagoa Metropolis

Gabriel C. Job Ph.D.¹

Email: gjob@noun.edu.ng

Tel: +2348033397290

Isaac B. Ado²

Email: isaacado2014@gmail.com

Tel: +2348138905819

¹Faculty of Education, National open University of Nigeria, Abuja

²Federal University Otuke, Bayelsa State

Abstract

This study investigated the impact of social network application on interest and performance in concept quadratic equation among secondary students in Yenagoa metropolis. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The instrument used for data collection was Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT). The instrument was validated by two experts in Mathematics and Measurement and evaluation and its reliability coefficient was found to be 0.87 using Kuder Richardson formula 20. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research question, while the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was adopted in testing the hypotheses at $P < 0.05$ level of significance. The two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that there was significant difference in the mathematics interest and performance of students taught using Slack and those taught using without social networking teaching app. Also, there was significant difference in the mathematics interest and performance of students taught using WhatsApp and those taught using without social networking teaching app. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that mathematics teachers should be encouraged to use social networking tools in teaching/learning of mathematics to help the students gain experiences on the strategy in order to enhance high performance level amongst them.

Keywords: Interest, Achievement, Social Network Application Tools

Introduction

Mathematics is a science that deal with the logic of shapes, quantity and arrangement. It is a discipline that is found to be more related to the scientific and technological facets of man's world than to any other aspect as it occurs and reoccurs in physical and natural sciences (Kwak, 2010). It is referred to as the language used to describe the problems arising from most branches of science and technology. It is however, found basically in almost all aspects of discipline, most especially in areas such as quantity, structure and space. The interrelationship existing between mathematics and advancement of the human race shows the importance of mathematics in human life.

Mathematics as a field of study over the years has been regarded as a worrisome subject as statistics have shown that the percentage of students' performance in it in public Examination such as WAEC and NECO has been low and one of the identifiable reasons recently offered by the WAEC Chief Examiner's report (2018) is that students find it difficult to translate word problems to equations. The WAEC Chief Examiner's report (2021) further affirmed students' poor interpretation of questions (both word and non-word problems) and inability to apply mathematical principles correctly. Numerous reasons have been given for the poor performance of students among which are, the use of non-appropriate teaching methods, lack of frequent interaction between teacher-students, students-students, the school environment, not using instructional materials and lack of interest in the subject.

Interest of students have been considered as an important factor in the teaching of mathematics. According to Arthur (2019), interest as one of the constructs is shadowed by the search of students' performance in mathematics and that students who develop interest in mathematics finds it easy to perform in the subject. The development of any nation lies in her dexterity for strategies that can arouse the interest of the students to love and embrace mathematics, science and technology (Ado, 2018). The strategies for arousing students' interest could also be achieved through the use of instructional materials.

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Instructional materials have been considered very important in the teaching of mathematics. A well-planned and imaginative use of visual aids in mathematics lessons do much to banish apathy, supplement of inadequacy of books as well as arouse the interest of students. The use visual instructional aid makes the lesson practical such that it enables students to see the links between concepts, thereby helping the flow of thought which assist in their logically thinking. Visual instructional aides (pictures, post cards, graph, diagrams, charts, maps, film strip and models) are very crucial to the teaching of mathematics. Many teachers over the years have endeavoured to select instructional materials that relates to the content of mathematics subject, in order to facilitate in-depth understanding of such mathematics lessons, and to make learning of mathematics interesting and attractive to the learner. Different strategies such as the audio, visual, and audio-visual teaching materials have been developed and used in the teaching of mathematics overtime, yet, records still show a significant increase in the poor performance of students in mathematics examinations (Levesque, Stanck and Ryan 2004). It is in the light of this that the research work seeks to address the issue of students' poor performance in the subject by introducing internet application tools such as slack and WhatsApp as a teaching resource to help improve students' performance in mathematics examinations.

Social media could be described as internet application tools which provides an opportunity for users to converse and interact in sharing of text and multimedia contents via virtual networks. According to Joseph (2013) and Nottle (2010), social networking help in schools and universities to leverage and complement formal education activities and enhance learning outcome. It also provides opportunities for new learning relationship as well as strengthening teaching and learning process. Joseph (2013) further reiterated that teaching-learning and adapting to the world using a relatively new form of communication is made easy through social media. This is why social media tools such as slack and WhatsApp is intended by this work to see if the performance of students can be enhanced.

WhatsApp is a mobile application that allows users to communicate with one another using a smartphone or a computer (Edglossary, 2016 cited in Bruno & Layer, 2020)). It helps in providing instructions when the instructor and students are separated by distance, time or both. Teachers can use WhatsApp to communicate with their students more swiftly and effectively. Group chat features can be used to coordinate learning and studies within and outside the school premises to produce lessons that could be listened to at students' leisure, and maintain constant contact with students outside of the classroom. Bruno and Layer (2020) investigated the effects of WhatsApp Use on Students' Socio-Emotional Development and Academic Achievement and found that video chatting, online chatting through WhatsApp and frequent use of WhatsApp has effect on students' socio-emotional development and academic achievement. Folasayo and Olajide (2022) examined effects of WhatsApp group learning platform on senior secondary schools' students' learning outcomes in Science, Technology, and Mathematics in Ekiti State, Nigeria and found that there was no significant difference between the performances mean scores of students exposed to STM through the WhatsApp Group Learning Platform and those exposed to the conventional method

Slack is a Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC) tool widely used as a collaborative tool in institutions. It is an application that can support the teacher in giving the material and assignment, and can improve their teaching practices (Perkel 2017; Heryandi, 2020). Teckchandani (2018) argues that it can also be used effectively in the classroom, as students will often find their own way of communicating with each other around an assessment which normally includes a combination of texting, email, and cloud-based services. According to Muller (2023), Slack allows for setting up channels dealing with different aspects, for instance, readings, lectures, or assignments. Transparency enhances fairness since students who are less willing to ask questions will be able to read the responses. Instructors can encourage students to help each other before providing an answer and share additional materials without drafting a formal email. Learners can communicate with one another and approve content by adding emojis below messages. Meenakshi (2013) investigated importance of ICT in education and found that teacher's empowering and significant achievement in teaching and learning can be improved by the use of the online application, such as Slack application in classroom practices.

The overwhelming adoption of these applications can be linked to the fact that the students have tremendously embraced the use of mobile devices as an integral part of their everyday life. In regard to WhatsApp becoming a growing phenomenon in academic usage for discussing academic topics of mutual interest and Slack being an application that can provide collaboration and communication issues. This study sought to examine the influence of social Networking such as Slack and WhatsApp in the teaching and learning of Mathematics in secondary school in Yenagoa metropolis of Bayelsa State.

Students' mathematics performance has been poor over the years. This poor performance of student in tests and examinations has been a challenge to the schools, educators, and the teachers. Hence, different methods and resources have been adopted in the teaching of mathematics which included, discovery method, traditional method as well as the problem-solving method to see if it could help to improve students' performance in mathematics. These methods and resources have not completely worked out in the enhancement of the performance of students in Mathematics. it is on this note that the study seeks

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to ascertain if social networking tools (WhatsApp and Slack) are used in the teaching of mathematics would enhance students' performance in mathematics.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to determine the impact of social network applications on interest and performance in concept quadratic equation among secondary students in Yenagoa metropolis. Specifically, the study sort to

1. Determine the difference in the mean interest score of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and that taught using lecture method in Yenagoa metropolis.
2. Determine the difference in the mean performance scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught using lecture methods in Yenagoa metropolis.

Research Questions

The following Research Questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in the mean interest scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught using lecture methods in Yenagoa metropolis?
2. What is the difference in the mean performance scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught using lecture methods in Yenagoa metropolis?

Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between mean interest scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught using lecture methods in Yenagoa metropolis.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught using lecture methods in Yenagoa metropolis.

Methodology

The design adopted for this study was quasi-experimental design, specifically, the pretest-posttest control group design. This design was used because the students were left in their intact classes to avoid disruption of classes. The population of the study consisted of a total of two thousand, two hundred and three (2,203) students in senior secondary two (SS II) 2022/2023 academic session in the thirteen public secondary schools in Yenagoa metropolis of Bayelsa State. The sample comprised of one hundred and fifty (151) students in senior secondary two (SS II) drawn from three schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area. The sample was selected purposely because the researchers ensured that the students in the selected intact classes for the experimental group had either their own computer, phone or can use that of their parents. The problem-solving method was used as the background teaching method for all the three groups. The experimental groups, one was taught using Slack and the other WhatsApp.

The instruments used for the study were the Mathematics Interest Inventory (MII) and Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT). MII had 10 items on mathematics interest with four options of Strongly Agree (SA), agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD); while MAT had twenty (20) multiple item questions with four (4) options in each question. The test questions were set on Quadratic Equation. The instrument had two sections, sections A and B. Section A contained students' information such as number, gender, class and test instructions while section B contained the twenty (20) multiple item questions on mathematics. One (1) mark was awarded for each correct option chosen by students while an incorrect option attracted a score of zero (0). The test was based on a maximum score of twenty (20) and a minimum score of one (0).

The Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was validated by two secondary school teachers of ten years teaching experience and one lecturer from the department of science Education in Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Inland. These experts made the necessary corrections which were incorporated in the final copy of the instrument. The instrument Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was trail-tested to establish its reliability with twenty (20) Mathematics students who were from the population of the study but not part of the sampled schools. The data was collated and analyzed using Kuder-Richardson formula-20, which yielded the reliability coefficient of 0.87

Permission was obtained from principals of the selected school to carry out the research. Students in the first school were taught using problem solving strategy only while students in the other two schools were taught using Slack and WhatsApp social networking tools as teaching resources with problem solving as the base teaching method. The tools were used to transfer materials, assignments and as discussion groups among students during or after class periods.

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The three group of students from the three selected schools were taught for the period of two weeks as prescribed by the scheme of work. After the teaching and learning process, the students were administered with Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT). The test scripts were collected, marked and scored. Data collected from the students were analyzed using adjusted mean, standard deviation and ANCOVA test statistics. All hypothesis were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in the mean interest scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught without?

Table 1: Adjusted Mean Interest Scores and Standard Deviation of Students Taught Quadratic Equations Using Slack, WhatsApp and without Resource

Resources	N	Adjusted Mean	SD
Slack App	44	25.12	3.90
WhatsApp	43	24.46	4.91
Without App	44	21.78	6.64

Table 1, shows that the mean interest scores of students taught using Slack App is 25.12. WhatsApp is 24.46 and those taught without is 21.78. The results indicate that Students taught using Slack had the highest mean interest score, followed by WhatsApp and students taught without resource had the least.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between mean interest scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught using lecture methods in Yenagoa metropolis.

Table 3: ANCOVA Analysis of Interest Scores of Students Taught Quadratic Equations Using Slack, WhatsApp and those taught without Resource

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean square	f	P-value
Covariates	Pre-Interest	973.31	1	973.31	46.64	.00
Main Effects	App Tools	274.97	2	137.49	6.59	.00
Residual		2650.30	127	20.87		
Total		3898.58	130	29.99		

Table 3 shows that the calculated probability value (P-value) of App Tools is .00 which is less than the alpha level of 0.05. Hence, null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there exists significant difference in the mean interest scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught Using lecture methods in yenagoa metropolis.

Table 4: LSD Post hoc Pairwise Comparison Test of Students' Post-Interest Scores Classified by Instructional Resources with Pre-Interest Scores as Covariate

(I) App Tools	(J) App Tools	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. at P < .05
Slack App	WhatsApp	0.66	.99	.50
	Without App	3.34*	.98	.00
WhatsApp	Slack App	-0.66	.99	.50
	Without App	2.68*	.98	.01
Without App	Slack App	-3.34*	.98	.00
	WhatsApp	-2.68*	.98	.01

* = significant at .05 alpha level.

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As shown in table 4, the mean difference of students taught using Slack and WhatsApp is 0.66, Slack and without app is 3.34 while WhatsApp and without app is 2.68. This indicates that Slack App is the most effective in facilitating- students' interest on the mathematics concept they were taught during this research work, followed by WhatsApp while without app is the least. The table reveal a significant mean difference between Slack and without app, and WhatsApp and without app at .05 level of significance.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in the mean performance scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught without?

Table 2: Adjusted Mean Performance Scores and Standard Deviation of Students Taught Quadratic Equations Using Slack, WhatsApp and without Resource

Resources	N	Adjusted Mean	SD
Slack App	44	18.93	3.22
WhatsApp	43	17.88	3.60
Without App	44	15.69	4.41

Table 2, shows that the mean performance scores of students taught using Slack App is 18.93. WhatsApp is 17.88 and those taught without is 15.69. The results indicate that Students taught using Slack had the highest mean performance score, followed by WhatsApp and students taught without resource had the least.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between mean performance scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught using lecture methods in Yenagoa metropolis.

Table 5: ANCOVA Analysis of Performance Scores of Students Taught Quadratic Equations Using Slack, WhatsApp and without Resource

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean square	f	P-value
Covariates	Pre-test	13.43	1	13.43	0.93	.34
Main Effects	App Tools	228.63	2	114.31	7.95	.00
Residual		1826.69	127	14.38		
Total		2068.75	130	15.91		

Table 5 shows that the calculated probability value (P-value) of App Tools is .00 which is less than the alpha level of 0.05. Hence, null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there exists significant difference in the mean performance scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught Using lecture methods in yenagoa metropolis. In order to ascertain the direction of significance the scores are further subjected to the post hoc analysis as shown in table 6.

Table 6: LSD post hoc Pairwise Comparison Test of Students' Post-Interest Scores Classified by Instructional Resources with Pre-Interest Scores as Covariate

(I) App Tools	(J) App Tools	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sign at P < .05
Slack App	WhatsApp	1.05	.82	.20
	Without App	3.24*	.82	.00
WhatsApp	Slack App	-1.05	.82	.20
	Without App	2.19*	.85	.01
Without App	Slack App	-3.24*	.82	.00
	WhatsApp	-2.19*	.85	.01

* = significant at .05 alpha level.

As shown in table 6, the mean difference in the performance of students taught using Slack and WhatsApp is 1.05, Slack and without app is 3.24 while WhatsApp and without app is 2.19. This indicates that Slack App is the most effective in facilitating- students' interest on the mathematics concept they were taught during this research work, followed by WhatsApp

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while without app is the least. The table revealed a significant mean difference between Slack and without app, and WhatsApp and without app at .05 level of significance.

Discussion of Findings

The findings on the mean interest scores of students taught quadratic equations using internet tools (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught without indicated a significant difference. Students taught using Slack and WhatsApp performed significantly better than those taught without app. The finding may have resulted to easy access to facilities and services as well as distant exchanges and collaboration. The tools may have been user-friendly, and promote users' interaction with fellow students and teachers. Instantaneous interactions provision of the tools for answering of question may have generated the interest of students. The study is in line with Bruno and Layer (2020), who investigated the effects of WhatsApp Use on Students' Socio-Emotional Development and Academic Achievement and found that video chatting, online chatting through WhatsApp and frequent use of WhatsApp has effect on students' socio-emotional development and academic achievement. Bruno and Layer (2020) state that the socio-emotional development of students being aroused would make the students become interested in whatever may have resulted to that enhancement. The study also agrees with the statement of Teckchandani (2018), who argued that Slack can be used effectively in the classroom, as students will often find their own way of communicating with each other around an assessment which normally includes a combination of texting, email, and cloud-based services.

The findings on the mean performance scores of students taught quadratic equations using internet tools (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught without indicated a significant difference. The findings reveal that students taught using Slack and WhatsApp performed significantly better than those taught without app. The apps been able to provide students with a lot of collaboration with peers through direct messages and channels may have given the students the opportunity of sharing ideas thereby enhancing their performance. The collaboration which provided students with the opportunity of interaction may have stimulated the ability of different thinking by asking or sharing knowledge in their groups thereby reaching new way of thinking and understanding. The findings of the study are in line with that of Folasayo and Olajide (2022), who examined effects of WhatsApp group learning platform on senior secondary schools' students' learning outcomes in Science, Technology, and Mathematics in Ekiti State, Nigeria and found that there was no significant difference between the performances of mean scores of students exposed to STM through the WhatsApp Group Learning Platform and those exposed to the conventional method

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it could be concluded that Slack and WhatsApp applications significantly aroused students' interest and achievement. The applications effectively brought students far and near through its application in their interactions thereby facilitating the process of teaching and learning of mathematics. The applications also demonstrated the increased flexibility of education that can be promoted through online application where learners would have the potential to access new knowledge and new experience.

Recommendations

1. Internet application tools should be used as teaching resource in the secondary school system by teachers to enable the students interact and improve their logical reasoning on the various mathematics topics.
2. Students using social networking tool for learning mathematics should be appropriately monitored and guided on the proper ways of applying social networking as a learning tool for the purpose of improving upon their academic performance.
3. The government should organize seminars and workshops to educate and inform parent and guardians on the need to purchase a type of phone that can facilitate the use of the internet in order to enhance effective learning of mathematics via the internet.
4. Teachers should endeavour to distribute mathematics assignment through social networking tool (Slack and WhatsApp) to all students after applying problem solving teaching strategy in the classroom.

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Impact of Teachers' Qualification on Performance in Social Studies among Junior Secondary School Students in Jibia Local Government Area, Katsina State

Auwalu Ishiye Ph.D.¹

Email: auwaluishiye@gmail.com

Tel: 08037161731

Bishir Mamman Zango²

Email: bishirzango@yahoo.com

Tel: 08167212847

Bello Muhammad Jamo³

Email: bellomjamo@gmail.com

Tel: 07030608229

¹ Department of Social Studies, School of General Studies Yusufu Bala Usman College Daura, Katsina State, Nigeria

² Department of Primary Education Studies, School of Education Yusufu Bala Usman College Daura Katsina State, Nigeria

³ Department of Social Studies, School of General Studies Yusufu Bala Usman College Daura, Katsina State Nigeria

Abstract

The study examined the Impact of Teachers' Qualification on Performance in Social Studies among Junior Secondary School Students in Jibia Local Government Area of Katsina State, Nigeria. This study employed the descriptive survey research design. Two research questions and hypotheses were formulated in line with the research objectives to guide the study. The population of the study comprised all Social Studies teachers of public Junior Secondary Schools and their students in Jibia Local Government Area of Katsina State. A sample of 47 Social Studies teachers and 100 students were purposively sampled from the two selected junior secondary schools. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire titled: Teachers' Qualification on Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (ITQSAPS). Mean and standard deviation, and the Pearson products moment correlation coefficient statistical tool was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings in the study revealed that teachers with NCE, B. A (Ed)/B. ED, M.Ed. of qualifications has significant impact on students' academic performance in social studies as compared teachers with Diploma, HD, HND, B.A and M.A qualification. Based on the finding, it was recommended that teachers without Education qualifications should obtain PDE and PGDE that will make the qualified to teach the subject.

Keywords: Teachers, Qualification, Students, Academic Performance

Introduction

This study aimed to examine the Impact of Teachers' Qualification on Performance in Social Studies in Jibia Local Government Area of Katsina State, Nigeria. Education is considered as the first step for every human activity as it plays a vital role in the development of human capital as well as individual well-being and opportunities for better living and future. Quality of education is now an issue of global concern as the Nation's attention is increasing focus on the outcomes of education policy makers have undertaken a wide range of reforms to improve schools, qualification ranging from setting new standards to redesigning new curriculum and innovative instructional strategies.

Education is viewed as a process of development that consists the passage of human personality from infancy to maturity by adopting various ways of getting physical, mental emotional as well as social development (Harris, & Sass, 2008). They also stated that, education is considered as a bridge that directs people to better future as well as better development of the country. It is generally accepted that promoting teacher quality is a key element in improving both primary and secondary education in the United States and elsewhere. Olajire (2022) viewed Social Studies as the study of man and his environment. This draws our attention toward understanding the interrelationship between man and his environment. On the other hand, Ajibola (2019) opined that social studies is one of the core subjects incorporated into the 9-Year Basic Education Curriculum as a school subject that teaches moral and values about how man interrelate with physical and social environment effectively for the purpose of inculcating citizenship skills on problem-solving and decision making about critical social issues.

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Furthermore, Ajibola (2019) stated that Social studies is the interdisciplinary integration of social science and humanities from which other subjects emanates such as government, geography, history, civic education and economics as well as sociology, archeology, anthropology, philosophy, psychology, political science and international relations courses studied at higher education levels.

Social studies lend itself more to the application of teaching strategies that are activity-based. This is largely due to the fact that social studies deal with social skills of effective living in society. When facts or skills are learned with relevant learning activities the longer the retention of what is learned and the greater the chances of it being internalized by the learner. However, Okobia (2012) opined that the only school subject which studies man in his readily and capable of addressing the issues of nation building adequately incorporated into social studies. Social Studies is meant to prepare citizens for activity participation in society and help student acquire basic knowledge, positive attitudes, values and social skills needed for responsible citizenship and contributing members of the society. Social Studies as one of the core subject in Junior Secondary Schools is facing attitudinal challenge in the society which take toll on teaching and learning effectiveness of the subject.

Nowadays, the quest for viable ways to improve students' academic performance faced great concern by educators that relies on well-organized constant teacher training programmes (Yakubu, 2023). Christopher & Gary (2018); Yakubu (2023) argued that a principal factor for students' academic success ties up with teacher's academic qualification. This was the opinion of Flipovic (2020); (Yakubu, 2023) that shortage of qualified teachers is responsible for the poor academic achievement observable among the students. However, Nwigwe & Arua (2020); (Yakubu, 2023) opined that teacher's academic qualification is essential toward students' academic achievement.

Furthermore, academic performance has many interpretations among authors. It seen as the aggregate academic scores a student attains at the completion of a particular programme of study assessed by means of evaluation. Goshi (2020); (Yakubu, 2023) viewed academic performance as the skills or knowledge acquired that is assessed by teacher through marks over a specific period of time. In this regard, the goals are evaluated through continuous assessment test and examinations results. Likewise, Ali, Goni & Saleh (2020); (Yakubu, 2023) buttressed that academic performance is a measurable and observable characteristic of a student within a specified period. In addition, academic performance consists of scores obtained by a student in an assessment such as class exercise, class test, mid-term, qualifying examination, and end of term examination. Kiamba & Mutua (2017); (Yakubu, 2023) define academic achievement as the extent to which a student, teacher, or institution achieved the educational goals aligned with standard. For this study, student academic performance simply denote the achievement of an individual obtained through evaluation instruments such as test.

The quality of education in a nation is determined by the quality of her teachers. The most important factor in improving students' achievement is by employing seasoned qualified teachers in all schools (Abe, & Adu, 2013). Bamidele & Adekola (2017) stated that, policy investment on quality of teachers is related to improvement in students' performance. Jacob & John (2020) opined that a teacher's qualification is seen as a teacher's certification. However, this view was emphasized by Gaji (2014) who stated that certification is a measure of teacher qualifications that combines aspects of knowledge on the subject matter about teaching and learning. Rice (2003), viewed teacher certification as the traditional primary gatekeeper machinery for the teaching profession. The author added that the essential requirements for teaching certification vary from one country to another but it should include the completion of an accredited and approved teacher education programme, practice teaching, and a formal recommendation from an institution of higher education. In the Nigerian context, according to the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014), the Nigerian Certificate of Education (NCE) was approved as the minimum qualification for entry into the teaching profession.

Ehrenberg & Brewer (1994), Rice (2003), Ahiauzu & Princewell (2011), Gaji (2014) and opined that a teaching qualification or teacher qualification is one of a number of academic and professional that enables a person to become a registered teacher in primary or secondary school. Such qualifications include, but are not limited to, the Post Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE), the Professional Diploma in Education (PDE), Bachelor of Education (B.Ed), and National Certificate in Education (NCE), Masters, and PhD in Social Studies Education. Academically qualified teachers refer to those who have academic training as a result of enrolment into educational institution and obtained qualifications such as HND, B.Sc, B.A, and M.A and so on; while professionally qualified teachers are those who got professional training that gave them professional knowledge, skills, techniques, aptitudes as different from general education (Akpo, 2012) stated that qualified social studies teachers are those obtained B.Ed., B.Sc. Ed, B.A. Ed, and M.Ed and served for long period.

Teacher qualification in Nigeria indicates main purpose of providing best education that facilitates the possibility and needs of children and youths in general (Elsbree, 2015). Teaching certification in Nigeria is an attempt to guarantee that teachers who teach in schools are qualified to perform their responsibilities that lead to the improvement of students' academic

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performance Cremin & Lawrence, (2013). Gold Haber and Brewer (2007) added that having qualified teachers can be one of the factors that can enhance the students' achievement. They also added that teaching is a profession that requires specialized skills and certification as well as degrees that standardize the specialization of teachers. Teacher qualification in Sub-Sahara African Countries (SSAC) including Nigeria, is taken as a profession needed in teaching profession which is also held to guide a professional teacher to grow knowledge and skills Tylor et al, (2019). They also added that a well-developed knowledge and skills of teachers facilitates teaching profession an opportunity that makes a strong part in key decisions related to the quality-of-service provision which can be done by improving student' academic performance and also develop their own profession related to teaching system. In Nigeria, teacher qualification has a significant impact in determination of school outcomes Adeyemi, (2010).

Empirical studies confirm relationships between qualifications of a teacher and learners' academic achievement. Kasiisa & Tamale (2013) examined the effect of teacher's qualification on the performance of Primary social studies. The purpose of this paper was to determine whether the qualifications of teacher have any impact on the performance of the students in social studies. The cross-sectional survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of all primary school pupils in Eastern Uganda and the sample for the study consisted of 128 Upper Basic Primary Schools social studies teachers. The years' mock results of the pupils in the schools were rated and correlated with the bio-data of their respective social studies teachers as instrument for data collection. The data were analyzed using inferential statistics to test null hypothesis at 0.05 significance level. Findings revealed that students taught by teachers with higher academic qualifications performed significantly better than those taught by teachers with lower academic qualifications. The authors concluded that there is significant relationship between teachers' qualifications and pupils' academic performance in the primary schools in eastern Uganda. Based on the findings, it was recommended that experienced teachers with professional qualifications should teach Social Studies. Therefore, the previous paper is on students' academic performance in basic science students' academic achievement and the present study is on students' academic performance in social studies. Thus, this finding agrees with the finding in the present paper.

Adekola & Bamidele (2017) examined the effects of Teacher's and teaching experience on Junior Secondary School (JSS) students' achievement in Basic Science. The survey type of research design was adopted in the study. The population of the study comprised of all the Junior Secondary School Students and the sample consisted of 455 JSS II students from 15 public schools randomly selected through multi-stage sampling technique in Ibarapa region of Oyo State. Teacher's qualification and teaching experience were used as criteria for selection of Basic science teachers. Three hypotheses were formulated and tested using t-test statistic at $p < 0.5$. the authors found that there was significant difference in the achievement of students taught by teachers with higher academic qualifications and their mates taught by teachers with low qualification levels, between students taught by trained teachers and students taught by untrained teachers and between students taught by long time experienced teachers and short time experience teachers. Based on the findings, it was recommended that only trained and high qualification teachers should be allowed to teach Basic science JSS III classes. While NCE holders should be allowed to undergo further studies as in-service. Likewise, teachers without teaching qualification should be advice to pursue their Post Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE). This could along way improve their teaching career and to improve the students' academic achievement in Basic Science. Even though, the previous paper is on students' academic performance in basic science students' academic achievement and the present study is on students' academic performance in social studies. Thus, this finding coincides with the finding in the present study.

Adadu & Agbo-Egwu (2017) investigates the effect of teacher's teaching experience on the academic performance of secondary school students in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) in the three senatorial zones of Benue State, Nigeria. The study employed descriptive research design. The population of the study comprised of all senior secondary schools students. A sample of 300 students and teachers randomly drawn from 150 secondary schools, 50 schools from each senatorial district through simple random sampling technique. Data collection was made using an inventory schedule. 300 questionnaires were administered. The responses gathered were analyzed using content analysis. Findings reveal that teachers' teaching experience significantly influenced students' academic performance in SSCE examinations and as observed on the respondents. Thus, the previous finding corroborated with the result in the present study that teachers' teaching experience significantly influenced students' academic performance in SSCE examinations.

Bolarinwa & Kolawole et al. (2020) examined the influence of teachers' teaching experience and educational qualification on academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The purpose of the research is to find out the relationship between teachers' teaching experience, educational qualification and academic performance of students in public secondary schools. The descriptive research of the survey type was employed for the study.

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The study revealed that there was significant relationship between teachers' teaching experience, educational qualification and academic performance of students. The study had shown that teaching experience and educational qualification had influence on academic performance of students. Hence, the previous paper is on students' academic performance in basic science students' academic achievement and the present study is on students' academic performance in social studies. Thus, this finding supports with the finding in the present study.

Bimbola & Daniel (2021) investigated the influence of teachers' qualification and experience on students' academic performance in basic science in junior secondary schools in Nigeria. The study employed a descriptive survey type of research. Simple random sampling was used to select 8 Junior Secondary Schools in Ogun East Senatorial District of Ogun State. Sample for the study consist of 18 basic science teachers and 540 junior secondary school students. The data were collected using a questionnaire and basic science achievement test. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, one-way analysis of variance and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation. The findings in this study revealed that most of the basic science teachers at the JSS level were not trained as basic science teachers, teachers' qualifications influenced students' academic performance in basic science but basic science teachers' years of teaching experience did not have a positive correlation with students' academic performance in basic science. Therefore, the previous paper is on students' academic performance in basic science students' academic achievement while the present paper is on students' academic performance in social studies that varied in subject area and scope. Thus, the previous finding disagrees with the result in the present study which says teachers' years of teaching experience has no positive correlation with students' academic performance in basic science.

Lawal (2021) examines the effects of teachers' academic qualification and experience on students' achievement and interest in Accounting. The population for the study comprised of all NCE students of FCE Zaria. While the sample consisted of 201 NCE II, Business Education Department, Federal College of Education, Zaria and 10 Accounting lecturers in the Department. 140 students of NCE II in Business Education Department and 7 Accounting lecturers selected using random simple sampling technique. Two research hypotheses guided the study, the research hypotheses were tested using regression analysis and ANOVA. Findings from the study revealed that lecturers' academic qualification and teaching experience made significant effects on students' achievement in Accounting. The previous study similar with the present study by differs in terms of subject area, students' level of education and geographical scope. However, the previous finding agrees with the result in the present study which revealed that lecturers' academic qualification and teaching experience made significant effects on students' achievement in Accounting.

Social study is a core subject in taught to students at junior secondary school level, which focus on the society and environment. It is designed to sharpen the students' creative potentials in terms of awareness and problem solving adequately to live worthwhile. According to Agyeman (2003); Jeffery (2019) a teacher who does not have both academic and professional qualification would have a negative influence on teaching and learning of his/her subject which subsequently affects the performance of students. Olobobou (2011) reported that most unqualified social studies teachers concentrate on the low level of cognitive domain neglecting the affective and psychomotor learning domains. Hence, this situation is reflected in The Junior Secondary Certificate Examination (JSCE) result. The finding of Kadiri (2008) revealed that learners display ignorance and lack of mastery of content areas in social studies and this seriously affect their future growth and development. Therefore, the problem which this study intends to solve: what then is the impact of teachers' qualification on Social studies students' academic performance in Jibia LGA of Katsina State?

Objectives of the study

1. Determine the impact of teachers' academic qualifications on students' academic performance in social studies at Junior Secondary Schools?
2. Find out the impact of teachers' years of experience on students' academic performance in social studies at Junior Secondary Schools?

Research Questions

1. What is the impact of teachers' academic qualifications on students' academic performance in social studies at Junior Secondary Schools?
2. What is the impact of teachers' years of experience on students' academic performance in social studies at Junior Secondary Schools?

Hypotheses

1. H_{01} There is no significant relationship between teachers' academic qualifications on students' academic performance in social studies at Junior Secondary Schools.

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2. H₀₂ There is no significant relationship between teachers' years of experience on students' academic performance in social studies at Junior Secondary Schools.

Methodology

The research design for this study is descriptive survey and ex-post factor. An ex-post factor research seeks to find out facts that are associated with certain occurrences, outcomes, conditions or types of behaviours by undertaking the analysis of past events and already existing conditions. In this study, the researchers have no control over the variables neither could they apply any form of treatment to the group because they already exist. Therefore, the study analyzed the 2022/2023 end of third term Social studies examination result of JSS II students in order to determine the impact of teachers' qualification on the performance of students in social studies in Junior Secondary Schools in Jibia Local Government Area of Katsina state. The population of the study included all the ninety-four (94) Social Studies teachers and 848 students' offering Social Studies in the two Junior Secondary Schools (GDJSS Jibia and GDJSS Natsinta) in Kaduna state. A simple random sampling technique was used to select one hundred (100) students offering Social Studies as a subject from two intact classes of Government Day Junior Secondary School (GDJSS) Jibia and Government Day Junior Secondary School (GDJSS) Natsina (i.e. 50 students from each school) and forty seven (47) Social Studies teachers.

The instruments used for the study were a questionnaire titled Impact of Teachers' Qualification on Students' Academic Performance (ITQSAPS). It contained two sections. Section A elicited information on the Bio-data of teachers. Section B elicited information on the teachers' qualification and years of experience. Other relevant data such as students' test scores obtained from their previous end of term examinations were analyzed. Split-half Test- method was used to establish the reliability index of the instrument. A reliability coefficient of 0.74 using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) with the help of SPSS. The r-value of 0.74 indicates a consistent reliability index for the instruments.

Results

The purpose of this study is to analyze how teachers' qualification affect students learning outcome in social studies. The independent variable is teachers' qualification and the dependent variable is the students' academic performance.

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1: Distribution of the respondents by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	35	74.5	74.5	74.5
Female	12	25.5	25.5	100.0
Total	47	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field survey, 2023

From the survey, the author computed the percentage of male and female social studies teachers who responded. The result in table 1 shows that 35 with 74.5% of the respondents were male, while 12 with 25.5% were female teachers.

Table 2: Distribution of the respondents by Academic Qualifications

Qualification	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid NCE	14	29.8	29.8	29.8
Diploma/Education	8	17.0	17.0	46.8
Diploma	3	6.4	6.4	53.2
HND/PGDE	5	10.6	10.6	63.8
HND	5	10.6	10.6	74.5
B.A(Ed)/B.ED	8	17.0	17.0	91.5
M.Ed	4	8.5	8.5	100.0
Total	47	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field survey, 2023

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The academic qualifications of the respondents are shown in table 2. From the table, 29.8% of the respondents were NCE holders, 17% Diploma/Education, 6% Diploma, 10% HND/PGDE, 10% HND, 17% B.A(Ed)/B.ED and 8% M.Ed have qualifications.

Respondent's Years of Experience

The years of the responders in the questionnaire are shown in table 4.3. The respondents comprise students and lecturers of the various Colleges of Education in the northeast.

Table 3: Distribution of the respondents by years of experience

Years of Experience	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-10 Years	27	57.4	57.4
	11-20 Years	13	27.7	85.1
	21-30 Years	4	8.5	93.6
	Above 30 Years	3	6.4	100.0
	Total	47	100.0	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2023

The years of experience of the respondents is shown in table 3. The table shows 27 of the respondents constituting 57.4% falls within 1-10 years of teaching experience, 13 representing 27.7% falls within 11-20 years, 4 representing 8.5% falls within 21-30 years and only 3 of the respondents constituting 6.4% above 30 years. The total percentage adds up to 100%.

Research Question 1

What is the impact of teachers' academic qualifications on students' academic performance in social studies at Junior Secondary Schools?

Table 4: Descriptive statistics on the relationship between teachers' qualification and students' academic performance in Social Studies

S/N	Statement	N	M	SD	Decision
1	There can never be good students' performance without quality staff	47	3.40	1.04	Agreed
2	The teaching process helps to recollect or unfold knowledge	47	3.72	0.62	Agreed
3	Meaningful praise gets and keep students actively participating in the learning process	47	3.68	0.66	Agreed
4	social studies teachers must show interest in their students	47	3.28	1.08	Agreed
5	When students have not learned, then the teacher has not taught	47	3.15	1.06	Agreed
6	A teacher must be a master of his subject	47	3.64	0.76	Agreed
7	Qualified social studies teachers will know how best to handle students and draw out their intellectual resources	47	3.13	1.19	Agreed
8	The quality of a teacher's training makes or mars the end product of his job as a teacher.	47	3.28	1.08	Agreed
9	social studies teachers with higher certifications receive higher ratings and students' performance than those with less certifications	47	3.36	0.97	Agreed
10	Fully prepared and certified social studies teachers are more successful with students than social studies teachers without this preparation	47	3.19	1.19	Agreed
11	Formal qualification of social studies teachers is an important indicator for their knowledge and competence in teaching	47	3.06	1.07	Agreed
Overall Mean			3.35	0.97	

Source: Field survey, 2023

The result in table 4 above revealed that the mean scores ranged from M=3.06, SD=1.07 and M=3.72, SD=0.62 with overall mean score of M=3.35, SD0.97 agreed decision from the respondents that the items on listed under the research question; the effect of teachers' academic qualifications on students' academic performance in Social Studies taught at Junior Secondary School levels of Jibia LGA, Katsina State. Therefore, the individual mean scores are more than the average mean of 2.50 based on the criteria of acceptance or rejection. It can be inferred that the respondents of items 1 to 11 have accepted that teachers' qualification has positive impact on Junior Secondary School student's academic performance in social studies.

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Research Question 2

What is the impact of teachers' years of experience on students' academic performance in social studies at Junior Secondary Schools?

Table 5: Descriptive statistics on the impact of teachers' years of experience on students' academic performance in Social Studies

S/N	Statement	N	M	SD	Decision
12	The teacher possesses all knowledge and information which students do not possess due to years of teaching experience	47	3.51	0.98	Agreed
13	The teacher formulates teaching tasks by his own experiences and insight	47	3.28	1.04	Agreed
14	Mastery of subject matter is accomplished through years of experience	47	3.28	1.12	Agreed
15	Students taught by more experienced social studies teachers achieve at a higher level	47	3.32	1.00	Agreed
Overall Mean			3.35	1.03	

Source: Field survey, 2023

The result in table 4 above revealed that the mean scores ranged from M=3.28, SD=1.04 and M=3.51, SD=0.98 with overall mean score of M=3.35, SD1.03 agreed decision from the respondents that the items on listed under the research question; the effect of teachers' academic qualifications on students' academic performance in social studies. Thus, the individual mean scores are more than the average mean of 2.50 based on the criteria of acceptance or rejection. It can be inferred that the respondents on items 12 to 15 have accepted that teachers' years of teaching experience has positive impact on Junior Secondary School student's academic performance in social studies in Jibia Local Government Area of Katsina state.

Hypothesis testing

The hypotheses were stated in the null form while the results are analyzed using the Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between teachers' academic qualifications on students' academic performance in social studies at Junior Secondary Schools.

Table 6: Pearson product moment correlation coefficient analysis of the relationship between teachers' academic qualifications on students' academic performance in social studies. N=200

Variable	N	M	SD	R	P value	Decision
Teachers' Qualification	100	36.190	2.048	.818*	.470	Significant
Students' Academic Performance	100	35.890	2.141			

*. p < 0.05 level (2-tailed), df = 46, critical .035

The result in table 6 revealed that the calculated R-value of .818 was greater than the p value of .470 at 198 degree of freedom. This signifies that there is a significant relationship between teachers' academic qualifications and students' academic performance. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis retained.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between teachers' years of experience on students' academic performance in social studies at Junior Secondary Schools.

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Table 7: Pearson product moment correlation coefficient analysis of the relationship between teachers' years of experience on students' academic performance in social studies at Junior Secondary Schools. N=200

Variable	N	M	SD	R	P value	Decision
Teachers' Years of Experience	47	27.220	4.368	.869*	-.067	Significant
Students' Academic Performance	47	26.690	3.109			

*. $p < 0.05$ level (2-tailed), $df = 46$, critical .321

The result in table 7 showed that the calculated r-value of .869* was greater than the p value of -.067* at 198 degree of freedom. This indicated that there is a significant relationship between between teachers' years of experience and students' academic performance in social studies. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis retained.

Discussion of findings

The result of finding from hypothesis 1 showed a significant relationship between lecturers with environmental education qualifications and students' academic performance. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Kasiisa & Tamale (2013), Adekola & Bamidele (2017), Adadu & Agbo-Egwu (2017) and Bolarinwa & Kolawole et al. (2020). Bimbola & Daniel (2021) and Lawal (2021) who found that students taught by teachers with higher academic qualifications with longtime experience performed significantly better than those taught by teachers with lower academic qualifications and short time experience. The result also corroborated the finding of Bimbola & Daniel (2021) and Lawal (2021) who found that there is a significant relationship between teacher qualification and social studies students' academic performance at the secondary school education levels in Nigeria. The authors found out that there was a significant difference in the performance of junior secondary school social studies students taught by teachers with high academic qualifications compared to those taught by teachers with low academic qualifications.

The result of the analysis from hypothesis 2 revealed that there is no significant relationship between teachers' years of experience and students' academic performance. This study is in line with Bimbola & Daniel (2021) and Lawal (2021) who found that students taught by teachers with higher academic qualifications with longtime experience performed significantly better than those taught by teachers with lower academic qualifications and short time experience. However, the disagrees with the finding of Bimbola & Daniel (2021) who found that teachers' years of teaching experience did not have a positive correlation with students' academic performance in basic science. Conversely, the study disagrees with the finding of Bimbola & Daniel (2021) who found that teachers' years of experience have no statistical relationship with students' academic performance in social studies.

Conclusion

The study was carried out to examine the impact of teachers' qualification on students' academic performance in social studies. Based on the finding of the study, it was concluded that teachers' qualifications and years of teaching experience has a significant impact of on students' academic performance in social studies. This implies that social studies can only be taught effectively by a professionally trained teachers (NCE, B.A (Ed), B.ED and M.Ed), who had acquired pedagogical skills in teaching in social studies toward realization of educational objectives. Furthermore, competent teachers of social studies teach for skill-based education that facilitates students understanding of social studies concepts, creativity, and problem-solving skills, awareness of issues related to physical and social environment.

Recommendations

The Following recommendations were made based on the findings of the research:

1. Federal, State and Local Government should ensure that experienced teachers with higher professional qualifications are qualified teach Social Studies in Junior Secondary Schools.
2. Unqualified Social Studies teachers should be given training, seminars and workshops which will help them to get knowledge, idea, facts in Social Studies, this will improve students' academic performance in Social Studies education.
3. Teachers should be encouraged to participate in pedagogically-oriented and content-oriented professional development activities to improve the quality of their teaching and consequently the academic performance of their students in test and examination.
4. Teachers should be encouraged to constantly seek to update their knowledge and skills through workshops, seminars and conferences. This will keep them updated on the current trend in Social Studies Education

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Impact of Thinking Map and Role-Play Instructional Strategies on Performance in Basic Science among Students in Makurdi, Benue State

* **Tartenger Timothy Terungwa**¹

Email: tartengertimothy@gmail.com

Tel: 07067699177

Omaga, Joy Okache¹

Email: joyokache@yahoo.co.uk

Tel: 08033674749

Enemariae Veronica¹

Email: veraenemarie7@gmail.com

Tel: 08036181533

¹Science and Mathematics Education, Benue State University, Makurdi

Abstract

The study investigated the Impact of Thinking map and Role- play Instructional Strategies on Performance in Basic Science among Students in Makurdi, Benue State. The study adopted quasi-experimental research design specifically pre-test and post-test non –equivalent, non-randomized control group design. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significant level. The population for the study consists of 1,886 upper basic II students from 27 UBE junior secondary schools located in Makurdi metropolis. Purposive and simple random sampling techniques were used to draw 60 students in two intact classes from two schools for the study. The research instrument used for data collection is called Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT) instrument. The instrument was validated by three experts and the reliability coefficient of the instrument was determined using Kuder- Richardson formula $20(K-R_{20})$ which yielded 0.80. The data collected were analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation to answer the research questions and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the null hypotheses. The findings revealed that: there was no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores $[F(1,26) = 0.104; p = 0.750 > 0.05]$ of male and female students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy. The second finding revealed that there was no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores $[F(1,28) = 2.623; p = 0.117 > 0.05]$ of male and female students exposed to Basic Science using Role play instructional strategies. It was recommended among others that Basic science teachers should employ thinking maps and role play instructional strategies when teaching basic science.

Key words: thinking maps, role play, academic performance and gender.

Introduction

The technological advancement of a nation depends on the level of scientific and technological knowledge of the citizenry where education remains a veritable tool for this attainment and that formed the decision of the federal government to introduce Basic Science at the upper basic level to exposes young learners to the world of science. Basic science is considered the bedrock of all science subjects. It is the subject that prepares students at the upper basic level for the study of core science subjects like Biology, Physics and Chemistry (Ode & Eriba, 2019). The overall objectives of Basic Science curriculum as stated in Nigeria Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC, 2012) is to enable the learners: develop interest in science and technology; acquire basic knowledge in science and technology; apply scientific and technological knowledge and skills to meet contemporary societal needs, take advantage of the numerous career opportunities provided by science and technology; become prepared for further studies in science and technology among others. In spite of the importance attached to the Basic Science it has observed that the performance of students over the years is low and inconsistent (BECE, 2021).

Performance is the observable or measurable behaviour of a person or an animal in a particular situation usually in an experimental situation Yusuf as cited in Ada, Eriba and Toryem (2020). Students' low performance is generally blamed on poor teaching strategies or methods (Ode, Akpoghol & Otor 2020). Jiya (2011) argued that when teaching is characterized by

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rote learning, meaningless memorization or verbalism, students learn ineffectively. One among the most striking challenges in BS is that, there has been low and inconsistent students' performance in the results of external examinations in the subject as evident at Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) over the years. Report from Benue State Examination Board (BECE, 2021) shows a mean failure of 46.61% and 49.30% in the year 2016 and 2017 respectively. However, in the year 2018, 2019 and 2020 the result showed an increased average score of 54.96%, 63.87% and 59.90% respectively with an inconsistent fluctuation trend. Prominent among the contributing factors responsible for low and inconsistent performance in Basic Science is the predominant use of teacher- centered teaching methods and traditional subject based methods, which in recent times became ineffective (Ode, Akpoghol & Otor 2020).

Effective utilization of appropriate and student-centered teaching strategies like Thinking Maps (TM) and Role Play (RP) may help to improve students' performance in Basic Science. To motivate students, the teacher needs to make science real and relevant by using teaching strategies that will enable students learn Basic Science easily and effectively. Thinking Maps according to Hyerle (2009) is a set of explicit visual representations of thinking processes which fosters life-long learning in students. To DeLorenzo (2011), Thinking Maps provide visual support for the mental processes of diverse learners. The graphic patterns are connected to the cognitive skills whereby they can stimulate how thinking is developed.

TMs has also been reported as a "useful tool for helping younger students with the process of building conceptual understandings of disciplinary content and, consequently, promoting their achievement" Abi-Ei-Mona and Adb-Ei Khalick as cited in (Ruba & Alaeddin, 2017). TMs therefore if effectively used in Basic Science lessons could positively affect students' performance and promote higher order thinking and helps students become independent long-life learners. TMs also allow students to be more involved in the learning process, "as it forces and encourages them to map out their thought process on paper, which leads to an increase in connections between content and experience (Long & Carlson, 2011)".

Empirically, Alabdulaziz and Alhammadi (2021) who conducted research on the effectiveness of thinking map to improve students' achievement in mathematics observed a significant difference in the mean scores of male and female students exposed to thinking maps strategy and those taught using conventional method. Also, Ugbeda (2021) conducted research on the effect of think-pair cooperative learning strategy on secondary school students' achievement and retention in electrochemical in Makurdi metropolis and found that students taught using think-pair cooperative learning strategy achieved higher and retained better than those taught using conventional method and the female outperformed their male counterparts. Role-playing as explained by Rao and Stupans (2012) is the practice of having students take on specific roles and act them out in a case – based scenario for the purpose of learning course content or understanding complex concepts.

Role-Play has been touted as a tool better suited for the needs of today's college students than more traditional teaching methods. According to Maier in Puyate (2017), Role-Play pedagogy has been shown to be effective in reaching learning outcomes in three major learning domains such as affective, cognitive and psychomotor. Westrup and Planander (2013), were of the opinion that by making students take on the role of another person, they practice empathy and perspective taking. This could lead to more self-reflection and awareness on the part of students. Empirically, Zhu (2012) found that role play improves both male and female learners' performance and generally helps students understand what they have learnt in an easy way. Moreso, Sadeghi and Sharifi, 2013, Nair, Yusof and Arumugam, 2014; Aldillah, 2015 and Altun, 2015 in their separate research found that role-play activities can provide a stress-free learning environment where students enjoy the learning process. The findings also showed that role play activities enable students to gain self-confidence and enhance performance.

Puyate and Eniekenemi (2017), investigated the effects of Role-Playing Teaching Strategy and Its effect on academic achievement of students in learning simple blue print reading. The findings from the study revealed that experimental group taught simple blue print reading with role play teaching method performed better than those taught with the lecture method and that there is no significant difference in academic achievement between male and female students taught simple blue print readings using role play teaching method. Gender is another variable that could influence performance. According to Ugwu (2015), gender is regarded as the sex of mentee which is also referred to as the stratification of male and female offering subjects in schools. Given the low and inconsistent academic performance of students, Jack and Japheth ascited in (Jesulowo, Lawal, Bichi, Lawal & Mari 2021) observed that many students' especially female students become less confident in their academic skills and career. According to the authors, poor

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academic performance of students may also be attributed to factors such as truancy from schools, poverty, economic issues, and teachers' inappropriate use of instructional strategies among others.

Research findings on gender difference in Basic Science students' achievement/performance are few. Moreover, the results of the few available ones are not consistent. For instance, Ode, Agbike, Abah, and Chia (2019) study revealed that there was no significant difference in the achievement of male and female Basic Science students in BECE, Oludipe and Oludipe (2018) found no significant difference, Oludipe (2012) also found that there is no statistical difference in academic achievement of students in respect to gender. On the other hand, Ada, Eriba and Toryem (2020) found that, male outperformed their female counterparts taught with simulation in Biology and Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM). Moreso, Akaayar (2017) and Ode (2018) found a significant difference between the academic achievement of male and female Basic Science students in their separate studies. The inconsistency of these findings suggests that research on the influence of gender on students' performance in Basic Science and science in general is inconclusive. This implies that more research is needed in this direction and area of study which this study intends to find the effectiveness of TMs and RP with regards to gender.

Objective of the Study

The following objectives were stated for the study:

1. Examine the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy.
2. Determine the mean academic performance scores of male and female students when taught Basic Science using Role Play Academic instructional strategy.

Research Questions

1. What is the difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy?
2. What is the difference in mean the academic performance scores of male and female students' taught Basic Science using Role Play instructional strategy?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy and those taught using Role Play instructional strategy.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy and those taught using Role Play instructional strategy.

Methodology

This study adopted the quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pre-test and post-test non –equivalent, non-randomized control design. The choice of this design was due to the fact that, this study used the intact classes so as not to distort the normal academic programmes of the schools involved, due to randomization of subjects to experiment groups. The appropriateness of quasi experimental design for this study was considered on this ground. (Emaikwu, 2012). A population of 1886 students was drawn from all the 27 UBE junior secondary schools located within Makurdi town (Benue State Universal Basic Education Board, 2021). Purposive and simple random sampling technique were used to select two schools for the study. Two intact classes were used for the study with a sample size of 60 Upper-Basic II students from the two schools selected for the study. The selection of intact classes was done using hat and draw method. One intact class each from the two schools was assigned randomly to experimental group one and the second intact class was assigned to experimental group two using thinking map and role play instructional strategies respectively and a psychometric test was carried on forty items in which thirty were accepted and ten were rejected.

The Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT), a 30 multiple choice questions with four options was used for data collection. Pre- test was administered before treatment; post-test was then administered after reshuffling in order to avoid familiarity immediately after treatment was given. The items were delimited to concepts of energy, work, power and energy transformation when work is done. BSPT's section "A" collected students' bio data; while section 'B' generated data on students' academic performance in Basic Science. The instrument was validated by three experts: of the three experts, two were

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science educators, while the third one is an expert in test and measurement, all from Benue State University, Makurdi. Their inputs were used to improve the quality of the instrument.

The instrument was trial tested using 40 Upper-Basic II students from two schools that were not part of the actual study but had similar characteristics. To determine the reliability coefficient of BSPT, Kuder Richardson formula (K-R₂₀) was used and yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.80. The instrument was administered by research assistants' understand standard examination conditions using BSPT and the data was obtained. The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using ANCOVA. The choice of ANCOVA was to remove the initial difference between groups since intact classes were used. The decision rule in the null hypotheses was that if the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis will be rejected, but if the p-value is not less than 0.05 the null hypothesis is not rejected.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in the mean Academic performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Academic Performance Scores of Male and Female students taught BS using TMs Instructional Strategy.

S/No	Gender TMs	Pre –test		Post-test		Mean gain	Decision
		Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev		
1	Male	9.21	2.485	14.32	5.323	5.11	In favour of female students
2	Female	9.00	2.789	15.00	4.784	6.00	
3		Mean difference				0.89	

(Source: Field work, 2023)

The data in Table 1 shows the difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy. Data in the table also reveals that the mean gain of male students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy is 5.11 and those of female students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy is 6.00. The difference in the mean Academic performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy is 0.89 in favour of female students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in mean Academic performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using Role Play instructional strategy?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Academic Performance Scores of Male and Female Students' taught BS using RP Instructional Strategy

S/NO	Gender RP	Pre –test		Post-test		Mean gain	Decision
		Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev		
1	Male	9.20	2.821	12.70	4.644	3.5	In favour of female students
2	Female	9.19	2.542	15.76	4.929	6.57	
3		Mean difference				3.07	

(Source: Field work, 2023)

The data in Table 2 shows the difference in the mean Academic performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using Role Play instructional strategy. Data in the table further reveals the mean gain of male students taught Basic Science using Role Play instructional strategy is to be 3.50 and those of female students taught Basic Science using Role Play instructional strategy is 6.57 The difference in the mean Academic performance scores of male and female students taught

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Basic Science using Role Play instructional strategy is 3.07 in favour of female students taught Basic Science using Role Play instructional strategy.

Hypotheses 1

There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students exposed to Thinking Maps instructional strategy.

Table 3: ANCOVA of Academic Performance Scores of Male and Female Students exposed to Thinking Maps Instructional Strategy

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Decision
Corrected Model	5.563 ^a	2	2.781	.101	.904	.008	Not significant
Intercept	498.841	1	498.841	18.175	.000	.411	
Pretest	2.496	1	2.496	.091	.765	.003	
Gender	2.845	1	2.845	.104	.750	.004	
Error	713.610	26	27.447				
Total	6860.000	29					
Corrected Total	719.172	28					

a. R Squared = .008 (Adjusted R Squared = -.069)

(Source: Field work, 2023)

The data in Table 3 reveals that $F(1,26) = 0.104$; $p = 0.750 > 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis which state that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students exposed to Thinking Maps instructional strategy is retained. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students exposed to Thinking Maps instructional strategy. The partial Eta square of 0.004 was obtained for gender meaning that only 0.4% of the Basic Science performance scores can be accounted for the influence of gender in Basic Science class when taught using thinking maps strategy.

Hypotheses 2

There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students exposed to Role Play instructional strategy.

Table 4: ANCOVA of Academic Performance Scores of Male and Female Students exposed to Role Play Instructional Strategy

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Decision
Corrected Model	66.019 ^a	2	33.009	1.364	.272	.089	Not sig.
Intercept	508.466	1	508.466	21.017	.000	.429	
Pretest	2.509	1	2.509	.104	.750	.004	
Gender	63.465	1	63.465	2.623	.117	.086	
Error	677.401	28	24.193				
Total	7510.000	31					
Corrected Total	743.419	30					

a. R Squared = .089 (Adjusted R Squared = .024)

(Source: Field work, 2023)

The data in Table 4 reveals that $F(1,28) = 2.623$; $p = 0.117 > 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis state that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students exposed to Role Play instructional strategy is retained. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students exposed to Role Play instructional strategy. The partial Eta square of 0.086 was obtained for gender meaning that only 8.6% of the Basic Science performance scores can be accounted for the influence of gender in Basic Science class when taught using role play strategy.

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Discussion of Findings

Finding from hypothesis one showed that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students exposed to Thinking Maps instructional strategy. This implies that both male and female students performed high when exposed to thinking maps strategy. This finding agrees with Ode, Agbike, Abah, and Chia (2019) study which revealed that there was no significant difference in the achievement of male and female Basic Science students in BECE. Abuh, (2021) also found that there is no significant difference in mean academic performance among male and female students taught thermal physics using cognitive conflict instructional strategy which is also an innovative strategy. This finding may be possible because thinking maps strategy provide equal opportunities to both male and female students as it has been reported to be a useful tool for helping students with the process of building conceptual understanding of disciplinary content and consequently, promoting their performance which made it possible for both male and female to attained high performance. Male and female students are free to share their ideas (thinking) between themselves. However, the finding disagreed with the findings by Akaayar (2017), Ode (2018) and Alabdulaziz and Alhammadi (2021) who found a significant difference between the academic achievement of male and female basic science students in their separate studies. Ode et al (2019) who found that there is a significant difference in academic achievement of male and female basic science students in Basic Examination Certificate Examination with male students recording higher mean scores than their female counterparts. The finding also revealed that gender has no effect on BS students' academic performance when thinking maps strategy is used.

The finding from hypothesis two indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students exposed to Role Play instructional strategy. This implies that the performance of both male and female students exposed to role play strategy is enhanced. This agrees with Zhu (2012) who found that role play improve learners' performance and generally helps students understand what they have learnt in an easy way. Oludipe (2012) also found that there is no statistical difference in academic achievement of students in respect to gender when exposed to RP. More so, Abah and Chia (2019) study also revealed that there was no significant difference in the achievement of male and female Basic Science students in BECE result. This high and gender free performance could be a result of the involvement of students' active participation in the class as every student's is given an opportunity to make their contribution during group discussions, the intelligent and even the slow learners. Conversely however, this finding disagreed with the findings of Akaayar (2017) and Ode (2018) who found a significant difference between the academic achievement of male and female Basic Science students in their separate studies, Aguele and Uhumniah in Agbidye (2019) also found that the male students achieved higher than the female in science.

Conclusion

The study established that the use of Thinking Maps and Role Play Instructional Strategies enhanced both male and female students' academic performance.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Basic science teachers should employ Thinking Maps and Role Play instructional strategies in their classroom when teaching Basic Science as the strategies provides opportunities for students to share ideas and understanding.
2. In- service training, seminars and workshops should be organized by the State and Federal Ministries of Education to train Basic Science teachers on how to use Thinking Maps and Role Play instructional strategies in teaching the subject.

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Influence of Politics in Education on Effective Posting of Teachers in Government Secondary Schools in Kebbi State, Nigeria

Haliru, Abubakar¹

Email: abubakar.haliru@fulokoja.edu.ng

Tel: 08034383973

Garba, Abdulhamid Illo²

Email: agarbaillo85@gmail.com

Tel: 08063362217

¹Department of Educational Foundation, Federal University Lokoja

² Department of Science Education, Kebbi State University of Science and Technology Aliero

Abstract

The study x-rays titled Influence of Politics in Education on effective Posting of Teachers in Government Secondary Schools in Kebbi State, with a single objective to guide the study, how does influence of politics in education affect effective posting of teachers in secondary schools in Kebbi State? A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population is of the study is 5177 which consist of all government secondary school stakeholders in Kebbi State during the 2022/2023 academic session, and sample of 360 was choose which falls within the range of 5000, recommended by Research Advisor 2006 and a purposive sampling technique was used to select 30% out of the six educational zones in Kebbi State. Simple random sampling was used to select 9 schools. Data was collected using the instrument title IPEETPGSS questionnaire and analyzed using statistical tools of frequency counts, percentages, mean scores, and tables. Subsequently, inferential statistics such as one-way analysis of variance was used to test the hypotheses for the study; findings from the survey study revealed that there is influence of politics in education on effective teachers' posting in government secondary schools in Kebbi State. The paper concluded that posting and transfer of teachers should be exclusively left in the hands of the supervisory agencies of government, who are saddled with such responsibility.

Keywords: Influence, Politics, Posting, Teachers, Secondary School

Introduction

Education is usually faced with avoidable challenges from the political point of view, especially in administration. It is so because the political appointees typically determine what type of management should be used for the system Muhammad (2013). They also support the components of the educational system and how it operates. For instance, the essential concepts of socialism as a political theory were about the capitalist system's widespread exploitation of the working class. Socialism is a political concept that acknowledges property as the cornerstone of the state's economic structure, which concentrates power in the hands of the people that possess property Osuji (2011). In a society where the owners of the means of production do not have to work, and the means of production are nationalized, workers have no property Muhammad (2013). Only educational reforms will be able to modify such a societal structure Muhammad (2013). The citizenry would be trained by the state, for the state, and at state institutions under a governmental mechanism with complete control over curriculum and instruction Haliru (2018). In these situations, the state authorities frequently set the curriculum's specifics, including residents' functional training Dada (2008). May include scientific training for social application may be included in the curriculum.

Mexico, Bulgaria, and Cuba are excellent examples of nations that have enacted a socialist education system Osuji (2011). The state's monopoly over education, secularism, physical and military training, political indoctrination inside and outside the classroom, and a greater emphasis on science topics are all shared characteristics of their educational system. Individual freedom and the concept of tolerance are not tolerated in these states. In contrast to these nations, France has a centralized educational approach based on its political philosophy. In France, the metropole, or central government, is in charge of all matters about education Osuji (2011). In the cases of the USA and Japan, the political ideologies of capitalism and democracy, respectively, are frequently incorporated into their highly decentralized educational systems Muhammad (2013). The national character and the national educational system are very closely related. For instance, the USA has a democratic national identity, and as a result, most components of its educational system are democratic Muhammad (2013). The political

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philosophy of nationalism has an impact on a nation's educational system as well. A group's psychological belief that they share a common viewpoint and customs based on a shared heritage is known as nationalism. These shared ancestries span racial, linguistic, religious, and geographic boundaries and frequently amplify national identity. A country's political ideology, which often includes racial issues, may significantly impact the educational system's components Dada (2008). Race can be a tribe, a nation, or a collection of states. Today's modern population is made up of people from many racial backgrounds. The decentralization and creation of a commonwealth of nations, each of which should be free to forge its own culture and national identity, served as the foundation for British colonial policy. As a result, there is a direct connection between national character and the educational system, with the former being widely acknowledged as a critical tenet of the latter Muhammad (2013). Thus, a nation's educational policy and political system are strongly intertwined.

These facts are well known to Nigerian politicians, who put education at the forefront of their campaigns for elective offices. The political parties that gained power betrayed the country for not fulfilling their campaign promises to raise educational standards Dada (2008). They usually allow extended strikes, mediocre teaching, and a lack of staff to ruin the educational system Muhammad (2013). As a result, secondary schools frequently lack the necessary resources and suffer from poor planning, bad financial and managerial practices, and a lack of dedication from the instructors, principals, and even board members. There aren't enough classrooms, and neither are there enough labs or libraries. It's a sign of decay in secondary schools, according to Osuji (2011). Education appeared set to become every state's top priority in the final decades of the 20th Century. Education, which was initially considered a luxury of wealthy nations and individuals, a way of preparing people for their station in life, or at the very least, a way of caring for the children until they were old enough to work, came to be seen as both a fundamental right of the individual and a requirement for the state.

As mentioned, our political system must necessarily extend into public education, making schools nothing more than tools for carrying out political dictates. For instance, throughout the past thirty years, the federalization of education has occurred through both direct and indirect mechanisms. Bureaucracy is inevitable in government policy and practice, of course. But the main problem with the demand for hierarchy and organization is that politics prioritizes leadership qualities over technical knowledge. No politician can possess the knowledge and experience required in all the diverse areas that a leader must handle, especially in positions like governor and president, as stated by Osaghee and Irabor (2018). The direct function of the president and governors concerning education has expanded significantly throughout the accountability era in education some years back, frequently with education as they prioritized education during their campaigns. According to Toljaduola, Odumade, and Agbajeola (2009), one significant flaw in that development has been a trickle-down effect from presidents and governors to state superintendents of education and school board chairs and members; individuals with little to no experience or expertise as educators or scholars attain leadership positions in charge of developing and implementing education policy. To put it another way, appointees and presumed reformers who, while frequently well-intentioned, lack considerable competence or experience in education are the faces and voices currently leading the drive for education reform in Nigeria. Given the above, its clear that there are many abnormalities in education in Nigeria and Kebbi State in particular, especially in education administration and proper policy implementation Haliru (2018). That is why we undertook the research to identify whether or not the level at which politics has influence on education, mainly on how teachers are posted to their various places of primary assignment.

One of the most essential components of the educational system is the teacher. They are a necessary component of every educational program. Their presence guarantees that the curriculum will be completed. The good academic accomplishment of student depends on the quality of the teachers. The researcher discusses hiring, posting, and retention in this regard. The recruitment process is the starting point for staff appointment at this stage. The school system must have classified its intentions as to the quality and quantity of the staff it wants, it must have an idea of the salary range it proposes to offer, and it must also understand other conditions of service that it will provide.

There are two types of recruitment according to Ojo (2018) Internal Recruitment and External Recruitment. Promotions or transfers among current employees can fill job openings in an organization. It is possible to pick people (for upgrades) formally by posting job openings and inviting employees to submit bids or informally by looking through a skills inventory to find people who meet the requirements (Ojo, 2018). The company can use departmental memos, periodicals, and bulletin boards to inform current employees about job openings. All interested workers will have an equal opportunity to apply in response to the internal advertisement. Employees will have to react to the advertisement with external candidates with whom they must compete if it is both "internal" and "external."

Skills inventory and personnel appraisal: Here, it is taught that a list of names with pertinent abilities and qualities makes up an employee's skills inventory. Names, education, current employment, position and location; previous jobs; training;

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performance; salary levels; and other details will be included. According to Ojo (2018), the talent inventory thus offers a simple method of looking for workers with unique skills or abilities who can fill open roles or positions that have just been created.

There are several external sources of recruitment, according to Ojo (2018). Unsolicited Applications "Casual" applications or "Walk-ins" can be a significant source of recruiting for unskilled and, to a lesser extent, for highly skilled employees. Many employees receive applications via letters or in person from several persons. Public Recruiting Agencies- In many nations, employment agencies serve as the primary or only recruitment method into the civil service. Each federation-level state in Nigeria has its civil service commission and the federal one. Additionally, each state has a local government service commission that hires particular kinds of local government employees. Private Recruiting Agencies or consultancy (recruiting) companies offer placement services for job seekers and referrals for specific positions that are advertised with them. In Nigeria, hiring through private agencies has gained popularity due to the significant growth in the number of such firms over time.

Recruitment advertisements may be published in newspapers, magazines, trade or professional journals, bulletins posted in supermarkets, and on radio or television. Some companies use their staff to fill open positions. Employees are informed of relevant information regarding job openings and the abilities required, and they subsequently share this information with friends and family members who may possess these skills and be looking for work. In Nigeria, employee recruitment is prevalent. Almost all staff levels are covered, including junior or unskilled, senior, and executive human resources. For instance, according to Ojo (1998, p. 190), approximately 33% of respondents obtained their initial jobs through family members, 27% through friends, and 19% through merit.

Educational Institutions or Organizations quiet often keeps in touch with various educational institutions, including universities, polytechnics, technical and vocational institutes, and others. They are reliable sites for finding young candidates with different formal educations. Specific candidates are recommended to employers by counselors or placement officials at some of these institutions. Labour Unions in some developed nations like the United Kingdom, the United States of America, and Canada, this source of hiring is more pertinent. Construction, seafaring, and ductwork are some areas and professions where it is primarily functional. Employers typically send requests for new hires to the "Union Hiring Hall" for proper action. The union members who have been jobless the longest or the most senior are typically given preference when job opportunities are documented. Professional Associations or groups in Nigeria offer assistance in finding qualified candidates for new, senior, and experienced positions.

Recruitment Authority in the Secondary Schools Management Board, the Arabic Board, the State Universal Basic Education Board, and the Ministry of Science and Technical Education are all tasked with carrying out the State Ministry of Education's recruitment duties for teachers. The Ministry of Education hires educators for grades 0 through 7 and higher. The Kebbi State Government must pay their salary and benefits. Because the Civil Service Rules and Regulations serve as the authority's guide, the three categories of appointments that are available are temporary, contract, and permanent/pensionable. In Contract Appointment, special educators whose services are occasionally still required are hired on a contract basis, typically after retirement. As for Permanent and Pensionable Appointment, a two-year probationary term is required for permanent and pensionable appointments. To be confirmed and promoted, an officer must pass all mandatory exams required for his appointment. The probationary appointment may also be terminated if the officer fails the required examination. Any officer must possess the National Certificate of Education (NCE) minimum qualification to be eligible for permanent employment and retirement benefits in the teaching sector. For Temporary Appointment, teachers are placed under two years of observation before their appointments are confirmed, meaning the officer must have been effective and efficient in their duty before the work is guaranteed. However, the appointment may be terminated if the officer is found guilty.

In general overview, the teacher is entirely different in terms of skills, personality, and dedication to the profession to which they belong. The beginners among them have basic knowledge, which according to the National Policy on Education (2014), the Nigeria Certificate of Education (NCE), while the professionals have advanced degrees. They have different perceptions of their presentation, and while some have the view of starting their presentation from simple to complex, others have a different perspective. Thus, if you assign them to handle students, you find that each has their way of presentation and a different way of classroom management. When management moves a teacher to a new position, it may do so at the teacher's request or through administrative action. When a transfer request is made, a gap or a series of issues arise for the school administration, the teacher, and the students.

The educational process is sensitive when it comes to personnel issues. It must be determined which aspects of hiring and posting teachers should continue to be handled by the federal government and which could be managed more effectively at the state level. The government should almost probably continue to exercise some control over the total number of teachers engaged

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in the public sector (and, consequently, over expenditure levels). It is also proper for the government to establish eligibility requirements. However, choices about the pattern of staffing in the schools and the selection of specific instructors may be made locally, even at the school level.

In terms of consistently supplying their schools with qualified teachers and keeping those in service, Nigeria's educational system is dealing with a severe problem. Some estimates show that more than a third of the country's instructors leave the teaching profession after three years, according to the National Commission on Teaching and America's Future (2009). According to more recent data, 46% of instructors quit their jobs by the conclusion of their fifth year. Specific significant issues have been identified as reasons for teachers leaving their jobs. Retirement, family problems, pregnancy/childrearing, salary/benefits, job unhappiness, and interest in moving into a better position, either inside or outside of education, could all be among them. Many of these same educators were worried about things like Low salaries, issues with student behavior, a lack of assistance, and few opportunities for decision-making participation.

Oke (2016) noted that teachers could leave their jobs as teachers and the schools where they work in a paper titled "Retention of Teachers and their Condition of Service" that was presented at the National Conference of Principals of Teacher Training Colleges held at the Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria in 1971. He observed that the rate of resignations from the teaching profession is excessive compared to other disciplines like law, medicine, and pharmacy. He claimed that teaching and attrition are widespread and not unique to Nigeria alone. However, their seriousness can vary from one nation to the other. Poor pay and a low social standing for teachers in Nigeria relative to other countries are some issues highlighted by Oke (2016). According to the Banjo Commission in erstwhile Western Nigeria, the teaching profession has been referred to as a diseased profession. The entrance requirements have historically been relatively low. The pay scales cannot be compared to other employment categories, such as the civil service. There are extremely few opportunities for promotion here, and his professional effectiveness barely impacts the teacher's career. Many people who are successful in "uplifting" themselves into grade one decide that it would be better to leave teaching and work in government instead, where they will be paid more. Dada (2008) conducted two studies on the supply and demand of school teachers in Lagos and a defunct Mid-Western state. In the Lagos study, survey questionnaires were distributed. The majority of responses were as follows:

1. Payment delays relative to the private sector
2. Lack of promotion opportunities
3. Poor service conditions
4. Our society does not value or appreciate teachers.
5. The government's lack of encouragement.

Out of the 178 questionnaires returned, 147 stressed poor conditions of service and the fact that society still looks down on teachers and the teaching profession. Several Nigerian authors have discussed these issues: The loss of skilled teachers to other industries when the teaching industry is struggling to find talented and motivated young people was previously brought up by Asiyai (2013). "The general lack of manpower has made it difficult to interest talented people in teaching, coupled with subpar service conditions, which has worsened the recruitment situation," he observed. For some reason, teaching has to compete with other professions for the attention of capable young people. Most individuals drawn are those who can't get hired for different jobs and end up teaching. This group includes the majority of secondary school teaching professionals.

Objective of the study

To assess influence of politics in Education on effective posting of teachers in government secondary schools in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

Research Question

Does influence of politics in education affect effective teachers posting in Government Secondary Schools in Kebbi State?

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between Influence of politics in Education and effective posting of teachers in government secondary schools in Kebbi state, Nigeria

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study, which, according to Ishaya in Haliru (2018), is appropriate for a study involving a large population of respondents. The population of the study is 5177 which consist of all government secondary school stakeholders in Kebbi State during the 2022/2023 academic session, and sample of 360 was choose comprising 18 principals, 327 teachers, 10 SBMC members, and 10 quality assurance officials and a purposive sampling

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technique was used to select 30% out of the six educational zones in Kebbi State. Simple random sampling was used to select 9 schools. Data was collected using the instrument titled IPEETPGSS questionnaire with five points Likert scale options which include; strongly agree (5), agree (4), undecided (3), disagree (2), and strongly disagree (1) for positive statements. Also, the scoring was reversed for negative statements. The questionnaire consists of section one, personal data of the respondents; section two, 10 option statements for hypotheses testing. A reliability test of the instrument was conducted with Cronbach alpha 0.84 to determine the reliability of the instrument and the paper was analyzed using statistical tools of frequency counts, percentages, mean scores, and tables. Subsequently, inferential statistics such as one-way analysis of variance was used to test the hypotheses for the study.

Results

The analysis of the bio-data, which contain the status and gender of the respondents, was done and presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Analysis of Personal Data of the Respondents

s/n	Bio-Data	Category	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
1.	Status	Principal	18	4.9	4.9
		Teacher	327	89.7	94.6
		SBMC officials	10	2.7	97.3
		Quality Assurance	10	2.7	100
2.	Gender	Male	294	80.5	80.5
		Female	71	19.5	100
3.	Qualification	NCE	185	50.1	50.1
		N D	20	5.5	55.6
		B. ED	105	28.8	84.4
		M.ED	45	12.9	97.3
		Others	10	2.7	100

Source: Field survey, 2022

Table 1, shows that 18 principals, 327 teachers, 10 SBMC officials, and 10 Quality Assurance representing 4.9%, 89.7%, 2.7%, and 2.7%, respectively, constitute the study's respondents. A total of 294 respondents representing 80.5%, were males, while 71, representing 19.5%, were females. On qualification, 185, representing 50.1%, had NCE, 20 representing 5.5%, had M.ED, 105 representing 28.8%, and had B.ED, 45 representing 12.9 %, had M.ED, and 10 representing 2,7% had other qualifications. What are the educational implications of the results?

Research Question

How does Influence of Politics in Education affect effective Teachers Posting in Government Secondary Schools in Kebbi State?

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Table 2: Mean Score of Respondents on the Influence of Politics in Education for Effective Teacher's Posting In Government Secondary Schools In Kebbi State

S/N	Item statement	Respondent	N	MEAN
1	English teachers are posted to schools based on Influence of politics in education in government secondary schools in Kebbi state.	Principals	18	3.0
		Teachers	327	3.1
		SBMC	10	3.8
		Q/Assurance	10	3.6
2	Mathematics teachers are posted to schools based on the Influence of politics in education in government secondary schools in the state.	Principals	18	2.9
		Teachers	327	2.9
		SBMC	10	2.5
		Q/Assurance	10	4.2
3	Qualification is considered when posting staff due to Influence of politics in education in secondary schools in the state.	Principals	18	2.7
		Teachers	327	2.8
		SBMC	10	3.7
		Q/Assurance	10	4.1
4	The posting of staff based on seniority is based on the Influence of politics in education in secondary schools in the state.	Principals	18	3.8
		Teachers	327	2.8
		SBMC	10	1.6
		Q/Assurance	10	2.5
5	Influence of politics in education affects staff posting to rural areas in secondary schools in Kebbi State.	Principals	18	1.4
		Teachers	327	3.4
		SBMC	10	2.7
		Q/Assurance	10	3.3
6	Gender is considered in a staff posting due to the Influence of politics in education in secondary schools in the state.	Principals	18	2.4
		Teachers	327	2.6
		SBMC	10	3.6
		Q/Assurance	10	3.6
7	Influence of politics in education influences staff posting to urban areas in secondary schools in Kebbi State.	Principals	18	3.7
		Teachers	327	3.1
		SBMC	10	3.4
		Q/Assurance	10	3.6
8	Influence of politics in education encourages favoritism in staff posting in secondary schools in the state.	Principals	18	2.5
		Teachers	327	3.1
		SBMC	10	4.6
		Q/Assurance	10	2.8
9	The appointment of principals is influenced by politics in education in secondary schools in the state.	Principals	18	2.1
		Teachers	327	2.9
		SBMC	10	1.0
		Q/Assurance	10	2.5
10	Appointing inexperienced staff to the principal cadre is influenced by the politics in education in secondary schools in the state.	Principals	18	2.9
		Teachers	327	2.9
		SBMC	10	1.9
		Q/Assurance	10	2,3

Source: Field survey, 2022

From Table 2, item 1 revealed principals having a mean score of 3.0, teachers 3.1, SBMC officials 3.8, and Quality Assurance (Q A) 3.6. It shows that all the respondents accepted the item statements. Item 2 showed that principals have a mean score of 2.9, teachers 2.9, SBMC 2.5, and QA 4.2, which implies acceptance of one and three were rejected. Item 3 was accepted by two respondents and dismissed by the other two, with the mean score for principals 2.7, teacher 2.8, SBMC 3.7, and QA 4.1, respectively. Item 4 was accepted by the principals but rejected by three other respondents with a mean score of 3.8, 2.8, 1.6, and 2.5, respectively. Item 5 had a mean score of 4.4 for principals, teachers 3.4, SBMC 2.7, and QA 3.3, indicating acceptance by three and rejection by one. Item 6 showed that principals had a mean score of 2.4, teachers 2.6, SBMC 3.6, and QA

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3.6. it shows the two accepted and rejected. Item 7 was obtained by principals, teachers, SBMC, and QA, with the respective mean scores of 3.7, 3.1., 3.4, and 3.6. Item 8 has the mean score of 2.5, 3.1, 4.6 and 2.8 for principals, teachers, SBMC and QA, indicating two accepted rejected. Item 9 has the means score of 2.1, 2.9, 1.0 and 2.5 for principals, teachers, SBMC, and QA, respectively, indicating all were rejected. Item 10 has the corresponding mean score of 2.9, 2.9,1.9, and 2.3 for principals, teachers, SBMC, and QA; all respondents left it. It was revealed, therefore, that Influence of politics in education has negative impact on teachers posting in government secondary schools in Kebbi State.

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference in the Opinion of Principals, Teachers, Quality Assurance Officials, and SBMC Representatives on The Influence of Politics in Education on effective Teachers' Posting in Government Secondary Schools in Kebbi State.

Table 3: Summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on The Influence of Politics on effective Teachers Posting in Government Secondary Schools in Kebbi State.

Posting	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.839	3	0.613	0.338	0.798
Within Groups	655.291	361	1.815		
Total	657.130	364			

Source: Computed from hypothesis testing, 2022

The result of the null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in respondents' opinion on the Influence of politics in education on teachers posting in Government Secondary Schools in Kebbi State is retained. It is because the calculated significant value (p) of 0.84 is higher than the 0.05 alpha level of significance set for the study. It implies that the responses of the respondents were in agreement.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed the Influence of Politics in education on effective teachers' posting in Government Secondary Schools in Kebbi State; this is because posting in rural and urban areas is influenced by politics, and the appointment of Head teachers / Principals is influenced by politics also posting of staff is gender-sensitive, male staff are posted more in the rural areas than their female counterpart. It is in agreement with the statements of Ogunu, in Osuji (2011) posited that politics influence the appointment, promotion, and transfer of teachers. The author further observed that in the school situation, staff personnel administration forms an essential responsibility of the school administration in achieving the school's goals in particular and in education in general. Similarly, Mgbodile (2004) stated that politics influences the posting and promotion of teachers in schools. They also mentioned that there is an influence of politics in the sponsorship of seminars, workshops, and conferences.

Conclusion

The Interference of politics in education on teachers' posting in Kebbi State is a reality; this is because posting and transfer of teachers are not done based on standard criteria for staff, which include specialization, years of working experience, and seniority among others but is due to the influence of politics. It maybe because, during the cause of this study, it was observed that there are teaching staff that are posted and or transferred based on their interest or the interest of their political Godfather, without consideration of the teaching service policy.

It was also observed that some of the officials at the Ministry of Education, Secondary Schools Management Board, Arabic, and Islamic Board, on most occasions, do the posting or transfer of teachers based on the instructions of the politicians.

Recommendations

Posting and transfer should be exclusively left in the hands of the supervisory agencies of government, who are saddled with such responsibility.

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Influence of School Discipline on Academic Achievement of Public Secondary School Students' in Gombe Metropolis

Sagir, Jummai Ibrahim¹

Email: jummaisagir@gmail.com

Tel: 08036933968

Abubakar, Musa Maikamba²

Email: maikamba@gsu.edu.ng

Tel: 08029149361

¹ Department of Educational Foundations, Gombe State University

Abstract

This study investigated the influence of school discipline on students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis. The population used was 23366 students out of which 355 were sampled. Simple random sampling technique was used. School discipline questionnaire was used for data collection (SDQ). Students' third term achievement scores was used to determine their academic achievement. Data was collected by the researchers and it was analyzed using SPSS version 23. Research question one and two were analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. While hypothesis one was tested using Pearson product moment correlation while hypothesis two was tested using independent sample t-test. The result revealed that school discipline has no influence on students' academic achievement, it also revealed that there was no gender difference in the influence of school discipline and students' academic achievement in Gombe metropolis. The study concludes that school discipline has no influence on students' academic achievement in Gombe metropolis public senior secondary schools. It was recommended that researches should be conducted to investigate why school discipline has no influence and relationship with students' academic achievement.

Keyword: school discipline, academic achievement and secondary school students

Introduction

The problem of poor academic performance of students in Nigerian secondary schools have been of much concern to the government, parents, teachers and even students themselves. The quality of education not only depends on the teachers as reflected in the performance of their duties, but also in the effective coordination of the school environment (Ajao, 2001). The problem is so much that it has led to the widely acclaimed fallen standard of education in Gombe State and Nigeria at large. The quality of education depends on the teachers as reflected in the performance of their duties. Over time students' academic performance in both internal and external examinations had been used to determine excellence in teachers and teaching (Ajao, 2001). Teachers have been shown to have an important influence on students' academic achievement and they also play a crucial role in educational attainment because the teacher is ultimately responsible for translating policy into action and principles based on practice during interaction with the students (Afe, 2001). Both teaching and learning depends on teachers, no wonder an effective teacher has been conceptualized as one who produces desired results in the course of his duty as a teacher (Uchefuna, 2001).

Considering governments' huge investment in public education, its output in terms of quality of students have been observed to be unequal with government expenditure. Literature revealed that there are many factors that are capable of influencing students' performance, these factors include but not limited to schools' discipline, classroom management, school administrator, teachers, poor time management (Afe, 2001). School or classroom discipline may be defined as the training which produces in the learners, a life of self-restraint, orderliness, good conduct, cooperation and the habit of getting the best out of themselves. Discipline can be determined by the extent to which the learners are convinced in what they are doing and willingly submit themselves to the authority of the teacher (Anuforo, 2007). Scholars over times have written more on indiscipline among students and its effects on learning outcome and their progress in schools. One of such was that of Stanley (2014) whose study was carried out to establish the relationships between schools' discipline and students' academic performance. The study employed cross sectional research survey design in which questionnaire was the main instrument of data collection in addition to interview guide and document review. Simple percentage and Chi-square statistical method were

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used to analyze the data. However, the findings of the study clearly showed that effective school discipline should be encouraged in controlling students' behaviour thus affects students' general academic performance. Another study also is that of Pasternak and Lezion (2013) in their paper discipline, learning skills and academic achievement. The article intends to find correlation between discipline, learning skills and academic achievement. Findings from a quantitative research conducted among 143 fifth-grade students in Israel and the US indicated a significant positive correlation between four discipline skills – perseverance, meeting schedules, goal setting and planning for their achievement as well as completion of unpleasant tasks – and academic achievement. None statistically significant differences were obtained between boys and girls, between the classes tested and between Israeli as opposed to US students. Some scholars suggest that disciplinary policies simply do not have different effects (Verdugo and Glenn, 2002; Chen, 2008; Schoonover, 2009). Other asserts that suspensions do not prevent students' future misbehaviour (Nichols, 2004). If school is effectively disciplined, the academic performance on the part of student and teacher will be highly rated. Gawe, Vakalisa and Jacobs, (2001:190) express cooperative learning if academic performance is to be achieved among students. However, apart from the fact that effective discipline helps in the achievement of goals, expectation and responsibility in students (Dunham, 1984:66). Discipline creates a good image of the school and prepares learners for the future. Disruptive behaviour amongst learners is eliminated if there is good discipline at school. The implementation of effective discipline at school is a key for the student in the journey to adulthood. Parents often have no choice but to enroll their children in a school with good discipline, which often leads to better academic performances. In our secondary schools today, learners are habitual late comers; this is contrary to the school rules and regulations. They leave school premises without permission; do not bring their books to school; refuse to do their homework; reject any kind of authority and resist any disciplinary measures taken against them. Teachers on the other hand, are always absent from school; present ill-prepared lessons; fail to exercise discipline in the classroom and lack a professional work ethic. Bieketty, (2004) opined that lack of discipline and respect among teachers cause a severe barrier to effective teaching and learning in the classroom. Discipline have been underestimated by over actualizing freedom and rights, an understatement of responsibilities and obligations, marginalization of the authority of the head teacher, bad role models by some teachers, lack of punctuality, abscondment from classes by both learners and teachers and the unionist attitude of some teachers. Based on this contextual background this study investigated the influence of school discipline on academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis.

Objectives of the study:

1. To find out the relationship between school discipline and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in Gombe Metropolis.
2. To determine the influence of school discipline on academic achievement of students in public secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis.
3. To determine the mean score difference between gender in the responses of students on the influence of school discipline on the academic achievement of public senior secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis.
4. To find out the significant gender difference in the responses of students on the influence of school discipline on the academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis.

Research Questions:

1. What is the influence of school discipline on academic achievement of students in public secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis?
2. What is the mean score difference between gender in the responses of students on the influence of school discipline on the academic achievement of public senior secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis?

Hypotheses:

1. **H₀₁:** There is no significant relationship between school discipline and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in Gombe Metropolis.
2. **H₀₂:** There is no significant gender difference in the responses of students on the influence of school discipline on the academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis.

Methodology

Survey research design was used. The population used for this study was all senior secondary students with a total number of 23, 366 spread across the 17 public senior secondary schools in the metropolis. Six schools were randomly selected also simple random sampling technique was used to select the participant using hat and draw method of drawing the participant of the study. 355 participants were used as a sample of the study. The decision of the sample size was based on the research advisor estimated sample size table. Students' third term achievement scores was used to determine their academic achievement. The

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instrument used for data collection was school discipline questionnaire (SDQ) with fifteen items with a five point likert scale namely, strongly agrees, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree. This is used to register the extent of agreement or disagreement with a particular statement of an attitude, belief or judgment. The instrument has face, content and construct validity and is reliable with 0.78 cronbach alpha value coefficient. The student academic achievement was determined using average scores of students at the end of third term (promotional exams) meanwhile, all the data collected through the questionnaire were analyzed, using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. Pearson product moment correlation and t-test were used in testing the hypothesis raised.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the influence of school discipline on academic achievement of students in public secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis?

Table 1: Result of the frequency and percentage on the influence of school discipline on students' academic achievement.

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	Discipline in schools is essential for good learning	16(4.5%)	82(23.1%)	168(47.3%)	85(23.9%)	4(1.1%)
2.	Discipline is essential for good teacher relationship	2(0.6%)	1(0.3%)	3(0.8%)	59(16.6%)	290(81.7%)
3.	Student indiscipline affects their academic performance	6(1.7%)	8(2.3%)	5(1.4%)	100(28.2%)	236(66.5%)
4.	Indiscipline students in your school perform well in exams	12(3.4%)	29(8.2%)	21(5.9%)	51(14.4%)	242(68.2%)
5.	Discipline students create a conducive learning environment in schools	132(37.2%)	90(25.4%)	26(7.3%)	54(15.2%)	53(14.9%)
6.	Indiscipline students relate well with teachers	130(36.6%)	73(20.6%)	31(8.7%)	61(17.2%)	60(16.9%)
7.	Indiscipline students have ample reading time	165(46.5%)	94(26.5%)	27(7.6%)	39(11.0%)	28(7.9%)
8.	Observance of time management affects student performance	138(38.9%)	114(32.1%)	43(12.1%)	39(11.0%)	21(5.9%)
9.	School Rule and regulation influences students' academic performance positively	55(15.5%)	69(19.4%)	54(15.2%)	105(29.6%)	72(20.3%)
10.	Personality of the teacher is to be blamed for indiscipline in schools.	33(9.3%)	42(11.8%)	34(9.6%)	63(17.7%)	183(51.5%)
11.	Leadership style of the teacher accounts for indiscipline in schools	57(16.1%)	71(20%)	66(18.6%)	80(22.5%)	81(22.8%)
12.	School/ class environment is a major source of indiscipline in schools	80(22.5%)	94(26.5%)	42(11.8%)	67(18.9%)	72(20.3%)
13.	Violence affects students learning	99(27.9%)	62(17.5%)	23(6.5%)	65(18.3%)	106(29.9%)
14.	Unrests cause time wastage	49(13.8%)	26(7.3%)	25(7.0%)	61(17.2%)	194(54.6%)
15.	Indiscipline students lead a good life after schooling	40(11.3%)	50(14.1%)	40(11.3%)	77(21.7%)	148(41.7%)

Field study

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Table 1 revealed that discipline in schools is not essential for good learning in Gombe State as majority 168(47.3%) were neither agree nor disagree that discipline is essential for good learning. Majority 290(81.7%) of the respondents strongly disagree that discipline is essential for good teacher relationship. Majority 236(66.5%) strongly disagree that Student indiscipline affects their academic performance. Indiscipline students in your school perform well in exams strongly disagree by the majority 242(68.2%) of the respondents. Majority 132(37.2%) have unanimously strongly agree that discipline students bring a conducive learning environment in schools. Majority 130(36.6%) of the respondents strongly agree that discipline students relate well with teachers in Gombe Metropolis. Majority 165(46.5%) strongly agree that discipline students have ample reading time. Majority 138(38.9%) strongly agree that observance of time management affects student performance. Majority 105(29.6%) disagree that School Rule and regulation influences students' academic performance positively. Majority 183 (51.5%) strongly disagree that Personality of the teacher is to be blamed for indiscipline in schools. Majority 80(22.8%) strongly disagree that Leadership style of the teacher accounts for indiscipline in schools. Majority 94(26.5%) agree that School/class environment is a major source of indiscipline in schools. Majority 106(29.9%) strongly disagree that Violence affects students learning. Majority 194(54.6%) strongly agree that Unrests cause time wastage. Majority 148(41.7%) strongly agree that Indiscipline students lead a good life after schooling.

Research question 2

What is the mean score difference between gender in the responses of students on the influence of school discipline on the academic achievement of public senior secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis?

Table 2: Result of mean difference between males and female students

Academic Performance	N	Mean	S.D	Std.Error mean
Male	97	49.57	7.20	.7314
Female	258	49.89	32.09	1.99

The result in Table 2, revealed that there is little or no gender difference in the responses of students on the influence of school discipline on academic achievement of students in Gombe metropolis. This is because mean scores of male students is 49.57 with a standard deviation of 7.20 and the females is 49.89 with a standard deviation of 32.09. The only difference is 0.32 which is negligible.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between school discipline and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in Gombe Metropolis

Table 3: Result of the Spearman Rank Correlation of the relationship between school discipline and students' academic performance.

Variable	N	X	S.D	r.	sig.	Decision
School discipline	355	63.69	14.036	.020	.710	Accepted
Academic performance	355	49.803	27.60			

Field study

Result in table 3, revealed that there is no significant relationship between school discipline and students' academic achievement. Spearman rank order correlation was used in testing the hypothesis. From table 3, the correlation value of $r = .020$ represents the correlation between school discipline and students' academic achievement while the sig-value of $.710$ represents the significance level. Based on the obtained correlation value ($r = .020$, $sig. = .710$, > 0.05), a statistically insignificant relationship exists between school discipline and students' academic achievement. This is because the obtained sig-value is $> .05$ level of significance. Based on the obtained result, the stated null hypothesis was accepted.

Research Hypothesis 2

There is no significant gender difference in the responses of students on the influence of school discipline on the academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis

Table 4: Result of the independent t-test between gender and students' academic performance.

Academic Performance	N	Mean	S.D	Df	t.	P	Decision
Male	97	49.57	7.20	353	.097	.922	Accepted
Female	258	49.89	32.09				

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Field study

Table 2, presents the results of the independent t-test on whether there is a significant gender difference on the influence of school discipline on their academic achievement. The result showed that $t(353) = -.097$ and $p = .922$ since the p-value (0.933) is greater than the alpha value (0.05), the hypothesis was therefore accepted. Thus, there was no significant gender difference on the influence of school discipline and students' academic performance in Gombe metropolis.

Discussion of Findings

This study found that school discipline has no influence on students' academic achievement, it was also revealed insignificant relationships between school discipline and students' academic achievement. It was also found that there was no significant difference between males and female students in terms of their academic achievement. With regard to influence of school discipline on students' academic achievement this study found that school discipline has no influence on students' academic achievement. This finding is contrary to the finding of Stanley (2014) who in his study found that effective school discipline influence students' academic performance. It is also not in consistent with the finding of Pasternak and Lezion (2013) who in the same study found positive correlation between school discipline and academic achievement of students. It is also contrary to the finding of Dunham (1984) who found that effective school discipline helps in the achievement goals expectation and responsibility in students. Bieketty (2004) also found that lack of discipline among teachers can affect students' academic achievement. It is not in line with the findings of Anuforo (2007) who found that there is no significant relationships between school discipline and academic achievement of students. This study found insignificant difference between gender in terms of influence of school discipline and academic achievement. The finding is consistent with the previous finding of Ajao (2001) who also found no significant difference between gender and academic achievement of students.

This finding is surprising, because previous reviewed studies found that school discipline has influence on students' academic achievement but this study found that school discipline has no influence on students' academic achievement and has no significant relationship between school discipline and academic achievement of students. The reason perhaps the interaction between the researcher and teachers as well as the students. It was reported indisciplined students tend to perform better than the discipline ones. It was common to find indisciplined students perform better in schools than the discipline ones. Meanwhile, discipline is different from achievement. One can be discipline but his/her performance is low and one can be indisciplined but his performance can be good. In most cases practically discipline has no relationship with an individual students' performance, however, it will be worthy of commendation when students have discipline and also perform better in school.

Conclusion

This study examined the influence of school discipline on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis. The study concluded that school discipline has no influence students' academic achievement. One being discipline has no relation with the academic achievement. It also concludes that discipline is someone behaviour while achievement is one's academic engagement to knowledge.

Recommendations

1. Researches should be conducted to investigate why school discipline has no influence on academic achievement of students. After all previous reviewed study demonstrated that school disciplined has influence on students' academic achievement.
2. Researches should be conducted to find out why there is no relationship between school discipline and academic achievement of students.
3. Researches should be conducted to investigate why there is no gender difference in terms of influence of school discipline among secondary school students.

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Influence of WhatsApp on Performance in Coordinate Geometry among Students of the Federal College of Education Zaria, Kaduna State

*Balarabe, Bashir¹

Email: bbalarabe5@gmail.com

Tel: 08113901887

Yahaya, Ibrahim El-Ladan¹

Email: Yahayaibrahm.61@gmail.com

Tel: 08033860788

¹Department of Mathematics, Federal College of Education, Zaria

Abstract

The study aimed at investigating the influence of WhatsApp on NCE 1 students' academic performance in Coordinate Geometry in Federal College of Education Zaria. Quasi experimental involving pretest and posttest research design was used for the study. The targeted population of the study was 366 NCE 1 students registered for the 2019/2020 academic session in the Department of Mathematics. The sample of the study was 140 students selected through Multistage and Stratified Sampling. The sample comprised 61 students (29 male and 32 female) students were assigned to the experimental group and 79 (42 male and 37 female) students to the control group. The average age of students was 19 years. The study was guided by two research questions and two research hypotheses. The CGPT was subjected to both face and content validation by two experts in the field of mathematics education. The final draft of CGPT was trial tested using 30 students that were part of the population but not part of the sample and test-retest method was used to obtain the reliability to coefficient which was found to be 0.82. A WhatsApp strategy lesson plan prepared by the researchers was used to teach the experimental group while the control group was taught using conventional method. Findings from study shows a significant difference in the mean performance score between the experimental group (mean= 72.67, SD= 11.811) and the control group (mean= 51.58, SD= 9.85), $t(138) = 11.52$, $p = 0.001$. The study also revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean performance score between male and female students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp male (mean= 71.79, SD= 12.37) and female (mean= 74.13, SD= 11.52), $t(59) = 0.762$, $p = 0.224$. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that the serving teachers be trained in current innovation teaching strategies such as WhatsApp strategy through workshops, seminars, conferences and in serve programmes.

Keywords: WhatsApp, Coordinate Geometry, Performance, Covid-19.

Introduction

Mathematics teaching and learning have become so imperative to the scientific and technological developments of any nation of the world. This is why the Federal Government of Nigeria, in its National Policy on Education (NPE, 2013), made mathematics one of the core subjects in the secondary school curriculum. It is also a pre-requisite for students to obtain credit in the subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) before gaining admission into any tertiary institution in Nigeria. This is necessary because disciplines such as the sciences, humanities, arts, etc, cannot be studied successfully without the application of mathematics. Coordinate Geometry according to Saidu (2019), is a field of study in Mathematics that bridges the gap between Algebra and Geometry. This is attested to the fact that the course content covers the following topics; Circles, Parabola, Ellipse, Hyperbola, and Equation of Lines. It is one of the core courses in Mathematics taught at National Certificate in Education (NCE) level one (1). The study of Coordinate Geometry dates back to ancient times because Isaac Newton (1642-1727) was the first to work on Functional Exponents and Coordinate Geometry to drive solutions to Algebraic Equations. As a result of this development, Scientist employs the knowledge of Coordinate Geometry in solving geometrical problems. Brown, Evans, Hunt, McIntosh, Pender, and Ramagge (2011) opined, the techniques of coordinate geometry are used in courses like Statistics, Calculus, Graph, Algebra, etc. Therefore, Coordinate Geometry is a gateway to learning other concepts in Mathematics and Science in general.

Despite the importance of Coordinate Geometry, students failed in answering questions that have to do with the concept. This was attested from WAEC (2019) Chief Examiner's report in which students failed in solving geometrical

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questions and this translates to poor performance by NCE 1 Mathematic students on coordinate geometry because students fail and score low grades in the subject. Even though many factors were responsible for the poor performance which include; teaching method been used by teachers of Mathematics, students lack interest, class size, lack of use of teaching aids to mention a few. However, research studies have shown that the conventional lecture method has a greater effect on poor performance by students. The method has been described by Usman (2007) as one that encourages students to learn without understanding. To attest to that, WAEC (2010) noted, lecture method of teaching doesn't meet the needs of the learners as such perform poorly in mathematics. Inah (2014) describes the conventional lecture method as it allows teachers to within a short period, cover a wide area of the syllabus without minding students' understanding. To this effect, researchers such as Ennyam and Yaratan (2018) suggested, the use of computer-aided technology in teaching and learning as an alternative strategy in teaching courses such as Coordinate Geometry.

One of such technological developments is the emergence of digital media in today's communication system of the world. Smartphones as digital media has several applications that allow for social interactions among groups and individuals. These applications include; Facebook, WhatsApp, Integra, Twitter, Snap Chats, Skype, Email, etc, are termed Social Networking Sites (SNSs) (Al-Mothana, 2017). According to Al-Mothana (2017), SNSs are often used by university students all over the world which suggests they could be used for educational purposes. Digital communication among students and their teachers is on the increase in the last decade through this SNSs (Hamiyet, 2016). Students often use these sites to obtain information through question and answer which allow for knowledge acquisition. Orij and Anikpo (2019) opined that 80% of active users of these SNSs are youths who are mainly students cut across Educational Institutions in Nigeria. They describe these SNS sites as technological platforms that allow for interactive web content formation, collaboration, and discussion by contributors.

One of these SNSs as noted by Al-Mothan (2017), is the WhatsApp application. It is a Smartphone application used as a means of sending and receiving instant messages to and from individuals and groups (Bouhnik and Deshen, 2014). The application, allows users to exchange text messages, images, videos, and audio using internet connections. Even though, WhatsApp as a new tool in education has positive characteristics as other previous technological tools used in teaching and learning. Thus, Bouhnik and Deshen (2014) noted that WhatsApp has some up-to-date features that encourage teachers and students to use it to enhance academic performance. Online collaboration, as prompted by WhatsApp instant messages help in facilitating learning, because learners can easily exchange information, have their inquiries quickly answered, construct knowledge and create class participation. It is therefore easy for mathematics teachers to create and form groups of students with WhatsApp and use it as a teaching strategy in teaching and learning concepts in the subject. Therefore, teaching and learning of mathematical concepts such as; Algebra, Trigonometry, Coordinate Geometry, Number and Numeration, etc can be taught to students using the WhatsApp platform.

The emergence of Pandemic Diseases in particular COVID-19, according to Ebohon, Obienu, Irabor, Amadin, and Omoregie (2021) was a result of a widespread of cases of patients with pneumonia admitted to Wuhan hospitals in China in late 2019. As a result of the widespread of the disease across the globe, World Health Organization (WHO) in 2019 declared, COVID-19 as a pandemic. Thus, as a result 87 percent of the world's students were affected by school closure from about 180 countries as reported by (Jacob, 2020) . Throughout the year 2020, all human activities were greatly affected by the pandemic spread across the world.

In Nigeria, Ebohon et al (2021) noted, tertiary institutions were taken unaware when the disease appeared because there was no contingency arrangement for such a problem. All activities including economic, religious, health, education, sports, transport, agriculture, mining, and many others, were seriously affected by the spread of the disease across the country. The Federal Government of Nigeria had to join in closing all schools public and private in March, 2020. The school started re-opening in October, 2020. While, students were at home due to the lockdown, the Federal and State Governments introduce Radio and Television educational programmes to make the students busy doing something. Administrators in private and tertiary institutions came up with online teaching and learning for their students. Some of the Social Media Applications, Television, and Radio, were used as an alternative method of teaching and learning for their students across the educational levels of the institutions.

The prevailing teaching methodology in teaching mathematics courses in Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria has been the Conventional Lecture method. The method has become a subject of concern among stakeholders in Education because it is largely teacher-centered. Students lack of interaction and activity during teaching and learning results in a lack of understanding of what is been taught in the class. One of the courses at the NCE 1 level that gives students a lot of difficulties is Coordinate Geometry because it's considered abstract. Students find it difficult to understand its concepts mainly due to the method of

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teaching. It is for this reason that the study is designed to determine the influence of WhatsApp on NCE 1 student's performance in Coordinate Geometry.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to determine the influence of WhatsApp and NCE 1 students' performance in Coordinate Geometry in FCE Zaria. The objectives of the study are;

1. To examine the performance of students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp and those taught using the Lecture method.
2. To determine whether there is difference in the performance of male and female students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp.

Research Question

The following questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What is the mean difference in the performance of students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp and those taught using Lecture method?
2. What is the mean difference in performance between male and female students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significant

1. There is no significant difference in performance between the students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp and those taught using the Lecture method.
2. There is no significant difference in performance between male and female student taught coordinate geometry using WhatsApp.

Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental pre-test, post-test control group design. The targeted population for the study consisted of all 366 NCE 1 students registered in the Department of Mathematics for the 2019/2020 academic session. A sample of 140 students comprising of 78 males and 62 females was selected through a Multi-stage Sampling technique. In the first stage, stratified sampling technique was used by dividing the students into two strata, that is those students who have WhatsApp applications on their phones and those who don't have the application or nor phone at all. In the second stage, proportional sampling was used to select from each course combination a certain number of students having the application and also those not having the application.

Coordinate Geometry Performance Test (CGPT) was used as an instrument for the data collection. The CGPT was a 20-item multiple-choice question that required students to choose the correct answers from the options lettered A-D. The instrument CGPT was subjected to both face and content validation by two experts in the field of Mathematics Education where their comments and suggestions were used in modifying some of the test items. The final draft of CGPT was trial tested using 30 students that were not part of the sample. A test-retest method was used to determine the reliability of the CGPT and was found to be 0.82. The treatment lasted for six weeks, after which a post-test was administered to both the experimental and control groups. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, while a t-test was used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in mean performance scores between those students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp and those taught using Lecture Method?

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Table 1: Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation of student performance taught using WhatsApp and Lecture method

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Experimental	61	26.57	4.537	72.67	11.811	46.10
Control	79	25.92	8.639	51.58	9.846	25.66
Mean Difference				21.09		

The results Table 1 show the difference in the mean between the two groups at pre-test as 0.65. At post-test, the Table revealed that the difference was 21.09 in favour of the Experimental group. The mean gains of the Experimental and Control groups were 46.10 and 25.66 respectively. This shows that the experimental group had higher mean performance scores than the control group. To test the significance of this difference independent sample t-test analysis was used.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in performance between those students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp and those taught using Lecture Method.

Table 2: Summary of t-test Analysis on Students Performance between Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	t-value	P-value
Experimental	61	72.67	11.811	138	11.52	0.001
Control	79	51.58	9.846			

Table 2 revealed that there was significant difference between the mean performance scores of experimental (mean = 72.67) and the control group (mean = 51.58) at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance $t(138) = 11.52, p = 0.0001$. Therefore, hypothesis one was rejected. This implies that, the mean difference in the performance scores between the students in the Experimental group and Control group was significant. The students taught using WhatsApp performed significantly better than those students taught using the conventional method

Research Question 2:

What is the difference in the mean performance scores between Male and Female Students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation between male and female students in the Experimental Group

Gender	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Male	29	27.69	5.100	71.79	12.370	44.10
Female	32	25.19	6.162	74.13	11.519	48.94
Mean Difference				2.34		

Table 3 shows the difference in the mean between gender at pre-test as 2.50 in favour of male students while at post-test, the female had a mean score of 74.13 and the male had a mean score of 71.79 showing a difference of 2.34 in favour of the female students. The mean gain of the male was 44.10 while that of female students was 48.94.

H0₂: There is no significant difference in performance between male and female students taught coordinate geometry using WhatsApp.

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Table 4: Summary of t- test Analysis on Performance between Male and Female Students

Gender	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	t-value	p-value
Male	29	71.79	12.370	59	0.7624	0.2244
Female	32	74.13	11.519			

Table 4 above shows $t(59) = 0.7624$ and $p = 0.224$, with $p > 0.05$, the null hypothesis was retained. This result implies that, the mean difference between male and female students who were taught using WhatsApp was not significant. It means that, the male and female students equally benefitted from the WhatsApp teaching strategy.

Discussion of Findings

The result in Table 2 showed that, significant difference existed between those students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp and those exposed to Coordinate Geometry using the Lecture method. Therefore, the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance was rejected. This is in line with the study of Saidu (2019) which showed that students taught coordinate geometry using GeoGebra teaching strategy perform better than those taught using the lecture method of teaching.

In the test of hypothesis 2 in Table 4 revealed that, there is no significant difference between male and female students taught Coordinate Geometry with WhatsApp. This finding is in agreement with the study of Molina, Gercia, and Mortoro (2010) who did not find a significant difference between the performance of male and female student Web-Based learning and practice. The researchers conclude that WhatsApp is gender-friendly.

Conclusion

The findings of this study provide empirical support that, the teaching of Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp improved students' performance much more than the lecture method. It is important to note that, the performance of students in Coordinate Geometry could be significantly improved if Mathematics Educators could explore the use of social media such as WhatsApp, Tweeter, Facebook, etc and appropriately utilized them in the teaching and learning of Mathematics courses. The study empirically shows that, social media is capable of helping students to understand Coordinate Geometry concepts better and could bridge the gender gap in terms of student's performance. In addition to that, study revealed that It is also important to note that, social media could serve as an alternative teaching strategy in situations like the emergence of Pandemic in our schools, right from primary to tertiary Institutions in Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. NCE students should be exposed to the new teaching strategy (WhatsApp) in teaching and learning in all courses offered by FCE Zaria.
2. curriculum writers should develop curriculum that allows for using WhatsApp as a teaching strategy in our Educational Institutions.
3. Conferences/ Workshops should be organized by organizations such as MAN to enlighten the teaching staff on the new teaching strategy.

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Open Technologies for Inclusive Educational Delivery at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria: Panacea for Sustainable Development Goal (SDG)

Shehu, Suleiman Abdullahi Ph.D.

Email: shehusuleman78@gmail.com

Tel: 07033674799; 08027303904

Federal University Gusau, Department of Educational Foundations PMB-1001, Gusau-Zamfara State

Abstract

This Paper X-rays Open Technologies for Inclusive Educational Delivery at Secondary School level of Education in Nigeria: Panacea for Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It has been established that, Sustainable Development Goals, especially, Goal-4 aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education for all and it is a known fact that, education is a fundamental human right and is critical in achieving meaningful development of any Nation's socio-economics development While, the term inclusive education is when all students, regardless of any challenges they may have, are placed in age-appropriate general education classes that are in their own neighborhood schools to receive high-quality instruction, interventions, and supports that would enable them to meet success in their learning process. Based on the fore-going, the paper discussed the concepts of sustainable development goals, which is seen as the blueprint to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all. Similarly, it highlighted inclusive educational delivery with the uses of open technologies at secondary school level of education. The paper further unveiled taxonomies of Open Technologies available for inclusive education at secondary school level such as Artificial Intelligence & open source tool and Learning Analytics & open source tool. Additionally, it examined the advantages of using open technologies for teaching, which include: Flexibility, Scalability and Reliability. Lastly, Theoretical Frame work supporting the use of open technologies for inclusive educational delivery in secondary schools were discussed. Then, Conclusion & Recommendations were made and such recommendation include: That, the quality of support for learners with diverse challenges to cater for diverse needs should be available and usable.

Keywords: Open Technology, Inclusive Education, Secondary School & Sustainable Development Goals

Introduction

Over the years it has been re-emphasized that education must be the top priority for governments and this is so because the global technological revolution is driving rapid and irreversible changes in every area of our lives: new types of knowledge, new forms of communication, new workplace skills. Therefore, harnessing these changes, making the revolution work for everyone, is the key to economic prosperity and the central challenge for progressive politics. There are brilliant examples of technology used to deliver quality education and this include providing the best resources for teachers to use in classroom teaching and home learning; accurate and timely feedback to students; and engaging, collaborative learning experiences adapted for learners' ability with or without disability, It was based on this background that, the most recent edition of National Policy of Education (NPE-2014-Six-Edition) categorically stated that, in section one of the sub-component eight, clearly stated that, in order to fully realized the goals of education in Nigeria and gain from the contributions to the national economy, government shall take necessary measure to ensure that; i- Educational activities shall be learner centred for maximum self-development and self-fulfillment and secondly, Teaching shall be practical, activity based, experiential and Information & Technology Supported (IT). Therefore, the above showcase that effective inclusive education delivery out rightly anchored on selecting and integrating appropriate technology to support implementation process (NPE-2014-Six-Edition; Tony, 2021). Therefore, in a broader perspective, technology can help educators create blended learning environments and leverage on digital technologies and or open technology for formative and summative assessments, bringing new models for learning and teaching to classrooms. This is so because technology in education and the right devices in students' hands helps prepare them with the career and technical skills, they need to be successful today and in tomorrow's workforce. The promise of contemporary technology lives in what these tools can do that previous learning and educational technologies could not and this is for the fact that they are open, connected, and flexible. Therefore, Open Technology, is a concept that encompasses notions of Open Standards, Open Source, and Open Software. (Dinesh et, al;2021). A standard is a specification for a technology or methodology. An open standard is such a specification that is publically available, in such a way that anyone who wants, can obtain it and use it to create an implementation of the specified technology or methodology. Software is open source if its source code is available to the general public without restrictions that limit studying it, changing it, or improving upon it. In

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legal terms, open software is published under an Open-Source license. The “open” adjective is also proudly presented in a host of software projects, some of significant prominence in their field: Open BSD, Open GL, Open LDAP, OpenOffice.org, Open PGP, and so on (Dinesh et, al;2021; Wehler, 2018)

However, open Technology thrives and feeds on Open Standards and Open Source, and is better characterized as a process and attitude similar to the scientific process than by technological aspects. Openness has a vital influence on security and reduces costs by leveling the playing field for product selection, and helps battle inflexibility and legacy-problems (Source) It was in line with the foregoing that, open technology was conceptualized as a government policy that allows users access to platforms or systems with very few constraints or restrictions on their use. Open technology standards foster innovation while ensuring that devices and networks can work together seamlessly, this collaborative approach to technology development depends upon what the technology intended to be applied for and used to achieving certain objective (s) Hence, open technology is a term that can refers to a government policy that allows users access to platforms or systems with very few constraints or restrictions on their used and this is possible through open source technology tools. These open-source technologies are seen as the production and development philosophy of allowing end users and developers to not only see the source code of software, but modify it as well for their intended use and accomplishment. The term equally “open-source technology tools” implied also a more generally to a community-based approach to creating any intellectual property (such as software) via open collaboration, inclusiveness, transparency, and frequent public updates (Dinesh et. al., 2021; Wehler, 2018)

There are two terms that largely explained open technology tool and these include open sources and open standard the former “open source” refers to something people can modify and share because its design is publicly accessible and it originated in the context of software development to designate a specific approach to creating computer programs. Today, however, "open source" designates a broader set of values what we call "the open-source way” Open-source projects, products, or initiatives embrace and celebrate principles of open exchange, collaborative participation, rapid prototyping, transparency, meritocracy, and community-oriented development. That open-source software is software with source code that anyone can inspect, modify, and enhance."Source code" is the part of software that most computer users don't ever see; it's the code computer programmers can manipulate to change how a piece of software a "program" or "application" works. Programmers who have access to a computer program's source code can improve that program by adding features to it or fixing parts that don't always work correctly. This therefore, implies Open source and open standards are not the same thing. Because in Open source we mean strictly, that software whose source code is freely available to users for reference, debugging, modification, and/or extension. While, Open standards are, typically, specifications and formal descriptions of software or software interfaces. (Dinesh, et. al., 2021; Wehler, 2018)

More explicitly, standard is a specification for a technology or methodology and open standard is such a specification that is publically available, in such a way that anyone who wants to can obtain it and use it to create an implementation of the specified technology or methodology. A particular product can, by definition, never be a standard; calling a product a standard is a basic category mistake. While not a standard in itself, it can however of course be an implementation of a standard. For software systems, a particular implementation, often called a reference implementation in this case, can play a role in the definition of a standard. As extensively advocated by Richard Stallman. On the Internet for example, interoperability between the vast hordes of connected systems, consisting of many different makes and models of systems running a Mind bogglingly vast arsenal of different software and software versions, is achieved on the basis of the so-called Internet Standards: standards ratified by the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) after a process of extensive peer review An example of an open standard is Postel's ‘Transmission Control Protocol that defines TCP, which is the very mechanism used by high-level protocols such as SMTP (mail transfer, which is of course yet another open standard and HTTP (data transfer on the world wide web (Dinesh,,;et, al;2021; Wehler, 2018))

Following this development, Open-source technology is seen has been beneficial to programmers and non-programmers this is because early inventors built much of the Internet itself on open-source technologies like the Linux operating system and the Apache Web server application anyone using the Internet today benefits from open-source software. Every time computer users view web pages, check email, chat with friends, stream music online, or play multiplayer video games, their computers, mobile phones, or gaming consoles connect to a global network of computers using open-source software to route and transmit their data to the "local" devices they have in front of them. The computers that do all this important work are typically located in faraway places that users don't actually see or can't physically access—which is why some people call these computers "remote computers." More and more, people rely on remote computers when performing tasks, they might otherwise perform on their local devices. For example, they may use online word processing, email management, and image editing software that they don't install and run on their personal computers. Instead, they simply access

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these programs on remote computers by using a Web browser or mobile phone application. When they do this, they're engaged in "remote computing. (Dinesh et, al;2021; Wehler,2018)

In this perspective, it is worthy to note that, Sustainable Development Goal 4 ultimately aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and it was an established fact that, education is a fundamental human right and is critical to achieving sustainable development and this so because the United Nations promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. Based on this premises it is important to unveil scholar's opinions as regards inclusive or inclusiveness of educational provision. The term Inclusive Education is when all students, regardless of any challenges they may have, are placed in age-appropriate general education classes that are in their own neighborhood schools to receive high-quality instruction, interventions, and supports that enable them to meet success in the core curriculum. This therefore means inclusive education pre-supposes an educational setting that cater for and take care of all learners irrespecful of any disability or inability that they might have but they meet equal treatment and opportunity in a learning centre (Classroom). Hence, it can be seen as an education that includes everyone, regardless of their ability, disability, language, or background, in the same classrooms and schools. It aims to provide equal opportunities, celebrate diversity, and foster a sense of belonging among all students. It also means that the education system must adapt to the needs and strengths of each student, rather than expecting them to fit into a standard model. Similarly, it can be perceived as avenue where all students, regardless of any challenges they may have, are placed in age-appropriate general education classes that are in their own neighborhood schools to receive high-quality instruction, interventions, and supports that enable them to meet success in the core curriculum (Al-Shammari,2019B: Côte-Real, et al:2017: Gandomi, & Haider 2015)

The school and classroom operate on the premise that students with disabilities are as fundamentally competent as students without disabilities. Therefore, all students can be full participants in their classrooms and in the local school community. Much of the movement is related to legislation that students receive their education in the least restrictive environment (LRE). This means they are with their peers without disabilities to the maximum degree possible, with general education the placement of first choice for all students (Dangiliena, & Kloviene, 2019). Successful inclusive education happens primarily through accepting, understanding, and attending to student differences and diversity, which can include physical, cognitive, academic, social, and emotional. This is not to say that students *never* need to spend time out of regular education classes, because sometimes they do for a very particular purpose for instance, for speech or occupational therapy. But the goal is this should be the exception. The driving principle is to make all students feel welcomed, appropriately challenged, and supported in their learning efforts. (Al-Shammari,2019A; Dangiliena, & Kloviene, 2019; and Mr. Dinesh, et, al; 2021)

Meaning and Conceptualization of Open Technology and Inclusive Education at Secondary School Level

Open Technology as a concept thrives and feeds on Open Standards and Open Source as earlier explained though, it is better characterized as a process and attitude similar to the scientific process than by technological aspects. (Dinesh, et al., 2021) Openness has a vital influence on security and reduces costs by leveling the playing field for product selection, and helps battle inflexibility and legacy-problems. It was in line with the foregoing that, open technology was conceptualized as a government policy that allows users access to platforms or systems with very few constraints or restrictions on their use.(Wehler, 2018) Open technology standards foster innovation while ensuring that devices and networks can work together seamlessly, this collaborative approach to technology development depends upon what the technology intended to be applied for and used in achieving certain objective (s) Hence, open technology is a term that can refers to a government policy that allows users access to platforms or systems with very few constraints or restrictions on their used and this is possible through open source technology tools. () These open-source technologies are seen as the production and development philosophy of allowing end users and developers to not only see the source code of software, but modify it as well for their intended use and accomplishment. More so, open-source technology tools implied more generally to a community-based approach to creating any intellectual property (such as software) via open collaboration, inclusiveness, transparency, and frequent public updates (Dinesh, et al;2021; Wehler, 2018)

In the same lane, the concept of inclusion has also been extended to the educational field, where it refers to the idea that all students are ensured with equal opportunities; thus, one of the target objectives to be reached by today's school systems has become that of offering the same level of education to all pupils, irrespective of their varying abilities/possibilities. With this understanding, Inclusive education refers to the placement of students with special educational needs in mainstream settings, along with other students without disabilities (Al-Shammari,2019A; Dangiliena, & Kloviene, 2019) Inclusive education determines appropriate educational practices used in general education schools by offering a variety of educational services to help all students with special needs best learn according to their abilities and needs (Al-Shammari,2019A;

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Dangiliena, & Kloviene, 2019) defines inclusive education as a philosophy that brings stakeholders together to create a school environment based on acceptance and belonging within the school and the community. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) has played an influential role in the consolidation of the idea of inclusive education for children with special educational needs in schools. Inclusive education has been adopted to ensure the quality of and right to education for all learners and is now a contemporary educational approach recognized globally. (Al-Shammari,2019A; Dangiliena, & Kloviene, 2019; and Mr. Dinesh, et, al; 2021)

Uses of Open Technologies as Effective Strategies for Inclusiveness at Secondary School Level

Scholars' have identified different methods and strategies that ought to be considered in order to bring about inclusiveness in teaching & learning of disable learners and these inclusive teaching strategies refer to any number of teaching approaches that address the needs of students with a variety of backgrounds, learning modalities, and abilities in secondary school system of education. These strategies contribute to an overall inclusive learning environment in which all students perceive to be valued and able to succeed. The following identified below are some of the evidence-based strategies aim to provide secondary school teachers' teachers with an overview of inclusive teaching practices to support the inclusion of students with a diverse range of abilities and strengths. Many of these strategies are relevant for all students, while others could be relevant to some students and they include ensuring the following as identified by these scholars: (Al-Shammari,2019A; Dangiliena, & Kloviene,2019).

The Strategies for Inclusiveness in Secondary School Level

1. Keep activities and instructions short, clear and engaging
2. Consider how tasks can be tailored to different student goals, strengths, abilities and learning profiles
3. Provide a visual schedule
4. Prepare students for an upcoming transition
5. Provide a sensitive environment
6. Provide encouragement and guide learning
7. Provide a quiet area
8. Express positive regard and support
9. Facilitate student voice, autonomy and independence
10. Set clear classroom expectations
11. Provide lots of opportunities for students to engage in collaborative learning
12. Teach peers how to interact with each other
13. Support students to manage and self-regulate their emotions among others

The identified above can help learners from secondary school level to be focus and learn with ease. Similarly, major frequent breaks in activities appropriate for a given content may also help to provide concrete examples to suffice and enable them learn better such as simplified text, visual supports, breaking tasks into smaller components, using a variety of teaching strategies, and providing alternate ways for students to respond as feedback for reinforcement and motivation are some of the ways that the listed above can be achieved. Visual cues (such as schedules or cue cards) can let students in secondary school level know what is coming up, and how they should move from one activity to another. learners who find moving from one activity to another challenging will be better prepared if they are aware, it is a coming up activity More so, to provide reminders about upcoming transitions, such as visual supports, countdown timers or regular reminders are indeed very necessary. .it is equally, important to provide an environment that is sensitive to the needs of students who have experienced trauma or adverse childhood experiences and considering providing effective, actionable feedback immediately when students are learning a task. (Al-Shammari,2019B: Côte-Real, et al:2017: Gandomi, & Haider 2015)

Some of the examples of their uses for inclusiveness in teaching and learning at secondary school

1. learning community using Google Docs; Piazza & Q and A Community (Inscribe) This can help to foster an inclusive learning community among secondary school learners. Without guidance, students will often choose friends or peers like themselves for creating informal and formal learning communities. There are several tools available to help create more inclusive learning communities by providing opportunities for students to communicate with the teacher and each other. Just using these tools will not ensure inclusion, however. The teacher needs to provide structure to learning activities and establishing heterogeneous groups; determining group roles that rotate among members; structuring assignments to require

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interaction and inclusion of diverse perspectives; actively inviting, validating, and using all students' voices; etc. (Al-Shammari, 2019A; Dangiliena, & Kloviene, 2019);

2. Secondly, it can help build a community where students of secondary school rely on each other for answers to class-related questions. they are equally an online problem-solving platform that allow them to post questions (including anonymously), answer questions posted by others, see instructor notes about answers, and see which answers have been endorsed by the teacher. Students can also post images, videos, and/or equations using the built-in LaTeX editor, and edit computer code collaboratively. It's a great way for students to recognize the value and contributions of classmates with whom they may not have ordinarily meet before (Al-Shammari, 2019A; Dangiliena, & Kloviene, 2019);
3. Thirdly, it enables creating of groups for Formal and Informal Learning: This strategy can be used to create regular interaction which can go a long way to helping students reach across cultural differences and learn to value those with different identities and backgrounds. Structuring these interactions to promote inclusion of all students is more vital than ever during remote learning. This could be possible with group projects, letting groups self-form can leave some students on the margins. Consider tools that let you organize heterogeneous groups around strengths and interests. This can be with the use of surveys in Canvas or Qualtrics to ask about important characteristics, while more comprehensive teamwork programs like CATME which is available for that. Moreso, students/learners can be encouraged to use Zoom to create virtual study groups. Consider helping them learn to structure those meetings, maybe by having teaching assistants host a few review sessions first. Hosting the first few meetings may also make the groups more inclusive of all class members than might happen in self-formed study groups. These live study meetings can supplement other approaches like crowd-sourced notes or study guides in Google Docs or class Q&As occurring in Piazza or InScribe. (Al-Shammari, 2019A; Dangiliena, & Kloviene, 2019)

Specific open technologies tools for inclusive education delivery to achieve sustainable development goal (SDG) in secondary school level

It has been revealed that one in five 15-year-olds secondary school children lack minimum proficiency in Reading, Mathematics or Science at this level. (UN 2023 SDG Summit) Hence, there is the need to find cost-effective ways of delivering education of a consistently high standard to hundreds of millions of students and the scale of the challenge, already exacerbated by Covid-19 that was experienced couples of years back, this will only grow in the next decade as the world moves towards achieving UN's Sustainable Development Goal 4 in realising inclusive and equitable quality education for all. The solution lies in developing a radically better approach to evaluating and applying new technologies in our educational process (Eleni & Lanitis, 2023)

In line with the foregoing, the end justifications for the use of any technology in teaching and learning process is to ensure democratization of knowledge and as well ensure effectiveness & efficiency in learning process with the technology integration especially, for those educationally challenge learners whom have one form of disability or the other. It was in realization of this fact, that scholars identified the following open technologies tools that could be used to bring about inclusiveness in the educational delivery of disable learners: In the view of Eleni & Lanitis (2023) they identified the following as Open Technologies Tools usable at secondary school level for educational purposes:

1. Artificial Intelligence & open-source tool
2. Learning Analytics & open-source tool
3. Big data & analytics and open-source tool
4. Cloud Computing & Open-source tools
5. Full stack development & Open-source tool

Artificial intelligence at secondary school level of education

Artificial intelligence is one of the most discussed topics in the educational industry. Artificial intelligence in education is a significant technology which helps education in a number of ways. Personalized learning is one of the most important area of education that has used artificial intelligence. In personalized learning, AI helps learners to find the best course material based on ones' identity, interests and way of learning. Artificial intelligence replaced the old-fashioned classroom study with a more personalized and student-centered approach. Artificial intelligence can monitor overall performance by identifying the strength and weakness of a learner. It can rank learners based on their performance and give real-time suggestions to improve the overall performance of their studies. Artificial intelligence is very important so as to keep track, report and monitor the performance of the learners. Chen et al. (2022)

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The term “Artificial Intelligence” (AI) was first mentioned by John McCarthy in 1956 and refers to the ability of computer systems to undertake human tasks (like learning and thinking) that frequently can only be attained through human intelligence. Since the 1970s, the specific field of Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIED) has begun to influence the application of technology to instruction and learning, to improve the learning process, and promote student achievements. The aim of AIED is to establish AI-powered systems such as virtual pedagogical agents, AI robots and intelligent systems which allow flexible, engaging and personalized learning as well as to automate daily tasks of teaching (e.g. feedback and assessment). AI has been extensively used in education in different forms such as computer programs, humanoid robots, web-based chatbots, and online platforms. Chen et al. (2022) indicates the usefulness of AI in education, which may be used in the form of intelligent tutoring systems for special education, natural language processing, educational robots, performance prediction, discourse analysis, teaching evaluation, learner emotion detection and personalized learning. (AlFarsi et al., 2021). (Sadiku et al., 2021). (Southgate et al., 2019).

Learning analytics at secondary school level of education

It was established that **learning analytics** provides great potential to promote inclusiveness in terms of reducing discrimination, increasing retention among disadvantaged students, and validating particular learning designs for marginalized groups in secondary school or outside it. This open technology it's often assumed in education that its benefits are distributed, that everyone has equal chances of succeeding and that the educational ecosystem is, per se, value and power-free. One of the dominant beliefs is that all learners can succeed if they try hard enough, show grit and resilience and take control of their learning and opportunities (Reed & Jeremiah, 2017; Warren & Hale, 2020).

The definition of learning analytics was established in 2011 and is generally accepted to be the measurement, collection, analysis and reporting of data about learners and their contexts, for purposes of understanding and optimizing learning and the environments in which it occurs (UN 2023 SDG Summit)

As learning is transitioning towards being digital and datafiled, student data from digital learning environments can provide stakeholders (students, instructors, administrators, student centres, among others.) with actionable information (Khalil et al., 2018). That is, it has the potential to facilitate the design and implementation of more appropriate and effective learning pedagogies, empower active learning, identify factors impacting student success at secondary school level, and support the design of courses to meet students' individual needs (Samuelsen et al., 2019; Nguyen, Tuunanen, Gardner & Sheridan, 2021).

Cloud computing as open-source tool at secondary school level of education

The cloud has had a huge impact on the way we use the internet and organize our online lives over recent years, and is one of the most fast-developing aspects of digital technology. It affects home and work life, and is also revolutionizing online learning in school system. The impact on those with special educational needs especially in secondary school level can be even more significant. Therefore, some of the tool that can be use is a virtualized desktop from a basic laptop, PC or tablet, and this can access all the educational resources they need, from any location. This means that being of limited mobility, or having other disabilities that restrict the ability to attend school are no longer barriers to achieving a full education and excelling academically. The tool equally can provide greater and more flexible learning opportunities to everyone, regardless of their age, sex, wealth or social demographic. The use of cloud technology in secondary school would also ensure that this inclusivity also extends to those with special educational needs. It can empower children with visual, learning, age- related, mobility, hearing and speech disabilities to learn more effectively, engage and collaborate with others more easily, and express themselves more clearly. (UNESCO; 2021; ISO, 2012; Mir Ali, 2017; & G3ict, 2023)

Big data analytics and open technology tool at secondary school level of education

Researchers have proven beyond reasonable doubt that, in this era of technological applications and its use for teaching and learning, more especially at secondary school level, in dealing with learners with disabilities which demand all-inclusiveness, Big-data-analytics is one of the open-source tools that can be of immense use and this is because, the Teaching-Learning process is changing significantly due to new technological changes. The adoption of Big Data Analytics in the education sector will enables it to strengthen further and reform the system. Therefore, simply put analytics is defined as a body of knowledge consisting of research techniques in mathematics, statistics, and operations; data collection and storage; techniques of artificial intelligence like deep learning algorithms and machine learning; and big data technologies such as

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Spark, Hadoop, and Hive. In areas where such data or information is stored, analytics is instrumental. Analytics deployment is critical to differentiated services and developing new competitive strategies. (Dagiliene and Kloviene, 2019; Manyika et al., 2011; Corte-Real et al., 2017)

Advantages around the uses of Open Technologies for learning at secondary school level of Education

Researches have shown that creating inclusive classes can help learners improve their performance by enhancing their learning this implies a key starting point for inclusion is making sure everyone feels like they *belong* to the class community where they have opportunities to be heard and engage with classmates. As an effective teacher at secondary school level and with the opportunity of having access to open technologies for learning it is obvious to note that this opportunity has the following advantages for their application and used in secondary school setting as thus:

1. **Flexibility:** The biggest benefit of open technology source in secondary school is that it offers great flexibility to use the platform according to learners needs. Interoperability and connectivity with the existing infrastructure or the platform is easier to attain and it also offers the liberty to the users to make changes to its features.
2. **Reliability:** Open technology source is always under continuous review, which leads to more reliability of the platform. Programs like Apache, DNS, HTML and Perl have proven to be robust and reliable even under strict conditions. Since developers devote their time and expertise, it is updated frequently and various features get added to it from time to time in order to suit different learning needs of the children with diverse learning challenges
3. **Quality:** A software platform of open technology was developed by countless users usually aimed to improve the quality of student learning
4. **Support options:** Open source is usually available for free and it has a huge community group to support the piece of software. The community works together and creates various learning resources and modules suitable for teaching and learning at secondary school system
5. **Support collaborative learning:** Open technologies ensured and provides opportunity for students to engage and collaborates with each other during teaching & learning process. This is a unique advantage to create avenue for peer-to-peer support in learning with any kind of this technology
6. **Ensure learning anywhere any time:** In the current technological dispensation, students' learning is not expected to be through only the conventional means. Hence, open technology used for teaching and learning in secondary school breaks away from this method and allows for students' engagements anywhere, anytime

Challenges and Inhibiting factors associated with open technologies uses for inclusive learning at secondary school level of education

Inclusive education has been enacted from a rights-based philosophy, implementation which requires a change in the mindset of school principals and teachers. Although, in overall, teachers are said to support inclusion, the inclusion of different groups of children, especially those with social, emotional or behavioral difficulties, continues to be considered as problematic and which teachers are expected to managed. However, there could be some perennial challenges that could possibly affecting true success of children with disability and learning in secondary school. They can include the following:

1. Classroom teacher demand to fully support teaching and learning process at this level
2. The quality of support for students with diverse learning disability in secondary school system
3. The degree of knowledge, understanding, and expertise required by classroom teachers in secondary school level
4. The uncertainty and time-consuming nature of identifying different approaches when providing support in secondary school level
5. Poor infrastructural ICT facilities needed in secondary schools to translate related curriculum content of learners with special needs during lesson
6. Gaps in skill and competency of special class teachers in handling technology for teaching & learning at secondary school level
7. There is a shortage of computers, tablets and other devices for conducting electronic lessons and homework. For inclusiveness in learning for an inclusive classroom

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Theoretical Frame work supporting the use of open technologies for inclusive education

In the perspectives of Ertmer & Newby, (2013), noted that, learning theories provide curriculum designers with instructional strategies and techniques verified to facilitate learning in classrooms, which includes the need to implement inclusive education practices for students with special educational needs, especially in general education settings. These instructional strategies and techniques include modifications of curricula and instructional design, the development of structures, and the use of evidence-based practices. Three major theories are considered to underpin inclusive education theory. Effective inclusive education practices should incorporate ideas from each of these theories so that teachers can successfully make curricular and instructional decisions for each student. These theories are identified as: Behaviourism, Cognitivism, Constructivism. The foremost theory, behaviorisms-based inclusive education practices include the application of behaviourism in inclusive education settings, which clearly appears in the emphasis on student behaviour and performance in manipulating stimulus materials (Ertmer & Newby, 2013). Examples of behaviourism-based inclusive education practices are included in well-known instructional approaches such as explicit or direct instruction (Al-Shammari, 2019A; Steele, 2005). Theoretically, behaviourism is one of the classical theories of learning and also recognized as the oldest. Behaviorism is known as a predominant psychological model as suggested by the metaphor for, 'learning as the acquisition of stimulus-response pairs. Behaviourists 'believe the objective of the theory is to impart to the learner the knowledge of reality Behaviourism occurs when consequences are associated with the stimulus or response that is followed by reinforcement to be maintained. To summarize, the key principles of behaviourism that support education are: behaviour is learned, behaviour is governed by the setting in which it occurs, teaching does not occur without learning, learning equates to changing behaviour, behaviour is governed by what follows actions, and there needs to be a focus on the observable. While, Cognitivism-based inclusive education practices are specifically the applications of cognitivism in inclusion settings, which involves the emphasis on mental information processing and interactions to guide student learning. And lastly, Constructivism-based inclusive education practices emphasize making learning more meaningful and using real-life experiences. (Abramson, (2013; Akpan, & Beard 2016; Al-Shammari, 2019A)

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is important to stressed that, Inclusive Education is an on-going, long-lasting process that needs to be pursued with determination, despite the significant challenges it poses; all the available/ suitable means should be employed, including technological tools that are widely recognized as having high potential to help in achieving SDG-Goals, with particular reference to goal-4 which is to be fully achieved by 2030 of the new targets. Therefore, the used of open technologies to deliver effective curriculum for inclusive learning at secondary school system will be a mirage without integrating the right type of technology this is so because of the promise of contemporary technology lives in what these tools can do that previous learning and educational technologies could not meaning they are open, connected, individualizing, free accessibility, flexible to be modified to suite a given learning content of a special needs and above all free to be use with no cost implications

Recommendation

The following recommendations are made for more effective uses of open technologies tools for inclusiveness in the classroom setting of children with disability as thus:

1. Classroom teacher demands, in relation to curriculum interpretation with special need learners should be viable and achievable
2. The quality of support for learners with diverse challenges to cater for diverse needs should be available
3. The degree of knowledge, understanding, and expertise required by classroom teachers should be gauged as been appropriate for learners with disability
4. The uncertainty and time-consuming nature of identifying different approaches when providing support, should be resolved
5. Needed infrastructural ICT facilities needed in schools to translate related curriculum content of learners with special needs during lesson should be ensured
6. Gaps in skill and competency of special class teachers in handling technology for teaching & learning should be taking care of through training and re-training programme

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Role of Teachers in Effective Implementation of Teaching and Learning Processes at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

*Burwa Umar Muhammad Ph.D.¹

Email: umar.muhd@udusok.edu.ng; umarmuhd619@yahoo.com

Tel: +2348037855482, +2348080408743

Muhammad Rabi'u^{2,3}

Email: rabiumuhammad52@yahoo.com

Tel: +2348036010685.

Abubakar Ibrahim Sahabi¹

Email: @udusok.edu.ng, ibrahimsahabi@gmail.com

Tel: +2348037855482,

¹Department of Educational Foundations, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

²Department of Education, Maryam Abacha American University of Niger, Maradi

³Department of Education, Maryam Abacha American University of Nigeria, Kano

Abstract

This paper x-rays the Role of Teachers in effective Implementation of teaching and learning processes at secondary school level of education in Nigeria. Hence, there is need for quality teachers through which education industry can be effectively utilized for transforming Nigeria for the socioeconomic growth and national development. Teachers are the main determinants of quality in education, but if they are apathetic, uncommitted, lazy, unmotivated, immoral, anti-social, demoralized and unethical, the whole nation is doomed. It was discovered that, problems characterizing teacher education in Nigeria include lack of training and re-training. The paper concluded that, a teacher has a tremendous role to play in the realization of the National objectives based on the National policy on Education via Millennium Development Goals. To provide this important instrument for the socioeconomic and National development of the Giant of Africa which in turn will lead to the transformation of Nigeria. Recommendations were made, these include among others adequate funding of the sector at all levels.

Keywords: Secondary Education, Teaching and Learning

Introduction

Teaching as Profession is the bedrock of all other profession and therefore, it is the foundation of all profession on human sustainable development. A Teacher is a person who impart knowledge to his pupils, imparts good morals by showing good examples, teach discipline, encourage good habits, discourage bad ones both within and outside the class room which help the pupils not only in the school, but even their various communities, teaching is a profession that has prescribed educational programme (s) and objective (s) through which teachers acquire knowledge and skills needed for an effective, meaningful, successful service delivery. From time-to-time, teachers have to decide which techniques would be most suitable or appropriate for any prevailing circumstances in the classroom. Again, teaching is a multi-dimensional activity that is geared towards impacting knowledge and change in the existing behavior of a child through instruction (s). In the Art of teaching, there is no single method that can be described or considered as most suitable or not appropriate. What is best depends on the teacher, the ability of students to assimilate and comprehend the learning situation and the content of the lesson. Both selection and application of methodology depends on the teacher's ability to achieve the set objectives (Mahuta, 2009).

When the concept of "teaching" is mentioned, different people will have different conception of it. Some may completely mis construct what teaching is. It is therefore, imperative that prospective teachers should as a matter of their preparation for the task of teaching, be aware of the right conception of teaching. Whether we view teaching as an occupation or a profession, we must acknowledge the fact that teaching is both an art and science. As an art it can be practiced under skillful tutelage towards perfection, and as a science it can be learned. Teachers are the catalyst of the expected changes on the society. The National Policy on Education (UPE) lays emphasis on professional development of teachers as it recognizes "in-service as an integral part of continuing teacher education and shall also take care of all inadequacies". The teacher being tool for implementation of UBE need to be professionally develop, such that he can bring the desired changes in the society. This professional competence becomes essential because the validity of any educational system naturally is dependent upon the

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quality of the teaching and the availability of competence teachers. Giving credence to this statement Adesokan (2000) referred to the teacher as the spark and key man in the Drive to progress in the educational enterprise (Goshe, 2007)

From the afore-mentioned, one can evidently conclude that teaching is not just being able to stand in front of your pupils and speak the language they understand but the ability to use appropriate communicative techniques to facilitate and promote their understanding. In view of this, therefore, people should discard the wrong notion that everyone can teach. Having a university degree is not a sufficient qualification for one to teach. Teaching qualification is pre-requisite for dissemination of knowledge. The right of teachers in freedom of association, to collectively bargain and to undertake industrial actions are recognized in several labor international organization (ILO) recommendations and conventions. The low or meagre salary of teachers in Nigeria, the non-payment of salaries for prolonged periods of time in some Local Government Education Authorities, and the hiring of teachers on fixed-term contracts, create situation of low esteem, demoralization and even precariousness, all of which have negative impacts on the teachers' work as well as their dignity. This subsequently affects the general development of the youth and the nation at large. In recent years, the importance of education has been rediscovered; the World Conference on Education for All in Jomtiem in 1990 saw government leaders' efforts to make global commitments. The UN World Summit for development in Copenhagen, held on March 1995, stressed the need for a new deal for investment in education. In its Policy report "Strategies and Priorities" published in August 1996, the World Bank has emphasized the importance of investing in education. Any education authority or government that seriously wishes to improve education has to recognize the key role, which teachers play in the education process. One of the important measures that can be taken to improve the working condition of teachers. Quality education requires teachers whose high qualifications are socially recognized. In order to recruit qualified young people into the teaching profession and to teachers in teaching profession there is need to improve the working conditions of teachers in Nigeria. It is a fact that, the low salary scale for teachers coupled with the problems of lack of status of recognition by the members of the society and poor conditions of service are seriously affecting the teaching profession in Nigeria (Mahuta, 2009).

National Objectives

Abdul Malik (2007) posited that for us to focus on the attainment of the millennium development goals, the National Policy on Education (2014) outlined the five National objectives section 1 under the philosophy of Nigerian Education as follows:

1. A free and Democratic Society;
2. A just and egalitarian Society;
3. A united, strong and self-reliant nation;
4. A great dynamic economy;
5. A land of bright and full opportunities of all citizens

The above National objectives are expected to be fully disseminated to all teachers during training as they will be required to guide all students/pupils in their care to digest the objective to serve as their guiding principles when they conduct themselves any in Nigeria. Teachers would be models that should be seen by their Pupils to be practicing every aspect of the objectives within the society. The effort to attain the objectives will go a long way to prepare ground for the attainment of the Millennium Goals. There are various definitions of teaching given by various scholars. Some widely accepted definitions of teaching include the following:

1. The act of practice of imparting to a learner knowledge, skills, values and norms that will be useful to the total development of the individual (Ekwueme, 2001)
2. Teaching is an art of imparting whole-heartedly useful knowledge in various forms and ways, formal or informal and by using all the communication media possible under proper guidance to enlighten the learner (Abdul Malik, 2007)
3. Teaching can be considered as any means by which an individual creates an understanding of a new knowledge on the part of the learner. This shows that this could be oral, practical, planned or unplanned, but it enables the learners to acquire values or skills which they had not known. It involves explaining, demonstrating, guiding and counseling by the teacher in order to effect a change in the learner (Abdul Malik, 2007)

Scope and Purpose of Secondary Education in Nigeria's Context

Secondary education is provided for children after primary education, that is, before tertiary education. It is aimed at developing a child better than the primary level, because it is obvious that primary education is insufficient for children to

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acquire literacy, numeracy, and communication skills (Ige, 2011; Yusuf, 2009). Such education is provided in secondary school, which can be owned by government (State or Federal), individuals or community. It is divided into two phases as follows:

Concept of Learning

Over the years, psychologists and educators realized that it is very difficult to define learning in a precise way. Some psychologists view learning as 'change' Behaviorist like B.F Skinner the 'father of behaviorism' argue that learning place when certain environmental conditions occur, apparently independent of any conscious human development. Thus, those who have adopted a behavioral view point describe learning as a 'relatively permanent process that results from practice and is reflected in changes in performance. Human learning basically is concerned with acquiring knowledge skills and attitude. We talk about learning how to read and write, how to drive a car, how to make a basket, sew dresses, operate a typewriter, memorize the line of a play play the piano or flute and how to decorate our homes. We learn about societies, about science and Technology and about values. All these acts are new performances which we acquire with reinforced practice. Learning is a fascinating interactive process involving the student (the learner) and the teacher within a learning environment (Mbakem & Ike, 2017)

The Beginning of Teaching in Nigeria

Teaching is one of the oldest and most important occupation in any society in the world. Teaching as an old craft, is as old as this world. Islam and Christianity are two dominant religions that to a great extent, influence all educational matters in Nigeria. Islam predated Christianity in Nigeria and Islam education has a long history in the country. The origin of formal teaching in Nigeria was intricately linked with the history of formal or western education. It should be noted that the discussion of western education in this country is directly connected to the missionary's activities. The first missionaries landed in Nigeria in 1822 (Ekwueme, 2001). With the coming of missionaries into this country, they established typical missionary schools. They first established primary school at Badagry where they trained the first generation of Teachers. With the establishment of schools come the need to train teachers who will carry out the task of imparting knowledge to the young ones. But the basic aims of missionary's school focused on winning souls for Christ. The missionaries were consciously or unconsciously the agent of oppressive and exploitative foreign presence There was no distinction between a school teacher and a catechist, for the teacher was basically an evangelist in addition to the teaching job.

Formal teacher education programmes begin in Nigeria in 1896 when St. Andrews College was established by the Church missionary society at Oyo to train People for the services of the CMS Yoruba mission (Abdul Malik, 2007). Some of those Institutions were meant to train teachers for the primary schools. It is important that we should examine the status of teaching during that time. The then teaching in Nigeria was in two fields, first at as an apprentice teacher and then on the job training. The missionaries provided the curriculum to be taught in the schools and also set up professional standard for the teacher and teacher education programmes. The syllabus consisted mainly of New Testament, preaching and theology, Hygiene, Geography, History, English, Carpentry and Mensory. The first category of teachers included primary school leavers who were sent into the classrooms on probationary basis. The teachers were under close supervision by European masters and Pastors. Those teachers were serving as auxiliary teachers. After teaching for a number of years were sent for the further training at teacher training schools. The teacher then entered into the second category. With the intervention of colonial government into the educational scene in 1882, more teacher training colleges were established in different parts of Nigeria. Some of the Institutions include: Baptist Training College Ogbomoso, (1897) St. Paul's Training Colleges, Akwa (1904). Oran Training Institute Ibadan, (1905). United Missionary College, Ibadan (1928) and St. Charles Training College Onitsha, (1929) as well as Teachers Training College Katsina (1929). The schools were meant for on-the-job training of teachers. The two-tier system of teacher training programme, recommended by Phelps-Stoke commission of 1911, was available for the education of teachers-the Elementary Teacher Certificate (TTC) or Grade III Certificate and High Elementary Teacher Certificate or Grade II (HETC). For the Grade III teacher's Certificate primary (standard six) certificate and years of experience (obtained from auxiliary service) were qualification for admission into Grade III Elementary Teacher Training Colleges. Having to teach for another two years or more after obtaining Grade III Certificate, would earn such candidate qualification to go for another two-year training for the Grade II High Elementary Teacher's Certificate. This system of teacher training continued in Nigeria for long time until 1950's. That was the state of teaching in Nigeria until the dawn of educational, economic and political realities of 1950's, 1960's and 1970's. During that period schools had rapidly increased both (public and private) as response to population explosion hence the need for more teachers. In an apparent response to that, the colonial government in 1959 set up the Ashby commission to look into the future needs of tertiary education in the country. As part of the recommendation of the

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commission, the federal government gave approval for the establishment of advanced teacher's training colleges in the country which later become colleges of education for the award of Nigerian Certificate of education (NCE).

The decades of 1960's and 1970's was turning points in the history of teaching in particular and education in general. There were the National Curriculum Conference and National Seminar on Policy of Education in 1969 and 1973 respectively which eventually led to the National Policy of Education in 1977. 1976, when the Universal Primary Education (UPE) scheme was launched. Teacher training schools were established to train teachers across the federation. The schools trained teachers (prospective) from nine months to two years, thus the influx of every body into teaching including the dropouts and dregs of educational system. This situation remains unchanged till today (Ekwueme, 2001). In 1939, a nine-month Teacher Training course in Agriculture was introduced at Ibadan and Umuahia. However, when Nigeria attained independence, the government opened Universities and Colleges of Education offering professional qualification, in teaching such as N.C.E, B.A. (Ed) B.Sc. (Ed) and B.Ed. respectively (Bamgbaiye, 2005).

Presently the following Institutions are responsible for the training of teachers:

1. Colleges of Education
2. Faculties of Education
3. Institute of Education
4. National Teachers Institute (NTI)
5. Schools of Education for Nigerian Languages (NINLAN)
6. National Mathematical Center (NMC)

Professionalization of Teaching at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Professionalization of teaching especially at secondary level of education in the country have been a point of discussion over the years Ekwueme (2001) posited that, the word profession is intimately related to the type of job/occupation from which an individual earns a living. According to him there is an outright ambiguity in the way many people use this word. This has made people to call themselves and to be called by others as professionals. It therefore, appeared pertinent to define the word profession. Some of the possible definitions of the word "profession" include the following:

1. An occupation or an employment (for which one has a calling) especially one that is possible only after advanced education and specialized training, and above all respected in the society, as honorable.
2. A calling in which one professed to have acquired special training used by either instructing, guiding or advising others or serving them in some Art
3. A kind of job that required its practitioner to possess a sound education and special training before he/she can be recognized as professionals.
4. A career in which all practitioners are guided by an effective code of conduct entry and exit measures. Examples of a profession are Teaching, Law, Medicine, Accountancy, Engineering etc.

Almost all occupations of the world have professional bodies that guide, regulate and direct their activities. The teaching profession at secondary level of education is not an exception. The teaching profession therefore has code of conduct and these are being enforced by the Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) and the Nigerian Union of Teachers (NUT) the enforcement, restriction and protection of the ethics of the teaching profession and the conduct are the sole responsibility of the employer. In this case, the Board or body of education has the right to execute and protect the provisions of the ethics of the teaching profession and its conduct. Workers can only be recognized based on their Union level of professional competence and the ability to stay by the body that binds or unites them together as a lawful professional body or professional Association. Nigerian teachers have the Nigerian Union of Teachers (NUT). Though it is a trade union, it equally helps to bring the Nigerian teachers together. However, at the moment it is still a teachers' union, which is restricted to Primary and Secondary Schools Teachers in Nigeria. (Mahuta, 2009)

Professionalizing teaching at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Major problems associated with professionalizing teaching especially at secondary school level of education in Nigeria in spite of the numerous problems facing the teaching profession and secondary school teachers in Nigeria, there are steps to be taken in order to better professionalize secondary school level of education teaching in Nigeria. Some of these steps or ways are as follows:

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1. The Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) should live up to the expectation by ensuring that only trained secondary schools' teachers who are qualified to be in the teaching profession, remain in it.
2. There should be a strong union especially at secondary school level of education to control the entire activities of the teaching profession such as entry, courses, code of ethics and certification.
3. The reward received includes that of prestige accorded to the profession as well as earnings, which are all symbols of the professional's achievement
4. There should be strictness in admission and certification of people into the profession.
5. Teachers without teaching qualification should be made to acquire such
6. The teaching profession should not admit or permit others who do not belongs to the profession to practice it so as to maintain the characteristics of control of entry.

There should be a special salary scale for the members of the teaching profession in Nigeria. Presently, teachers in Nigeria are seriously agitating for a special salary for teachers of Secondary Schools. The salary scale being agitated for by teachers is called 'Teachers Salary Scale (TSS). Doubtless, the teaching profession in Nigeria is suffering from societal misplacement and neglect. This attitude has made education to suffer and is resulting a decline in educational standards. Yet education remains a strong tool for the development of the society. There is therefore, the need for the TRCN to ensure the implementation of the Teachers Salary Scale (TSS), especially secondary school teachers in order to improve the remuneration given to teachers.

Problems of Professionalizing Teaching at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

There are quite a number of problems bedeviling the professionalization of teaching especially at secondary school level of education in Nigeria. Some of these problems are as follows:

1. Unrealistic and wrong perception of the teaching profession held by the general public. Unfortunately, this is promoted by some members of the profession.
2. Functional disagreement among secondary school teachers about the purpose of education, and ignorance about contradictions across desired functions
3. The question of who is really in control of the standards, and policies encompassing secondary level of education and educational reforms in Nigeria.
4. The problems of occupational insecurity coupled with the lack of training and upgrading the general conduct of the ethics of the teaching profession especially at secondary school in the Country.
5. The teaching profession in Nigeria has suffered and is still suffering due to many factors, namely: i) Competence factors ii) Quality factors iii) Institutional factors iv) Economic factors and v) National factors

Ways of improving the status of teaching at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

The following are some of the ways of improving the status of Teaching at secondary school level of education in Nigeria they are:

1. Secondary school teachers are not only restricted to providing knowledge and qualifications, but also universal ethical principles of social justice, tolerance and peace. They also play important role in the economic and cultural development of the society. Secondary school teachers share the concerns of parents and youths concerning the sociolect-economic development of Nigeria. However, teachers are facing pressures from the governments and employees who limit their performance by poor remuneration and therefore alter the nature of their responsibilities by imposing on them undue adjustment to the serious economic, social and cultural problems stemming from the current global and social challenges.
2. It is important to grant the teaching profession at secondary level of education a high status, not just for the sake of quality of education, but also for the progress of society as a whole. Society needs quality secondary school education and thus, highly qualified teachers, to ensure social and economic development.

Teacher Education at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Teacher Education Programmes in Nigeria are the designed educational programmes, whose contents are meant to offer special training for intending teachers such as the pre-service and the in-service teachers. The global trend in Teacher Education seeks the improvement and systematic application of recent strategies, methods, innovations in education to meet up with the past developing and global challenges in society. The only possible means of equipping the individual is through the provision of skills, information and knowledge for advancement. Teacher Education Programmes provide valuable knowledge, information and skills for teacher-trainees. This is to equip them to be able to face the challenges of training others

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in the society states that a coherent teacher education programme should systematically embrace integrated curriculum innovation, which reflects the social, economic and political environment of the modern society, an educational innovation which seeks to succeed, must necessarily involve a reorientation of teachers' education to accept new challenges. (Oyekan, 2000)

Teacher education Programmes in Nigeria should enhance human quality; embrace innovations, bring about social changes and integrate individuals to the society with the knowledge acquired for problem solving. A functional programme is that which promotes efficiency and effective display of the knowledge and skills acquired by the teachers and teacher-trainees. However, potential teachers should be professionally rational, positively functional, and administratively competent. Therefore, they should be flexible and liberal in executing their duties. These qualities or attributes will allow a teacher to handle the teaching problems in the educational environment. It is in view of the importance attached to Teacher Education Programmes in Nigeria that the National Policy on Education (2014) states that, since no Education system can rise above the quality of its Teachers Teacher education shall continue to be given major emphasis in all Educational Planning and development. The minimum qualification for entry into the teaching profession shall be the Nigerian Certificate Of Education (NCE). The fact that, no education system may rise above the quality of its teachers, makes Teacher Education Programmes to occupy a vital portion in the planning and implementation of educational policies and programmes (Mahuta, 2009).

The Goals of Teacher Education at secondary level of education in Nigeria

The National Policy on Education (2013) outlines the goals of Teacher Education Programmes in Nigeria as follows:

1. to produce highly motivated, conscientious and efficient classroom teachers for all levels of our educational system
2. to encourage further, the spirit of enquiry and creativity in teachers
3. to help teachers to fit into social life of the community and society at large and enhance their commitment to national goals
4. to provide teachers with the intellectual and professional background adequate for their assignment and to make them and to make them adaptable to any changing situation not only in the life of their country, but in the wider world.

Qualities of Secondary School Teacher

Teaching profession has its own ethics, rules and so its professional teachers ought to have some basic qualities. An ideal teacher to do his job satisfactorily needs to possess the following:

1. Bright and cheerful disposition
2. Scholarship/expertise- without this one can never be a teacher i.e. must know his subject matter very well and can make others to understand the subject
3. Firmness and determination- always stick to institutional policy and feel detrimental to succeed in your task.
4. Paragon (Model) of virtues – always practice what you preach
5. A good command of language- an important asset for a teacher clarity, fluency- not too fast or too slow but moderate with clear voice, be modified of grammatical mistakes
6. Fair judgment and impartiality- in or outside the school treat all equally, especially in class discipline and performance assessment
7. Sincerity- be man of truth and frankness
8. Adaptability- needs to be daily aspire, expand knowledge, ability to respond intelligently to new similar problems to promote own states
9. Punctuality and time consciousness- be practiced as much as possible
10. Satisfactory inter-staff relationship has a good relationship with other teaching and non-teaching staff for the job satisfaction
11. Sociability out the school- good understanding between the school and immediate community.

The Nature of Teaching at Secondary School level of Education

Three focal points in Education: Teacher, Child and subject. Teaching is the relationship which we established between these three. Conclusively the role of a teacher in transforming Nigeria ought to reflect the following:

1. Guides and counsels, the masses professionally
2. Onward looking for a better capacity building and education unreluctantly
3. Obedient and loyal to the constituted authority to serve as a model
4. Demonstrates discipline and orderliness both in words and in action
5. Teaches and trains to build a better future generation

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6. Earnestly erases illiteracy and ignorance steadily and systematically
7. Appear to be an agent of civilization and academic excellence
8. Curves inefficiently and serve as a Centre of excellence at all level of Education
9. Heads towards honesty, hard work, commitment and sacrifice to duty
10. Endeavors to promote expertise at all spheres of knowledge
11. Rear his clients well to help remove away the darkness of life from the society
(Hakimi, 2007)

Conclusion

It could be concluded that, a teacher has a tremendous role to play in the realization of the National objectives based on the National policy on Education via Millennium Development Goals. To provide this important instrument for the socio-economic and National development of the Giant of Africa which in turn will lead to the transformation of Nigeria emphasis should be given on teacher and teaching pupil and the immediate community, improvement of learning environment, development of appropriate instructional materials and their usage, effective and efficient school management and multi-optional Teacher Education Programmes. If these are given adequate attention in the provision of education in Nigeria, it would actualize the nation's agenda in producing elites that would man different sectors of the nation's economy.

Recommendations

1. Adequate funding of the secondary school level of education should be given priority in line with UNESCO minimum requirement of 26% of the Total budget of a given country to be allocated to Education.
2. Training and Re-training of secondary school teachers via in-service and on the job training which include among others, attending Conferences both Local and International, Workshops, Seminars and other Refresher Courses for capacity building should be facilitated by educational managers.
3. New Proposed Teacher's Salary Scale (TSS) and other incentives should be re-visited and implemented as this will in turn boost secondary school teacher's Morale to put more inputs for the realization of secondary school Educational goals and objectives for National development.
4. Re-visiting the previous Professional Teacher Development Programme 2013 Cluster Training Centers from December 2013 to March 2014 in the 23 Local Governments of Sokoto State organized by the Faculty of Education and Extension Services, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto in Collaboration with UBE Sokoto State to be approved as Permanent and NCE awarding Centers based on contact Sessions.
5. TETFund intervention on Staff Development should consider incorporating Secondary Schools Teachers Training as a priority for the realization of the nations' vision to be a reality.

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Social Studies Education: Panacea for Tackling Corruption in Nigeria at Basic Level of Education

*Ashiru, Abdulwahab¹

Email: abdulwahabashiru@yahoo.com

Tel: +2348034764975

Muhammad, Sule¹

Email: muhammadsule78@gmail.com

Tel: +2347030475088

Adamu, Nuradeen Kanon-Hakki¹

Email: kanonhaki02@gmail.com

Tel: +2348063194702

¹Department of Educational Foundations, Federal University Gusau

Abstract

This Study is aimed to Examine Social Studies Education Panacea for Tackling Corruption in Nigeria at basic level of education. Social Studies is the subject saddled with the responsibility to contribute in tackling the social, economic, and political problems in Nigeria. The thrust of the paper is to discuss the concept of Social Studies, Philosophy of Social Studies, Objectives of Social Studies, the paper also discussed the concept of corruption, types of corruption, causes of corruption, social implication of corruption, educational implication of corruption in Nigeria and Social Studies education panacea for tackling corruption in Nigeria at basic level of education. The paper concluded that the causes of corruption in Nigeria are: political interference, lack or inadequate welfare package, greediness, selfishness among others. The paper also identified that the implication of corruption in Nigeria are: it slows down economic development and produces unproductive graduates. The paper has the following suggestion: Attitudinal change, Teaching of Social Studies, Good Leadership, Strict and severe punishment, Welfare package, creating awareness on the dangers of corruption.

Keywords: Social Studies, Education, Panacea, Corruption

Introduction

Corruption is one of the social problems that is bedeviling Nigerian and could be found in all the sectors. Corruption is innate and deep seated in Nigeria particularly in the public sector (Okolo and Raymond, 2014). Corruption is any act or behavior or omission, committed intentionally or not to influence the action of another, the influential and the influenced respectively has corrupted a system which is detrimental to the entire society (Okolo and Raymond, 2014). Corruption is a behavior which deviates from the formal duties of a public role because of pecuniary or status gains which violates rules against the exercise of certain types of influence (Aigbengbe, 2010). It implies that is a bad attitude of greediness and selfishness exhibited by the perpetrator. This act has become the order of the day in Nigeria and many countries of the world and made Nigeria to be rated 24 out of 100 as put forward by (Transparency International, 2023). This clearly indicated that Nigeria is yet to get out of the Menace of corruption because there is corruption in all spheres of our lives which could be attributed to various factors as put forward by different scholars. The purpose of this paper therefore, is to identify the causes as well as socio-economic, and educational implications of corruption in Nigeria with the view to tackle it from Social Studies angle. According to (Adeboye and Obaje, 2016) the causes of corruption in Nigeria are: greediness, poor reward system, wrong home training, peer influence, poor condition of service. (Ribadu in Tikuma 2009) posited that the causes of corruption in Nigeria could be traced to the 29 years of military rule in Nigeria. Others blame it to tribal and ethnic factors as the fountain of Nigeria corruption. Corruption has eaten deep into the fabric of almost all Nigerian society which in turn threatened the socio-economic growth and development of the country. Corruption is a stigma that destroys the reputation of affected country. It lowers investment there by lowering economic growth of the country (Ola, 2014). Nigeria society encourages corrupt practices and this is higher at the basic educational level. Teachers encourage corruption through extortion, collection of gifts items, receiving of bribes and unethical favoritism. Corruption causes a reduction in quality of teaching and learning as many teachers are not rewarded the way they should. A corollary of corruption is late payment, delays or refusals in payment for services

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already rendered what directly impacts on the country's educational enterprises (Adeboye and Obaje, 2016) hence, the need for the Social Studies Education panacea for tackling corruption in Nigeria.

Concept of Social Studies

Definitions varies according to situations, aspirations and expectation of the people. A critical analysis of the definition of Social Studies in Educational literature indicated that Social Studies Education has been defined in the following ways: Irmiya and Bitrus (2019) express Social Studies as an integrated subject that exposes learners to desirable knowledge, attitude, values and skills necessary for effective socio-civic life. Aigbangbe (2010) opined that Social Studies education is a problem solving course of study. It deals with societal issues and problems and prescribes effective ways of solving them. Nwanko (2018) Social Studies education would produce detribalized, patriotic, flexible and objective citizens who could be able to adapt to changes in order to suit the prevailing needs and interest of the nation. Thus Social Studies education helps in three critical areas of values oriented education, civil Education and Environmental education. Uzokife and Obaje (2022) submitted that Social Studies education among other school subject is primarily design an taught in schools to address issues relating to tight type of values, attitudes and behavior with a view to achieving sustainable development. Farmson (2020) posited that Social Studies is meant to provide coordinated, systematic study which draws upon such disciplines as anthropology, economics, geography, history, law philosophy, political science religion and sociology, as well as appropriate contents from the humanities, mathematics and natural science. Social Studies is a comprehensive adequate and total study of man in his environment with the aim to lead realizes the potentials and uses them to solve various problems. Thus, social, economic and political problems could be solved using the subject of Social Studies. Through the teaching of good values of selflessness, contentment, justice, tolerance, fair play, positives attitude, and self-reliant etc.

Philosophy of Social Studies Education

The philosophy of Social Studies presupposes that the curriculum package envisaged in this “functionality principle” necessarily demands that Social Studies education need to be problem solving; it must not only possess a relative and transfer value but to display a purpose that relates to life situations (Aderalege, 1980). These criteria of the philosophy of social that Social Studies represent a relevant curriculum package which aims at integrating many related subject areas and discipline which offer to the young learners a “holistic” portrait of a man and his knowledge of society. Social Studies should not only be Nigerian in orientation but must portrait her as a dynamic and developing society. Based on this philosophy, young learners need to be equipped not only with necessary tools for making their own contributions in terms of societal changes but also giving directions of these changes that the framework of Nigeria. This philosophy must be actively oriented and need to offer learners the opportunity to practice skills which will assist them function effectively at school and in life situation (Okam, 1998)

Objectives of Social Studies Education

Social studies as stated earlier was introduced into Nigerian schools and made a core or compulsory subject at primary and junior secondary schools to help achieve the four national educational aims and objectives namely:

1. The inculcation of national consciousness and national unity.
2. The inculcation of the right type of values and attitudes for the survival of the individual and the Nigerian society.
3. The training of the mind in the understanding of the world around, and
4. The acquisition of appropriate skills, abilities and competencies both mental and physical as equipment for the individual to live in and contribute to the development of his society.

In line with the above national educational aims and objectives, social studies educators and educationalists in Nigeria formulated among others the following general objectives of social studies educators and educationists in Nigeria formulated among others the following general objectives of social studies teaching in schools:

- i. To create an awareness and an understanding of our evolving social and physical environment as a whole in its natural, manmade, cultural and spiritual resources for national development.
- ii. To develop a capacity to learn and to acquire certain basic skills, including not only those of listening, speaking, reading, writing and of calculation, but also those skills of hand and head together with those of observation, analysis, and inferences which are essential for making sound social economic and political judgment.
- iii. To ensure the acquisition of that relevant body of body of knowledge and information which is an essential pre-requisite to personal development as well as to a positive personal contribution to the betterment of mankind.

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- iv. To develop a sympathetic appreciation of the diversity and inter-dependence of all members of the local community, and the wider national and international community.
- v. To develop in students' positive attitudes of togetherness, comradeship and co-operation towards a healthy nation; the inculcation of appropriate values of honesty, integrity, hard work, fairness and justice at work and play as one's contribution to the development of the nation.
- vi. To encourage learners to appreciate that all the things they have learnt are interrelated through social studies it is possible to present knowledge as a whole instead of a series of specialized fragments.

To achieve the above national educational aims and objectives and the formulated general studies objectives in schools, there is the need for proper education and re-education of social studies teachers in the areas of methodology and evaluation strategies. There is also the need for production of relevant text books and other instructional materials. Equally importance is that teachers and students should be provided with conducive atmosphere for effective teaching and learning process. (Argungu, 2000)

Concept of Corruption

Oganwu (2016) defined Corruption as deviation from existing norm for personal benefit. Omale mumini and salisu (2018) see it as a form of dishonesty or unethical conduct by a person entrusted with a position of authority, often to acquire personal benefit. Adebayo Funsho and Obaje (2020) submitted that corruption is a behavior which deviates from the formal duties of a public role because of pecuniary or status gains which violates rules against the exercise of certain types of influence Jarome and Anekwe (2022) View it as; allowing self to get influenced for personal interest at the detriment of the need of the society. Dramola (2020) posited it as a social phenomenon which manifests in various human actions such as deceit, wickedness, selfishness, embezzlement of public fund or property, which could be described as primitive accumulation of wealth, moral degradation, bribery, insatiability, covetousness etc. Wikipedia (2017) defined it as form of dishonesty or unethical behavior by a person(s) entrusted with position of authority. Ekechukwu (2021) opined Corruption as dishonest, illegal or moral behaviors carried out by those in positions of authority or entrusted with something or an office. It is an irresponsible unmatured behavior displayed by trusted people for personal gains. This act is needed to be arrested in all respects before it consumes the entire nation.

Types of Corruption

According to Aigbange (2010) Corruption can be categorized into the following:

1. **Bribery:** This involves the payment (in money or kind) that is taken or given in a corrupt relationship and includes kickbacks, gratitude, pay off, sweeteners, greasing palms etc.
2. **Fraud:** This involves some kind of trickery, swindle and deceit, counterfeiting, racketing, smuggling and forgery.
3. **Embezzlement:** This is the theft of public resources by public officials. It is when a state official steals from the public institution in which he is employed. This is very common in Nigeria.
4. **Extortion:** This is money and other resources extracted by the use of coercion, violence or threat. It is often seen as extraction from below (the police and custom officials are the main culprits in Nigeria but things are changing now)
5. **Favoritism:** This is a mechanism of power abuse implying a highly brazed distribution of state resources to favored friends, family members and close associates
6. **Nepotism:** This is a special form of favoritism in which an office holder prefers his /her kinfolk and family members. This occurs when one is exempted from the application of certain laws or regulations or given undue preference in the allocation of scarce resources.

Causes of Corruption

Adebayo et'al (2020) maintained that the root cause of this evil is materialism, so materialism is the only cause for quest for corruption in education. A society which glorifies the fruits of materialism inevitably sow the seeds of corruption. In the same vein tikuma (2009) indicated that factors responsible for corruption in Nigeria are: poor salaries and social welfare, departure from traditional economic system, self-aggrandizement. Adebayo and Obaje (2016) maintained that it is common to see that when the government does not cater for all the basic needs of the people any more, there is tendency for people to get corrupted inorder to be able to cater for such needs. Greediness, poor reward system, wrong home training, peer influence, poor condition of service. Ola (2014) alluded that the causes of corruption in Nigeria are: Low civil service salaries and poor working conditions, with few incentives and rewards for efficient and effective performance, are strong incentives for corruption in Nigeria. Other factors are less effective government works with slow budget procedure, lack of transparency, inadequate strategies vision and weak

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monitoring mechanisms make a Nigeria a fertile the environment for corrupt practices. Aigbangbe (2010) maintained that the causes of corruption in Nigeria can be summed up as great inequality in distribution of wealth; political office as primary means of access to wealth; conflict between changing moral code; the weakness of social and government law enforcement mechanism, the get rich quick syndrome, poor welfare package, influence of peer group and the absence of a strong sense of national pride.

Socio-Economic implication of corruption in Nigeria

Rosemary and Bonmwa (2014) posited that massive and extensive corruption in Nigeria has depleted the stock of capital requisite for development just as it does in any other political economy. Corruption had severe negative consequences on the economic growth and development of Nigeria. Where improper conducts such as fraud and bribery are prevalent, the public effects and severe. Corruption has adversely affected governance and the larger social structure. It has crippled the nation's ability to deliver for it citizens' welfare of even their minimum social and economic right. This generally has led to a retardation of economic of economic development and deterioration whatever public infrastructure has been put in place. According to Peter Sunday and Ndem (2012) maintained that corrupt economic practices tend to increase the cost of doing business in the country. The corrupt resources transferred abroad or used for importation of non- essential good act as drain on the economy, depriving it of the ability to generate jobs for people domestically. In another sense the smuggling of foreign made products can cause unemployment by undercutting the competitive sales of the existing legitimate industries there by forcing them to operate under capacity. When a corrupt socio-political-ecomomic system enthrone mediocrity in position of leadership, a vicious system of mediocrity emerges and this tends to be self-perpetuating. Corruption has led to a chronic deficit in Nigeria balance of payments both directly and indirectly. Indirectly the leakage-effects corruption imposes on GDP can jeopardize the country's balance of payments positions. Corruption tends to generate and perpetuate distributional inequality in both economic and political powers in a society. The effectiveness of economic policies can be seriously undermined by corruption as is currently the case in Nigeria. Adebayo and Obaje (2016) pointed out that corruption has eaten deep into the fabric of almost all Nigerian society, which has inturn threatened the economic growth and development of the country. Corruption has destroyed the value system of Nigerian society and is killing the conscience of the nation. Ola (2014) opined that corruption stiple economic growth, reduced economic efficiency and development despite the enomous resources in the country. Corruption creates negative national image and loss of much needed revenue. It devalues the quality of human life, robs schools, agricultural sectors, hospital and welfare services of funds. Corruption is a stigma that destroys the reputation of affected country. It lowers investment there by lowering economic growth of the country. Bamboye (2018) realizes that the impact of corruption includes among others, poor economic growth, poor infrastructural development, underutilization of human and natural resources distorted policies and poor policy implementation and a colossal loss of public funds and poor in flow of foreign direct investment. The issue of corruption in Nigeria is endemic and pervasive, with negative impact on all facet of the country. Ekechuku (2021) submitted that corruption has ravaged all the sectors in Nigeria and it is responsible for the under development, economic and social crisis witnessed all over the country. It has become a societal norm and an acceptable way of life to the extent that corrupt people are celebrated and recognized by awarding chieftancy titles to them or appointment into public offices. The various government at all levels have failed due to this cankerworm that has eaten up the whole country.

Educational Implication of Corruption in Nigeria

Elem (2019) Opined that corruption in educational sector in Nigeria is responsible for the low standard of education in the country. As a result of half backed graduates that Nigeria institutions turn out every year, the rate of unemployment has continued to rise. It is a well-known issue that no economy in the world no matter how viable, will be able to completely grow and be sustained without well trained and educated one's, hence the need to adequately take care of our educational sectors. Madaki (2019) alluded that corruption in the education sector has more serious implication for the country in general because it short-changes members of the society in its provision of their fundamental human rights of social service. Corruption encourages mediocrity, impacts orderliness, abandons merits and equal competition which goes against the objectives of education in global stage. The study established that corruption in educational sector has engineered the feeling of frustration, disgruntlement, immorality, militancy, infrastructural deficits, poverty and lack of foreign investment. Ngita Njoka and Ndegwa (2019) submitted that corruption in education portends a bleak future by withdrawing from people their worth. Rewarding unmerited achievement and normalizing society mistrust. Similarly, corruption and poor governance are a major impediment to the realization of the right to education. Corruption is one of the most problematic forces in the world that intuitively undercuts the expected education gains in all social and economic areas. Chatham house (2021) maintained that in societies where corruption is widespread, and where children witness authority figures such as parent and educators engaging in corrupt practices, the value of integrity is eroded.

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Jarome and Anekwe, (2022) Opined that corruption in tertiary institutions have far-reaching consequences. It jeopardizes the provision of qualitative education for the citizenry, there by leading to drop in tertiary education standard.

Social Studies Education Panacea for Tackling Corruption in Nigeria

Edinyang and Usang (2012) used the philosophy and Objectives Social Studies education and concluded that Social studies is a value free and value laden subject with the capacity to build sound morals and integrity in all facets of the society and that the subject has five unique ways of bulldozing corruption in Nigeria: exposing students to socio-civic competence and effective citizenship, inculcation of worthy attitude and habits, use of enter-educate institutional mode, Social content area and finally using integrated holistic framework. Akintola (2013) maintained that Social Studies education is an avenue for providing young people with a feeling of hope in the future and confidence in their ability to solve the social and environment problems of individuals, their country, state or nation. This implies that Social Studies has all it takes to solve the problems that is affecting the society such as corruption, insurgency, banditry, kidnapping.etc. Ogunwu (2016) maintained that corruption can be fought through re-orientation of values, development of positive attitudes that transform the moral qualities and consciousness of the individual and the entire society. More importantly the role of Social Studies teacher in curbing corruption cannot be underscored. The teacher is the most influential and life changing model as she/he is practically with the students teaching them society core values. Like Germany, Singapore and America are built on trust, discipline, liberty, equality and free enterprise Nigeria cherished values include integrity contentment, discipline and service. All these can be inculcated into the learners through using the instrumentality of Social Studies. Omale Mumini and Salisu (2018) Submitted that Social Studies education by virtue of its nature and content is able to bring about the desired change and national transformation because it places a premium on corruption prevention, avoidance, resistance, non-indulgence or abhorrence via right character propelled self-discipline as against coercive discipline of the anti-corruption efforts or commissions. Proper teaching and learning of value contents in Social Studies will not only improve conceptualization of values but will also curtail other societal ills such as excessive materialism, examination malpractice, cultism, corruption, Social and political differences in Nigeria. Adebayo Olatunde and Obaje (2020) opined that Social Studies education teaches the practice of virtue, values, skills which is the ultimate route to behavior change or modification that could reduce corrupt practices among teachers in Nigeria junior secondary.

Conclusion

Based on the paper, corruption had a great implication to the educational and socio-economic development in Nigeria at basic level of education. Which made some teachers and schools to collect gifts from the students which resulted in producing unproductive graduate that cannot move the country forward to achieve economic growth. Therefore, the paper concluded that greediness and selfishness of some people entrusted with positions of authority to serve the people and also the political interferences with bad leadership of not doing the right things to the people such as protecting the life's and properties, provision of social services, taking care of the welfare of the workers, salary increment among others are the major causes of corruption in Nigeria. This is why Social Studies education become a necessary tool which if effectively use to inculcate positives attitudes and values of loving one's country coupled with contentment and integrity the corruption will be tackle in Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following suggestion were made in respect of this paper to tackle corruption in Nigeria at basic level of education.

1. **Attitudinal Change:** There is need for change in behavior people should learn to good and discard their old ways of attaching much value to worldly materials. Instead they should be contented with the little they have and allowed peace to reign for one's betterment and that of the society.
2. **Strict and Severe Punishment:** Government as a matter of urgency should give autonomy to the anti-graft agency and court to do their job without interferences. This will make possible the perpetrators of corruption to face the law of the land irrespective of their class, gender, religion or political affiliations.
3. **Welfare Package:** There is need for both the Government and Private employers to take adequate care of the welfare of their staff's rewards, increase salaries. This will motivate the workers to put in their best not only that it will also make them not to delve in corruption.
4. **Good Leadership:** The Leaders should ensure that they provide good leadership to their subjects such as protecting the lives and properties of the citizens, and social services etc. when leaders are doing the right things and declare zero tolerance in corruption citizens will dare not involves in corruption.

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5. **Teaching of Social Studies:** There is need to teach and prioritize the national values (discipline, tolerance, integrity, contentment, honesty and patriotism, etc.) embedded in the Social Studies content which will help to tackle the problem of corruption in Nigeria.
6. **Creating Awareness on the dangers of corruption:** There is need to embark on massive campaigns by the government, civil society organizations to educate the people dangers posed by this ugly diseases (corruption) this could be done via different media such as radio, televisions, online etc.

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Technological Challenges among Human Kinetics Distance Learning Students of Nigerian Universities: An Analysis of Academic Coping Strategies

*Ogunleye, Oluwasogo Ruth¹

Email: dokitasogo@gmail.com

Tel: +234 813 651 8023

Ajala, Racheal Bolanle²

Email: ajala_bola@yahoo.com

Tel: +234 806 718 1254

Ajayi, Olusegun Adewale³

Email: segxyajayi@gmail.com

Tel: +234 805 955 6131

¹Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja

²Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education, Osun State College of Education, Ila -Orangun

³Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education, Emmanuel Alayande University of Education, Oyo

Abstract

This study examined the technological challenges experienced by Human Kinetics distance learning students in Nigerian universities. The review highlighted several challenges such as technical issues with the learning platform, limited access to computers, shortage of electricity, poor pedagogical skills, ineffective time management, lack of instant communication, digital divide and poor internet connections. In addition, the results highlighted various coping strategies adopted by the students such as increasing their duration of studies, forming online study groups, and utilizing physical libraries. With technology providing many benefits to human kinetic educators and students' learning experiences. It also assists the students in finding balance between a healthy use of technology and the negative effects it may cause. The findings of this study offer implications for those who are responsible for creating, managing, and delivering Human Kinetics distance learning courses in Nigerian universities. The study establishes the importance of reliable technical infrastructure and access to learning resources for successful completion of the courses. Furthermore, it provides the basis for designing strategies to reduce technological barriers faced by students. The results of this study may also be useful in understanding and supporting the coping strategies adopted by the Human Kinetics distance learning students in Nigerian universities. It was therefore recommended that online academic counsellors should be provided for the learners.

Keyword: Technology, Human kinetics, Coping strategy

Introduction

Technology has helped to advance educational progress, but there are still certain challenges. By offering internet connectivity, equipment like tablets and PCs, and developing programmes to increase computer literacy for both lecturers and students, the majority of distance learning-based schools are demonstrating their support for higher levels of technology in the classroom. The advantages of educational technologies are commonly recognized by instructors, but they frequently find it difficult to integrate new technologies into their classrooms in an efficient and effective way. Technological integration poses serious difficulties for educators at every level, from purchasing new technological equipment to adapting curricula and teaching methods to include new educational resources. Human kinetics is a discipline that focused on the comprehensive practice of human movement and exercise as well as its impact on health and physical performance (Angba and Abass, 2018). In order to research physical activity and health, the curriculum promotes interdisciplinary and interprofessional approaches. The main goal of distant learning is to give student employees a simple way to earn a higher degree. Despite the interconnected benefits, there are obstacles for both learners and suppliers. Because a portion of the Human Kinetics course is practical in nature, the difficulties cannot be overstated. According to Ojo (2009), these difficulties can be divided into social, environmental, institutional, educational, and psychological. Distance learning in Nigeria Universities is mostly hybrid, which allows the students to have an interactive session in form of revisions before examination.

While they are far apart, technology will tremendously aid both the tutor and the students in receiving information regarding teaching materials and homework. More specifically, technology supports teachers by enabling them to use videos to illustrate the movement skills that students will develop during learning situations. As a result, information regarding the teaching materials for the subject will be easier to transfer and both teachers and students will learn more. Another issue is that not all faculty members recognize the value of incorporating technology into the teaching and learning process (Ogunlela and Ogunleye, 2014). Also, lecturers who are not technological inclined, are a challenge. Therefore, the need to strive to integrate technology in the learning process and directing them to achieve optimal learning goals for the students. Based on students' transition from the classroom walls to the boundaries of virtual reality, it is very important that every distance learning based institutions must provide effective online learning so as to deliver quality education and outcomes-based education to students. Sometimes, students are not prepared to embrace the tutor's introduction of technology as a tool for learning. The difficulty for learners is in how well they comprehend how to use technology wisely for educational objectives. If teachers, students, and the institution all support one another, the deployment of technology use in Human Kinetics learning will go well. Video recorders about sports movement techniques, sports-related movies, the internet, and mobile fitness apps are just a few examples of the technology used by human kinetics lecturers in the learning process. These apps can be downloaded from the AppStore. Another challenge is the inadequate faculty support for learners which could also affect students' ability to progress and complete their study (Osafu, 2017). In Agbofa (2012), the student's motivation could be affected due to the less contact between students' peers and tutors as a result of the once in a while face-to-face arrangement. Also, the usage of part-time facilitators tends to pose several instructional challenges to the learners.

In those days, distance learners in Nigeria are largely adults, and parents, suggesting a huge demand on their time. Due to poor economy and the need for many young ones to cater for themselves as well as desire to further their education, many now engaged in distance learning education. The demands of these multiple roles on these distance learners could pose work, academic and life balance-related challenges. Students could have herculean tasks attending to the demands of their personal lives, academic activities and that of their employer. Inability to address all the dictates of the three constituents (life, education, and work) will result in work and life conflict among distance learners. Work, academic and life conflicts further pose high-level stress upon distance learners and ultimately affect their academic performance (Segbenya & Peniana, 2021). Students may be distracted when using technology for academic purposes, making it difficult for them to multitask. In Sharaievska et al. (2022), learners are not the only ones who experience stress or anxiety when learning to use technology in the classroom, many instructors experienced stress when learning new technology and having to work extra hours too. Teaching students how to use technology efficiently is an integral role of every educator, however, educators need to lead by example when it comes to using technology within the classroom. With technology providing many benefits to educators and students' learning experiences, assisting students in finding a balance between a healthy use of technology and the negative effects it may cause is critical. The use of technologies in higher education classrooms has both positive and negative consequences. Although the positive effects outweigh the negative ones, it is critical that the negatives are not overlooked because they can be detrimental. Distance learners face psychological, socio-religious, and financial challenges as a result of their various personal and family roles and responsibilities (Ojo & Okon, 2019).

Also, the usage of hired facilities belonging to a second circle institution to deliver a university course content also comes with associated institutional-related challenges regarding the suitability of furniture and washrooms, among others, for distance learners (Segbenya et al., 2019). All these challenges could affect the academic performance or outcomes of distance learners. The face-to-face tutorial and the dependency on the print media- modules/course material for teaching and learning also come with inherent challenges to the distance learner. Delays in supplying modules or course materials could affect the academic performance of distance learners. Furthermore, distance learners could also face an institutional challenge in the form of delays in resolving student assessment-related challenges and communicating timely feedback on students' continuous assessment. Failure to give feedback on students' continuous assessment can affect distance learners' preparation for their examinations (Agbofa, 2012).

Conceptualization of the problem

Higher education is becoming more and more in demand in Nigeria, which is made worse by problems like the rising expense of educational infrastructure and the government's reduced budget. As a result, online education is now viewed as an urgent solution. Even though it can provide convenience, flexibility, and affordability, using technology is also linked to a number of problems, particularly in Nigeria.

Theoretical Perspectives to the problem

Benefits of using technology for online teaching and learning

Across the globe, the higher education system is now transformed to a world where extreme usage of tablets and social media is very common for both teaching as well as learning. According to Angeli & Valanides (2013), technology has played and continues to play an important role in the development and expansion of online education. The way we use technology for teaching and learning has enhanced our education and also proved to have a positive impact on the education process. This adoption of technology has enriched the popularity for Open and Distance Learning (ODL) among learners as it offers flexibility and accessibility. Barbour and Kennedy (2014) found that online teaching encouraged teachers to adopt a new role of facilitators, assisting students to develop problem solving skills, stressing critical thinking, and encouraging collaborative interaction among students. Similarly, ODL lecturers also found that the usage of technology can improve the interaction as well as collaboration among learners. Technologies assist in handling large number of students from different parts of the world and hence at an institutional level, learning using technologies may be considered as a cost-effective teaching method (Botham & Mason, 2007). Technologies can transform higher education in many ways: Digital technology enables fundamental shifts in instructional methods, content and assessment (Weir, & Connor, 2009). The benefits of using technology for online teaching and learning are well documented in literature. Some of them are:

1. **Learn at own pace:** Open and Distance Learning offers the learners the opportunity to study at their own pace. According to Sargent & Casey, (2019), students report benefits of using learning technologies such as the ability to learn at their own pace, to learn independently and to have fun. With the help of technology for online teaching and learning the materials can now be accessed from a computer or from mobile devices. This has created more opportunities for the learners.
2. **Promotes interaction:** Technology offers the opportunities to promote interaction between learners, learners and lecturers as well as with experts in ODL. Nowels & Hewit, (2018), reported that interaction can increase learning and lessen the psychological distance involved in ODL. Similarly, interactions can help in achieving the learning outcomes and thus ensure successful learning. Interaction in turn can promote students' motivation and can enhance the whole learning process. According to Croxto (2014) online courses with high levels of interactivity lead to higher levels of student motivation, improved learning outcomes, and satisfaction over less interactive learning environments.
3. **Promotes higher-order think skills:** Technology tends to promote critical thinking and problem-solving skills among learners. There are many platforms that can be maximized by lectures for the sake of critical learning. Such include: Google Docs, Telegram, Google meet, Microsoft team and Discussion Forums among others. (Moralista & Oducado, 2020).
4. **Opportunities for real-time student assessment:** Technology allows continuous monitoring of the learners' progress in terms of reading, participation in discussion forums and even the amount of time spent on the virtual learning platforms. Digital technology makes it possible to monitor how long students devote to readings and videos, where they get electronic resources, and how quickly they master key concepts (West, 2012).

Empirical Perspectives to the problem

Challenges faced in online teaching and learning in Africa

1. **Access to technology:** Access to technology is also a challenge, especially in many parts of Africa. The underdeveloped areas, as in other countries on the African continent, face challenges in accessing information technology as a result of poor infrastructure (Bandalaria, 2019).
2. **Digital Divide:** When compared with other countries of the world, digital divide in Africa is a main constraint. This is major barrier for the usage of technology for online teaching and learning.
3. **Pedagogical skills:** Online lecturers need to acquire relevant skills to teach online, they are also challenged to develop curricula of an exploratory nature that engages learners with hands-on, inquiry-based learning.
4. **Ineffective Time Management:** Effective time management can be difficult in a distance learning environment, where students are challenged to pace themselves without the support from friends and peers that would help them stay focused in class.
5. **Lack of Instant Communication:** In a conventional university, communication occurs instantly, making it simple for students to ask clarification on unclear subjects and receive replies. Communication is frequently asynchronous in an e-learning environment, which causes a chasm between the teacher and the learner. Sometimes these gaps might lead to misunderstandings, which can cause a problem to worsen before it can be addressed.

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6. **Not Receiving Timely Feedback:** One of the most significant and impactful ways that an instructor interacts with a student is by giving feedback. Students may feel confused or unsure about their goals, their progress, and their performance in the course if feedback is delayed by additional days or weeks due to an online format.
7. **Not Receiving Clear Instructions or Expectations:** It's always crucial to set clear expectations for students. Otherwise, they can only guess at whether they're performing tasks and projects correctly. While setting clear standards is a challenge in any classroom, asynchronous communication can make it a greater obstacle.

Practical Solutions to Challenges faced in online teaching and learning

Here are four steps that teachers can take to help position e-learners for greater success in the virtual classroom.

1. **Time Organization:** Effective time management is a fundamental skill for distance learners. Facilitators should encourage their learners to take advantage of the numerous time management apps and resources that are available to e-learners, they are mostly free. These include daily planner worksheets, infographics, and even a time management calculator. Education experts also recommend periodically surveying the students, which provides one with actionable insights into how the students allocate their time toward various tasks. Guidance can be done too.
2. **Utilize Educational Technology:** Just because communication occurs over the internet doesn't mean it has to be lagged or asynchronous. In fact, there are countless free tools to help students and tutors communicate in real-time. For example, video conferencing software can be used to have live conversations with the students, either one-on-one or in group settings. This gives the students a chance to ask questions, raise concerns, and work through complex course material more successfully. In addition to video conferencing software, instant messaging apps can be used for students who prefer to communicate via text. Examples include Skype, Google Meet, FaceTime, Zoom, and Google Hangouts.
3. **Increase Peer Review:** For students to assess their performance and make improvements, they require prompt, insightful feedback. The feedback that students receive can be enhanced in a number of ways. One strategy is to arrange one-on-one or group meetings with them, for instance, once a week or twice a month, during which you'll provide them feedback on recent work. Allowing the students to give feedback on each other's work more frequently is an additional strategy.
4. **Provide Clear Grading Rubrics:** Rubrics and syllabi are important tools in the traditional classroom. The facilitators should maximize it in the virtual classroom too. Be sure to provide the students with a clear and detailed overview of the course, including information about:
 - a. Resource materials
 - b. Learners' materials
 - c. Mode of grading assignment
 - d. How to share or upload documents
 - e. Solutions to technical issues
 - f. Deadlines, exam dates, days off, and other special calendar events
 - g. Facilitators contact

Emerging technologies that can be used for online teaching and learning in Human Kinetics

Usage of technology in ODL teaching and learning has become very crucial nowadays. In the initial days of ODL the common technologies used for communication were emails and bulletin boards; these are now replaced with synchronous technologies such as mobile technologies, smart board and social media. In 21st century, there has been the replacement of physical textbooks with e-books (offline and online), tablets and ipads. Usage of social media for teaching and learning is also gaining popularity in ODL. Similarly, remote classrooms enhanced by video images (video conferencing), shared writing and display spaces (smartboards), and feedback mechanisms including polling and text chat (web conferencing) are very common in ODL (Anderson & Dron, 2012).

Theoretical review of coping strategies

Coping strategies are defined as methods employed by people to deal with situations that require a tremendous investment of their resources such as time and effort. Coping strategy can be reviewed based on the following theory:

1. **Transactional Coping Theory:** The transactional coping theory helps to discuss how and why individuals need to manage different circumstances and cope with challenges associated with situations.
2. **Emotional- focused Coping Strategy:** Emotion-focused coping refers to efforts to reduce the impact of emotional stressors. On the other hand, emotion-focused coping strategies deploy several tactics to mitigate or reduce related

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emotional stress produced by the problem. Even though both coping strategies are used in most stressful encounters, they depend on how one appraises the situation (Schwarzer & Knoll, 2007). When we are emotionally stressed, we may feel overwhelmed by feelings such as fear, anger, sadness, or shame. We may even feel numb or “spaced out,” with either too much or too little emotional response to the situation. In the process of coping with emotional stressors, there is need to regulate one’s emotions in various ways. Identify what is behind your feelings so that they don’t feel so overwhelming. Also, an individual must try to accept his/her feelings so as to avoid pushing them away, as well as reduce the intensity of the feelings through distraction or relaxation.

Emotion-focused coping can be positive or negative. Positive examples include talking or writing about their emotions through therapy or journaling, mindful meditation, or distraction with other activities.

Benefits of using emotion-focused coping

1. Emotion-focused coping is flexible. Emotion-focused coping gives you the tools to change your emotional response as needed. You might start out feeling overwhelmed and end up feeling calm. You might start out feeling too little and end up feeling energized.
2. Emotion-focused coping can be a good strategy to use before working on problem-focused techniques.
3. Emotion-focused coping can be helpful for all kinds of stressors.

Disadvantages of using emotion-focused coping

1. People with low emotional intelligence may find it difficult to be aware of and change their feelings.
2. Getting overwhelmed by altering feelings.
3. Getting to a new level of acceptance that is not helpful based on acceptance.

Problem-based focus coping strategy

Problem-focused coping refers to efforts to solve the underlying causes of stress. The problem-focused coping strategies relate to a situation where individuals solve the relevant external problem and include a problem-oriented approach aimed at the self (Kwaah & Essilfie, 2017). When we are stressed by a problem or challenge, we feel like we’re not in control of our lives and that we’re not going to be able to meet our goals. When trying to cope with these stressors, we may attempt to generate solutions and new ways of approaching the problem. You might try to reduce the intensity of your feelings by talking to an objective friend, brainstorming different solutions, or writing down your emotions to get them out of your head. Problem-focused coping has been shown to promote mental health, provide a sense of control as well as reduce depression, paranoid thinking, anxiety and aggression.

Uses of problem-focused coping

1. If there is need to solve the underlying causes of stress, then problem-focused coping will be more effective.
2. Problem-focused coping is a good choice when an individual want to feel in control of ones life and have a solid plan for solving the underlying causes of the stress.
3. Problem-focused coping has a positive effect on individuals’ mood.
4. Problem-focused coping can help reduce some of the negative impacts of stress.

Some weaknesses of problem-focused coping

1. Problem-focused coping doesn’t always reduce the intensity of one’s feelings.
2. Problem-focused coping can make one feel stressed about the challenges of solving the problems.

Institutionally related challenges and academic output of distance learners

Another challenge distance learners face is institutionally related challenges that manifest themselves in five main forms: infrastructure or study centre-related challenges, delay in supplying course materials, quality and calibre of course facilitators, delay in resolving students’ assessment-related challenges, internet or technology-related challenges for online courses (Segbenya & Peniana, 2021). Learners’ challenges regarding infrastructure borders on classroom furniture and washrooms. Distance educational institutions do not have their own permanent built facilities hosting their distance programmes in the various districts (Segbenya & Peniana, 2021). For this reason, they relied on franchised facilities or

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infrastructure/study centres in various communities to roll out their distance programmes. Most of these facilities are somewhat below the standard existing on regular campuses. The most extensive challenges distance learners have in these hired facilities are poor sanitary conditions and uncomfortable furniture in the classrooms, making sitting down for a long time during face-to-face sessions very challenging for distance learners (Segbenya et al., 2019).

Delay in printing course materials could be responsible for late distribution of modules to distance learners (Bampo, 2008; Osafo, 2017) found subletting the production function of modules to private entities as a cause of delay in supplying course materials to distance students. Such delays have the potential of impacting on students' performance and satisfaction with academic programmes (Segbenya & Peniana, 2021). Distance learners also have several challenges with the calibre of course facilitators appointed by the various institutions to handle such courses (Fricke, 2010). The part-time tutors are sometimes not committed to the distance programmes and are not of the same qualification as their counterparts in the regular stream (Segbenya & Nyieku, 2021; Mamhute, 2011). The commitment and qualification differences could affect tutors' delivery of course materials and could also affect distance learners' ability to do well in their academic programmes. Thus, institutional related factors could have effect on educational output and the coping mechanisms adopted by distance learners.

Conclusion

The challenges that have been identified in this study include challenges that come from the environment (availability of facilities & infrastructure supporting technology integration), teachers, students, and other school community support are some of the challenges that must be faced by all person that concerned to be able to integrate technology into learning. The challenge of using technology in Physical Education learning can be a platform for formulating solutions that can be used in overcoming problems of using technology in the Physical Education teaching and learning process.

Recommendations

1. Face-to-face counselling could be supplemented with electronic or online counselling sessions to cover every distance learner to enable them to obtain good grades, complete their academic programmes on time, and enhance their satisfaction level for the distance education programme pursued.
2. There should be decent and suitable teaching and learning facilities for face-to-face sessions, if need arises, most especially for practical classes.
3. There is need for continuous in-service training for the course facilitators so as to update their technological skills and teaching methodology.

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